

***TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENTS ON COUNTRY BASED FIVE-
STAR HOTELS IN COLOMBO, SRI LANKA.***

A Dissertation by:

Sachin Samarasinghe

Supervised by:

Prof. Rasika Aponsu

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Doctor of
Philosophy in Hospitality Management.

**IIC UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, CAMBODIA,
2024**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

Declaration

This dissertation contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any University or equivalent institution, and that to the best of my knowledge and belief, contains no material previously submitted or written by any other person, except where due reference is made in the text of this thesis.

I carried out the work described in this thesis under the supervision of Prof. Rasika Aponsu.

.....

Sachin Samarasinghe
Student ID: FNR190129

.....

Date

(Supervisor's comments to be written here)

.....

Signature
Prof. Rasika Aponsu

.....

Date

Abstract

The tourism industry in a country is considered as one of the most crucial elements that is a development factor. Since Tourism is a popular topic, customer satisfaction accounts majorly in the industry towards its success. Over the past years, the hospitality industry has been showing many improvements where the hotels are immensely benefited quite a lot in terms of revenue. Therefore, when considering this extraordinary upshift hotel factors are considered which broadly focusses on the modern technology that hotel amenities are comprised of.

However, considering the hotel development of Sri Lanka, it consists of many five-star accommodations for guests to choose from. This ranges from International hotels chains such as Hilton Colombo, Shangri-La and Sri Lanka based hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel. However, the Sri Lanka based five star hotels entails the ancient atmosphere being the oldest hotels in Ceylon. Moreover, these hotels lack the modernization that most contemporary tourists consider prior to setting a reservation. When comparing to the modern hotel amenities, certain aspects can be taken into consideration by the hotel owners in developing the current standard of these hotels that equally provides a ancient cultural atmosphere and modern technology. Technology is a vital factor that every industry focusses on today. And lately with many improvements to the hotel industry technology is considered as a key factor of development to greater heights.

So, the author tends to focus on the importance of technology in developing the amenities and facilities of these hotels, considering these hotels compete equally in Sri Lanka, most tourists prefer the cultural atmosphere in these hotels. However, simultaneously eco-friendly developments on these amenities would also be linked to provide extensive improvements.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my appreciation towards all the individuals who assisted me in the possibility of completing this research report. A special gratitude goes towards my supervisor Professor Rasika Aponso for contributing in stimulating the encouragement and suggestions, which helped me coordinating my projects especially in writing this report.

Also, a special Thank you will be rendered towards my parents and my mentors in motivating me. Furthermore, I have to acknowledge and appreciate the effort given to me by the hotel managers for their valuable information in my data collection who in fact gave their maximum in assisting me to distribute the questionnaires among the guests. Last but not least, I would like to thank the IIC University of Technology, Cambodia and ICBM campus of Sri Lanka for providing the necessary guidelines and information to complete this report.

Table of Content

Abstract.....	3
Acknowledgement	4
Table of Content	5
List of Tables	8
List of Figures	11
Chapter I - Introduction	12
1.1 Tourism Background in Sri Lanka	12
1.2 Hotel Industry in Colombo	13
1.3 Major challenges faced by the Hospitality Industry in Sri Lanka.....	14
1.4 Destination Satisfaction of Tourists	17
1.5 Hotel refurbishments – a shift upwards on a hotel.....	18
1.6 International hotels versus Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo	21
1.7 A developing factor of the Hotel operations Process - Technology	23
1.8 The future of Technology in the Hospitality Industry	24
1.9 The Hospitality Industry going Green.....	26
1.10 Importance of Technology on the Hospitality Industry.....	27
1.10.1 Objectives and aims	28
1.10.2 Research Questions.....	28
Chapter II – Literature Review	30
2.1 Factors in the growth of Tourism in Sri Lanka.....	30
2.2 Major challenges faced by the Hospitality sector of Sri Lanka.....	36
2.3 The Hotel Employee – a vital customer experience factor	36
2.4 An assist to hotel staff via Technology Introduction.....	38
2.4.1 Guest service	38
2.4.2 Hotel and Employment Management.....	38
2.4.3 Reporting and Analysis.....	39
2.5 Ongoing concepts on Technology in the Hotel Industry	39
2.6 Smart Hotels.....	41
2.7 Internet of Things and ICT	42
2.7 Responsible Innovations	43
2.8 State of Art Hospitality services	49
2.9 Kano Model	52

2.10 Technology Amenity Guest Satisfaction.....	56
2.11 Modern findings	58
2.12 Hotel Information System (HIS)	65
2.13 Hotel Personalized Service	68
2.14 Technology Acceptance Model	73
2.15 Environment Friendly practices in hotels.....	81
2.15.1 Greening trends in hotels.....	82
2.15.2 Maintaining an Eco-Friendly environment for Hotels in Colombo with the current Status	88
2.16 Future of Technology in the Hospitality Industry.....	91
CHAPTER III.....	94
METHODOLOGY	94
3.1 Introduction	94
3.2 Research Philosophy	95
3.3 Approach of research	96
3.4 Research Strategy.....	96
3.5 Time Horizon	97
3.6 Research Framework.....	98
3.7 Hypothesis development	102
3.8. Research Data	103
3.9. Measurement – Primary data collection.....	110
3.10 Secondary Data Collection	113
3.11. Data Collection Procedure	113
3.12. Sampling method	114
3.13. Method of Data Analysis	115
3.14. Validity of the Questionnaires.....	116
3.15. Research Limitations	116
3.16. Research Reliability	117
3.17. Research Validity	120
3.17.1. Research Reliability and Validity	122
3.17.2.Ethical Validity	123
3.17.3. Generalized Validity	125
3.18. Data Analysis	126

3.18.1. Data Analysis software	126
3.18.2. Reliability Statistical Analysis	126
3.18.3. Normality Statistical Analysis	126
3.18.4. Inferential Statistical Analysis	126
3.18.5. Correlation analysis	126
3.18.6. Regression Analysis	127
3.18.6. ANOVA Analysis.....	127
3.18.7. Regression coefficient	127
CHAPTER IV	128
DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS	128
4.1. Introduction	128
4.2. Descriptive statistics.....	129
4.2.1. Demographic data analysis	129
4.2.2. Descriptive data analysis for variables	141
4.3. Reliability analysis	160
4.4. Validity Analysis of variables	162
4.5. Factor Analysis	164
4.5.1. Sample Adequacy	164
4.5.2. Communalities	165
4.5.3. Total Variance Explained	165
4.6. Correlation Analysis of variables	167
4.7. Multicollinearity Diagnosis Test	169
4.7.1. Multicollinearity diagnosis by Pearson correlation coefficient	169
4.7.2. Multicollinearity diagnosis by VIF value	170
4.8. Multiple linear Analysis	171
4.9. Cross Tabulation and Chi square Test	177
4.9.1. Gender and advanced technological experience that mostly prefer	178
4.9.2. Age category and advanced technological experience that mostly prefer	179
CHAPTER V	183
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	183
5.1. Conclusion	183
5.2. Discussion.....	185
5.5. Limitations of the study and suggestions for further research	186

List of Tables

Table 1:- Mandatory requirements for a five-star hotel in Sri Lanka facility wise	20
Table 2:- International hotels versus Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo.....	21
Table 3:- State of Art Hospitality services	49
Table 4:- Greening trends in hotels.....	85
Table 5:- Operationalization.....	112
Table 6:- Frequency Table of Gender	129
Table 7:- Frequency table of age group	131
Table 8:- Frequency table in which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel	133
Table 9:- Frequency table of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations.....	135
Table 10:- Frequency table of Do the rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc.	136
Table 11:- Frequency table of as a tourist, would you prefer making reservations online via the hotel website?.....	137
Table 12:- Do most of the international hotels you have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website?	138
Table 13:- Guest and employee preference for payment method	138
Table 14:- Preference for In the future, advanced technological experience, do you believe, will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction?	141
Table 15:- As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations (PF1)	142
Table 16:- Frequency table of Most of the hotel amenities and equipment's require technological developments in this hotel (PF2)	143
Table 17:- Frequency table of this hotel can develop further on the concept of Sustainability (being eco-friendly) (PF3).....	144
Table 18:- Frequency table of when reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities are (PF4).....	145
Table 19:- Frequency table of Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use (PF5).....	146
Table 20:- Frequency table of There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel (PF6)	146
Table 21:- Frequency table of Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests' easy access to hotel facilities (CF1)	147
Table 22:- Frequency table of Payment method should be further developed where transactions are done via a hotel app or website due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic (CF2)	148
Table 23:- Frequency table of Tech Savvy guests and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experiences prior to booking a hotel (CF3).....	149

Table 24:- Frequency table of Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees (OF1).....	150
Table 25:- Frequency table of Tourists tend to prefer technological developments favoring towards sustainability (OF2)	151
Table 26:- Employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel (OF3).....	152
Table 27:- Frequency table of When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired (OF4).....	153
Table 28:- Frequency table of Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees (OF5).....	154
Table 29:- Frequency table of Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catchi.....	155
Table 30:- Frequency table of with the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective	(GS2) 156
Table 31:- Frequency table of Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. E.g.: developed IT facilities (GS3)	157
Table 32:- Frequency table of The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field (GS4)	159
Table 33:- Frequency table of In the future hotel prices needs to extensively increase if further technological changes are to be made	160
Table 34:- Reliability Statistics for Product factors (PF)	161
Table 35:- Reliability Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF)	161
Table 36:- Reliability Statistics for Operational factors (OF)	162
Table 37:- Reliability Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS).....	162
Table 38:- Validity Statistics for Product factors (PF).....	163
Table 39:- Validity Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF).....	163
Table 40:- Validity Statistics for Operational factors (OF).....	163
Table 41:- : Validity Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS).....	164
Table 42:- KMO and Bartlett's Test for the sample data.....	164
Table 43:- Communalities of likert scale items	165
Table 44:- Total Variance Explained	166
Table 45: Correlations of variables.....	169
Table 46:- Correlations between independent variables.....	170
Table 47:- Coefficients.....	171
Table 48:- Collinearity Diagnostics	171
Table 49:- Residuals Statistics	172
Table 50:- : Variable enter/ removed.....	174
Table 51:- Model Summary	175
Table 52:- ANOVA table	175
Table 53:- Coefficients	176
Table 54:- Case Processing Summary.....	178
Table 55:- Cross tabulation	179

Table 56: Chi-Square Tests179
Table 57: Symmetric Measures.....179
Table 58: Cross tabulation.....180
Table 59: Chi-Square Tests181
Table 60: Symmetric Measures.....181

List of Figures

Figure 1 : A student's perception on the Hospitality Industry (compiled by author).....	16
Figure 2: conceptual framework of the reasons a tourist revisit an international hotel chain (compiled by author).....	20
Figure 3:- The research Onion.....	94
Figure 4:- Factors affect to overall hotel conditions	98
Figure 5:- Conceptual framework of Guest and Employees satisfaction	100
Figure 6: Graph of Gender	130
Figure 7:- Bar chart of age group vs frequency	132
Figure 8;- Bar chart of in which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in hotels	133
Figure 9:- Bar chart of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations.....	135
Figure 10:- Guest and employee preference for payment method	139
Figure 11: - Scree plot	167
Figure 12:- Zresid Normal P-P Plot	173
Figure 13:- Scatterplot of the regression model	173
Figure 14:- Histogram of regression model.....	174

Chapter I - Introduction

1.1 Tourism Background in Sri Lanka

World Travel and Tourism Council stated in 2011 that the Hospitality & Tourism sector is one of the highly important and rapidly expanding sectors from a Managerial perspective to many national economies. As a growing industry and with the competition that is existing between star class hotels, each Hotel thrives to become the best choice of many travelers (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2011). Considering each tourist destination, tourists have a wide choice to choose from prior to booking a hotel they would prefer to spend their holiday at. Considering the current situation, an individual would come into conclusion that the choosing of a hotel eventually narrows down to the brand Loyalty. However, the brand Loyalty seems to depend on to a certain extent to which the meanings of Hospitality rendered by employees and the guests should match up, creating an image in the mindset of the guest when choosing a star class hotel for their stay (Kamoun, 2014).

According to Hemmington, the four key dimensions of Hospitality were identified in Hospitality Literature as Host – guest relationship, personalization, hospitableness and the little surprises that hotels tend to organize. The main aim of any Hospitality business is to create that one experience the guests look forward for and develop memorable experiences that would stimulate ones five senses. From the hotels point of view this is where the employees of hotels need to behave authentically by taking responsibility for the guest experience. Also respecting guests and developing a sense of security toward them is a vital key factor. Hotels that are able to capture this sense of genuine behavior can gain the competitive advantage by providing their guests with the experiences which are much more personal, memorable and that can add value to their lives. Is it that hotel employees treat their customers as potential friends (Hemmington, 2007).

Many natural attractions and highly diversified landscapes in Sri Lanka have many welcoming an immense number of visitors to the country. Considering the year 2018, a pandemic free year it has accounted to 2.3 million tourists arriving in Sri Lanka whereas in 2017, 2.17 million tourists were welcomed to the country. The revenue which was generated through Tourism remained to be a high contributor towards the national economy which contributed a sum of 5.1% towards the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) for 2017 and 2016. Understanding that the tourist arrivals

increasing over the coming years, Colombo has more than 14 hotel construction projects which are scheduled to be opened in 2022. This will create an opportunity for approximately 2000 hotel rooms to arise if the above project becomes successful amidst the Pandemic situation. Sri Lanka recorded an average daily revenue of LKR 20,500 which was in the year 2018 and also recorded a fairly good occupancy rate of 60% for the same year however due to the Easter terror attacks in April 2019, all the key indicators recorder much fewer figures compared to 2018 (Mordor Intelligence, 2021).

India continued to be one of Sri Lanka's largest supplier of tourists where tourists' arrivals grew by 7.8% each year from 2014 – 2017. China was considered the second largest market where the Western Europe accounted majorly from countries such as Britain, Germany and France. According to Fitch Ratings, an estimate of tourists increasing 15% for the next four years was predicted in 2015 however the chances decreased with the Easter attack taking place in 2019 (Word Press, 2015).

1.2 Hotel Industry in Colombo

Colombo is considered as the heart of Sri Lanka where it is the home to many popular five-star hotels. When tourists arrive in Colombo, they have an array of options to choose from to spend their unforgettable stay in Sri Lanka. Considering that they also can enjoy their stay in Colombo with respect to Sightseeing, shopping and Entertainment facilities. An understanding in 2016 was made by the government that all well renowned hotels in Colombo must increase their star class mostly who were in the range of 3-3.5 stars. However, many four-star hotels were directed towards improving their quality and thereby could receive the recognition in later years as 5-star hotel. Considering this improvement, the government wanted to enforce high pressure on existing five-star hotels to maintain their standards and expectations to obtain the competitive advantage. An exploratory research that was conducted in Colombo, it was discovered that customer loyalty was key whereas service quality played a vital role and as two marketing strategies for gaining that competitive advantage spoken above (Abeysekara et.al, 2016). There are tangible aspects in any five-star hotel in Sri Lanka which expands to color, music, lighting, comfort and overall cleanliness of the different locations inside the hotels. It is quite clear that all these effects have an effect on the customer perceptions which would directly have an effect on brand loyalty. There

are intangible dimensions in these hotels which would be focused specifically on reliability, assurance, responsiveness and empathy. In any five-star hotel the dimension of reliability is defined as delivering the promised performance accurately (Ambepitiya et.al, 2017).

1.3 Major challenges faced by the Hospitality Industry in Sri Lanka

According to World Bank group in 2013, the five-star hotel sector in Sri Lanka faces two major challenges. As mentioned above one of the major challenges is that since there are many five-star service providers in Colombo the authorities face difficulties to implement standards and to assure the quality of service unless the hotels implement them by themselves. The major challenge that they face is the need for dynamic service staff that delivers better quality service for their guests. Considering most hotels are operating at the moment barely reaching the breakeven point. The major issue is that most employees are lack the necessary experience to run a tourism business using the modern management applications (Wijesiri, 2010).

According to Dr Chandana Jayawardena, in 2020 it was identified that as for the facilities and comfort rendered by the five – star hotels in Colombo there is somehow overdevelopment but there is also a shortage of trained employees. Dr Chandana has also mentioned that the government needs to have a control over the overdevelopment at eventually it may lead to price wars and this he was identified as an improvement and quantity of hotels but the service being lagged. A suggestion was put forward to attract the Sri Lankan five-star hotel employees abroad to return the output of the hotel schools in Sri Lanka. Currently it would be approximately 20% of the requirements that is being presented by the hotel schools in Sri Lanka and a proposal where incentives can be offered to large hotels in Colombo area to expand their training and development department into future hospitality schools (DailyFT , 2020).

A private sector approach was introduced to address on the skilled worker shortage, which was launched as a roadmap on Sri Lanka tourism and hospitality workforce competitiveness which was scheduled as six-year strategy from 2018 – 2023 in Colombo. This initiative was first launched with the intention of identifying what the tourism and Hospitality industry is lacking, that needs improvement and draw young hoteliers in to the industry. According to Tourism skills Committee chairman Mr Malik Fernando, the main aim by 2023 would be to make the hospitality

industry in Sri Lanka well developed by providing the necessary training and support on the young talented workforce that in return would improve the Hospitality industry with skilled employees in the near future. A tentative plan of the road map was to build up to 100,000 more tourism sector employees in the next three years in 2018. The road map included that the number of training strategies needs improvement as there was a lack of proper training that created the skill gap (Jayasuriya, 2018). According to the Sunday times in 2017, numerous foreign hotels in Sri Lanka was seeking to import foreign labor to fill the shortage skilled worker gap. As there were many foreign hotels under construction, many hotel owners were urging the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka to allow to import well trained and skilled staff to work in Sri Lankan five-star hotels. According to Miss Manik Suriyarachchi, the managing director of the Emirates Academy of Hospitality Management mentioned that one of the top five-star hotel under construction has plans to import approximately 250 Filipino workers with the purpose of filling the gaps in the trained and skills staff shortage in the Hospitality industry. It was also stated that almost every hotel in Sri Lanka does not invest much on uplifting the standards of the staff in order to retain them from leaving the industry to migrate to abroad or to a hotel that pays well. However, it will be quite important to invest on training the staff to be more skilled individuals and this strategy has to be continued (Moorthy, 2017).

A research was conducted in 2015 that assisted in examining the perception of many graduates in Sri Lanka on gaining employment in the tourism and hospitality sector in Sri Lanka. The study resulted in many Negative perceptions than the Positive perceptions. The main reasons for this Negative perception were that the respondents mentioned that there is less stability and low pay in the hospitality industry. The graduates have also mentioned that the working hours can be long whereas the hours are unsuitable to lead a normal life and can directly impact the family life by these unusual working hours. The high achieving students were recruited into the management training schemes that consists of Operational experiences that was conducted only between 12 to 18 months. With the completion of the student's university studies, graduates possess well developed academic skills and by this they would expect that the industry they work in would allow them to apply the knowledge that they obtained from academic courses. Considering Sri Lanka, many students are interested in areas such as Human resources and Marketing. The belief

is that in the Hospitality Industry, having skilled, enthusiastic and committed graduates is the vital success in the Hospitality industry. Towards the end of this research numerous factors were considered by graduates that provided much insights about their perceptions (Wijesundara, 2019)

Figure 1 : A student's perception on the Hospitality Industry (compiled by author)

According to Kaldeen and Nawaz in 2020, with respect to many unskilled workers employees in Sri Lanka's finest five-star accommodations, it was later revealed that this in return would lead to poor planning and management and poor value addition. A strategy was put forward called Knowledge Management (KM) in order to patch the strategic failures that could harm a hotel. The challenge for the hospitality sector in Sri Lanka is formulating the KM implementation strategy and to decide which kinds of inputs are required to improve a hotel's performance. Because with the level of skill of the employees in a hotel a strategy as such was said to be important which could resolve many issues. However, it is quite important to understand that Firm is dealing with the knowledge and understanding of the employee. It is said that previous studies have shown KM infrastructure and process capabilities has impacted greatly on a firm's performance irrespective of the industry. However, it was identified that KM capabilities will assist to drive strategy, follow best practices, solve problems, improve further knowledge on the products and services, cross fertilize different ideas and create opportunities for innovation. So in order to make KM practical, Organizational culture, Human capital and Information

Technology is required simultaneously that forms the KM process Capability and in return improving the Organization Performance (Kaldeen et.al, 2020). However, this strategy was introduced with the intention of uplifting the hotel development from the workforce point of view. But it is vital to understand that the main argument lies in the employee's skill and knowledge level to apply this theory and make it function.

1.4 Destination Satisfaction of Tourists

Currently most developing countries tend to attract visitors from developed countries and also many other developing countries through various pull factors such as attractions, attributes of the destination and mostly tourists consider the features and the quality of the hotel they will stay at. In any hospitality business there is a direct linkage between the service quality and customer satisfaction. Therefore, it is considered that customer satisfaction is the foremost important factor in Hospitality Marketing. Understanding that Sri Lanka is one of the best destinations for tourist arrivals, mainly the Five – star hotels in Colombo play a major role in the holiday satisfaction, which a hotel is considered as the second home of a tourist. According to the SLTDA, in 2018 many tourists chose Colombo and greater Colombo as their first choice of Accommodation where five-star hotels mostly benefited with a 79.2% occupancy rate in 2018, however with the Easter attack in 2019 reducing the accommodation rate to 57.9% whereas Colombo was only second to the South Coast region in that year. Towards the end of 2017, there were a total of 119 449.000 room nights spent by foreign tourists in Colombo Specifically. (SLTDA, 2019). Understanding that many tourists prefer five-star accommodation, their perceptions are vital on hotel facilities that also has a direct impact on customer satisfaction. As mentioned by Wuest, Taz and Emenheiser in 1996, perceptions on hotel attributes is considered as the degree to which tourists find different services and facilities which are significant that will increase their satisfaction during their stay at the hotel. According to the research conducted by Poon and Low in 2005, it was identified that quality and customer satisfaction as the best differentiation strategy. Therefore, it was advised that hoteliers need to actions or necessary steps to identify the satisfaction levels of their customers (Gnanpala, 2014).

1.5 Hotel refurbishments – a shift upwards on a hotel

With the current situation prevailing in Sri Lanka, many hotels in Colombo find the opportunity to engage in refurbishments, though it is considered as value enhancement and delivering the required functionality of the hotel premises, its maintenance and preservation as it is importance to bring back to the usable condition. As understood refurbishment to the hotel building cannot be changed with parameters such as location, existing construction and orientation. Therefore, the changes will need to take place inside the hotel. An individual may consider the refurbishment factor as to changing the image of the hotel with different factors such as changing the wall colors, drape and carpet materials and even the location of certain objects to be moved as necessary. Among various interpretations of refurbishment, it may also refer to the upgrade a hotel may consider to improve their customer satisfaction. For example, back in April 2013, one of the major historic five-star hotel in Colombo the Galle Face Hotel stopped operation for 2 years up until 2015 to undergo a major restoration process where the restaurant area space was doubled, poolside bar and the terrace has seen extension almost closer to the beach area, and hand-crafted artwork especially with rich wood Mahogany was implemented and used where necessary to please their tourists in bringing the historic atmosphere in the hotel (Daily FT, 2013). As mentioned in the Daily Mirror online paper, Mount Lavinia Hotel another supremacy five-star accommodation in Sri Lanka has taken actions to do refurbishments to the hotel understanding that it would be important start once tourism booms in the country in the future (Daily mirror, 2020). According to Arian in 2005, there are five types of refurbishments and the reason for refurbishment is mentioned as:

- Space altering refurbishment – Change in use
- Pleasure refurbishment – Subject to changes as per the liking of the hotel owners
- Opportunity refurbishment – change of circumstances
- Optimizing refurbishment – Optimization of Economic factors
- Corrective refurbishment – The failures occurring in buildings

(Ekanayake et.al, 2018)

Considering the refurbishments conducted by Galle Face Hotel and Mount Lavinia Hotel, they fall under the category of Pleasure refurbishment as the hotel owners' keen interest is to give the two hotels a whole new image or appearance. However, as this research will focus on in later

depth is that hotels as such being only Sri Lanka based needs to focus much on Opportunity refurbishment as it focusses on better and unique methods of improving the process and functioning of the hotel.

As the research revolves on particular limited five-star hotels in Colombo, according to the standard of SLTDA, a five-star accommodation is graded according to the following where the expectation in Sri Lanka is much different as a developing nation compared to many developed countries.

Mandatory requirements for a five-star hotel in Sri Lanka facility wise		
No.	Item	Facilities
1.	Hotel Building	A minimum of 30 rooms including 3 suites. A suite needs to be 65 square meters or more in size where it needs to be with an attached toilet, dining and living area.
2.	Main services	A generator which is capable of providing 100% back up electricity supply. Acceptable number of service elevators are required for more than three floors which is a necessity to include in the ground floor.
3.	Bed rooms	The room door lock should be on a master key or card system that should need double locking facility from within. A keyless safety deposit locker of a appropriate size is a must in each room
4.	Restaurant and Bar	Glass washing machine to be available in the bar. An ice cube making machine to be available at the bar. Room service facility is a prime necessity which would include a wide variety of food and beverages.
5.	Kitchen	Lighting to be with diffusers to prevent insects entering into the kitchen. A dish washer machine with a pre wash sink to cater to all the cutlery and crockery.

6.	Location	Adequate areas with adequate facilities with good furniture for tourists for guests to relax and enjoy. Valet parking is necessary with an efficient car call up system.
----	----------	--

Table 1:- Mandatory requirements for a five-star hotel in Sri Lanka facility wise

However certain non-Mandatory facilities can be included in a hotel of the five-class category where the SLTDA has put forward as the “Smart Hotel” concept (SLTDA, 2016). These facilities are not limited to a certain extension however considering Colombo as a hub and home to many international hotel chains, to maintain the standard of their mother company, they follow the same regulations and the same amenities in their hotels here in Colombo.

In Colombo some of the leading international hotel chains such as Hilton Colombo, Taj Samudra, Shangri La are few to name that renders the quality and service as their mother company does. The reason behind this revolution is that the organization name tends to believe to provide their guests the same experience in all the countries they have started operation. According to Guruge & Silva, tourists tend to revisit a same brand of international hotel in Sri Lanka due to the following reasons:

Figure 2: conceptual framework of the reasons a tourist revisit an international hotel chain (compiled by author)

According to the above figure many international hotel chains in Colombo maintain the standards of their mother company with numerous facilities and considering the convenience of their

guests. The factors such as Accessibility of bookings, Intention to travel and the service quality widely depends on the development that these foreign hotels maintain with skilled labor, adaptive management and the facilities (Guruge et.al, 2020).

1.6 International hotels versus Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo

The main purpose of this research widely revolves on the fact of ways developing Sri Lanka based five-star hotels to the standard of International five-star hotel chains. Tourists are aware of major names including Hilton, Shangri La, Intercontinental and Four seasons however this research majorly revolves on improving the Colombo based hotel concept technologically. The below comparison will be essential in identifying the difference in revenue each hotel has earned via tourist arrivals of two major 5-star accommodations in Colombo.

Hotel	Galle Face Hotel (LKR)	Hilton Colombo (LKR)
Revenue earned in 2019	7,327,000.000	15,330,551.000

Table 2:- International hotels versus Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo

As per the table above, it can be understood that Hilton Colombo is depicting double the amount of revenue earned by Galle Face Hotel in 2019. Considering the damage on the tourism industry with respect to the Easter attacks in April, these two hotels earned much higher compared to \previous years but however, Hilton Colombo with much higher room rates than Galle Face Hotel has done well in terms of revenue (Hotel Developers Lanka PLC, 2019)

Considering the oldest two Hotels in Sri Lanka which is the Mount Lavinia Hotel and Galle Face Hotel established in 1877 and 1964 respectively hold much cultural value in Sri Lanka and at the heart of Colombo. Both hotels share the same amenities and the unique antique appearance. Galle Face Hotel room rates are marginally higher than Mount Lavinia Hotel (Tripexpert, 2021). Both these historic hotels had the visits of famous individuals such as Yuri Gagarin, Mahatma Gandhi, Richard Nixon, Princess Alexandra of Denmark and many more to name. Both these hotels share the historic culture throughout the hotel with its antique atmosphere but still are considered as two of the best five-star accommodations in the country. When it comes to Galadari Hotel of Colombo and Hotel Kingsbury, both these hotels share a common nature of modernization compared to the previous two hotels. Galadari Hotel was established in 1984 whereas Kingsbury

Hotel was established in 2012. Both these hotels share a modern concept in terms of appearance and amenity wise. These four hotels are well renowned in Colombo among Locals and cater to many special occasions such as weddings, birthday celebrations and certain functions because of the brand name. Considering many Trip Advisor and Booking.com comments tourists first speak on the cultural heritage concepts of these hotels rather than the facilities rendered by these hotels. The main difference between these country-based hotels and the international hotels in that Country based hotels are owned by a sole proprietor or partners of the local community. Whereas the international hotels in Colombo are overlooked by their mother company and therefore as mentioned before they are in need to maintain the same standard as their mother company where the evaluations are made regularly (Varotsis, 2019).

PROCESS & CONFIRM

Firstly, May I have your Last name and First Name spelling?

May I also have the accompany name and child name, please?

May I have your contact number and email address, please?

Which credit card would you like to use for this booking?

May I have a card holder name please.

WOULD YOU care for King Size bed or Twin Beds? And Smoking or Non-Smoking?

Is there any Special occasion for this coming stay?

1st Visit	Honeymoon	Anniversary	Vacation	Other
Share with them our Hotel's location or offer them the hotel's location map.	Say "congratulations" and share with them the Honeymoon benefit. (If available)	Say "congratulations" and share with them the Anniversary benefit. (If available)	Share with them some of Hotel activities.	You may share some of Hotel activities or other related to their interest.

Would you like us to send SPA Menu, Spice Spoon, and Dining by Design Menu once we finalize the reservation?

Our check-in time is and check-out time is

May I know your expected arrival time and flight details, please?

We also have a limousine service from the airport, would you like us to arrange this for you?

I already request an early check-in in our system which will be our first priority subjected to room availability upon arrival.

In case the room is not available, you can leave your luggage at our store room and enjoy our facility first.

Read the Closing SCRIPT

Penalty Charge of 1 night or full payment

Good —, Thank you for calling Minor Hotel Reservation. My name is —. How may I assist you?

Which Minor Hotel can I book for you today?

When are you looking at staying and for how many nights?

How many people and are there any children and elderly?

In order to make your stay convenience, We would recommend you / May I recommend you to book XXXX room for XXXX people

Have you stayed with us before? Are you a Discovery Member?

GUEST STAY STATUS

YES: Thank you for choosing us AGAIN for your coming stay. Share HOTEL Location. May I have your last name and first name spelling?

NO: Thank you for choosing us for your coming stay. Share HOTEL Location. How can I address you?

CHECK GUEST PROFILE

Reconfirm ROOM PREFERENCE

Check DISCOVERY Member account

YES: GUEST NAME, as you are a DISCOVERY Member you will get a benefit as
 GOLD member: Complimentary WIFI during stay, Daily newspaper, Complimentary 2 bottled drinking water.
 PLATINUM member: State Gold member benefit plus Platinum member benefit.
 BLACK member: State GOLD member benefit plus Platinum member benefit.
 For PLATINUM and BLACK member only I can also redeem the "Local Experience" for you once we complete.

NO: DISCOVERY is a loyalty program and you will be entitled a special selection of benefits such as Comp. WIFI during stay, Daily newspaper, Comp. 2 bottled drinking water. Members are recognized worldwide when they stay at brands with the DISCOVERY Collection: Kempinski, Pan Pacific and Marco Polo.

Is this a business or leisure trip?
 GUEST NAME, One moment please, Let me see what I have available.
 Offer 2 Room types (LEAD and UPSPELL) with FAB.
 Would you like a price on that?
 Quote Average Daily Rate with Deposit and cancellation policy
 Which of these room types sound most suitable for you?
 YES! Process the booking
 NO! May I put you on waitlist?

Offer an alternative HOTEL

Offer an alternative PERIOD

Offer an alternative HOTEL

Figure 3: Telephone etiquette standards in international five star hotels (compiled by author – resource acquired from Anantara Resorts, Sri Lanka)

(compiled by author – resource acquired from Anantara Resorts, Sri Lanka)

Maintaining a specific standard in the hotel is the main motto of any five-star hotel. It is a method of putting forward professionalism to their guests. As shown below, maintaining the standard is much defined because answering a phone call itself shows the standard is a must to be maintained in international five-star hotels. The above images were derived from a well renowned five-star accommodation in Sri Lanka. It is a standard that the whole hotel needs to follow chain wise as

this is that defines that the hotel is one group even though chain hotels are all over the globe providing the same service and quality to their guests. However, the same level is not expected from a Country based hotel as they serve for that particular country and city only. Therefore, improvements on Country based hotels being made is a vital factor for the development of those hotels at least towards the standard of the international hotels that would in return give much fame and recognition to these hotels worldwide.

This research is only limited to Colombo as it is understood that Colombo is the heart of Sri Lanka and over the past few years, and as mentioned above Colombo has seen many tourists visiting. Therefore, a strategy that attracts tourists and provide good recommendations about the hotel is vital. This research tends to prove how technology would cause an impact positively on Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo. A strategy where standard as the international hotels could be implemented if adequate training and knowledge been given to the employees where standards could be uplifted. However, exploring a diverse area for these hotels will be critical that could give a mighty push in terms of recognition and especially “word of mouth” situations. Improving the hotel in certain levels of with respect to technology can be critical factor as being hotels funded on its own and being the oldest hotels in Sri Lanka will be one of the astonishing changes in the Hospitality industry of Sri Lanka. The aim is to maintain the cultural, historic, traditional look of the hotel and set improvements to these hotels in terms of foreseeable technology.

1.7 A developing factor of the Hotel operations Process - Technology

At the moment online reservation system has played a vital role for these hotels making it quite convenient for guests to make reservations from any part of the world. Facilities of WIFI is a common factor in all common areas of these hotels and in each room making it accessible for the guests to surf the net at any time. Common technology improvements as such were established in hotels many years back now paving the way for the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels to do a much better improvement on technology wise and improve the hotels in a much unique method to match their standard to a certain extent as the international hotels in Colombo.

The COVID-19 pandemic has drastically made changes to the state of affairs in various areas in the travel industry. Therefore, most researches prove that the best the best option that hotels need to adapt at this situation is to use the latest technologies, in a way that could attract that could increase their safety during and after the pandemic period that could make significant improvement to profit maximization. According to the future Hotel technology trends it is based on numerous factors such as:

- Increase in Revenue
- Increasing customer comfort level
- Applying Internet of things
- Workflow automation
- Optimization of service and development
- Reputation management and smart marketing

A hotel room is a crucial factor for any guest where the comfort which they look for lies within here. The Hotel technology trend will increase the comfort for the hotel guests and would optimize the check-in and check-out procedures which would be internally helpful for the hotel employees. According to many research's conducted hotel guests tend to lose their room key at many occasions or lock the rooms with the key inside. Therefore, one in four interviewees have preferred smart room keys. For example, a recommendation where a mobile app is downloaded to get full access to the room where keys are plastic cards will not be necessary anymore (Intellectsoft, 2021). Hotel technology is yet to be developed fully in the world where it is the beginning of a modern operation. As an industry where the time equals money, hotel technology is mainly focusing on making operations faster and easier for the hotel staff requiring a few numbers of employees with a fair industry knowledge and with adequate training – while levelling the guest experience.

1.8 The future of Technology in the Hospitality Industry

Currently technology wise, all five-star accommodations commonly adapt booking engines, Websites, payment solution and check-in/out software that assists the hotel employees and also the guests. According to Kansakar, Munir & Shabani in 2019 put forward that Digitalization of

services is a successful strategy that pushes the hospitality services to the guests touch-point. The purpose of digitalization is that it a useful service platform that it affords guests the ability to plan, browse, and also choose activities at their own convenience which would directly integrate technology into the guest's travel experience. Booking and reservation services, location-based services and more importantly personalized communication with a touch of social media integration would be critical areas the modern tourist may consider. Guests could be encouraged to use in house applications over third-party applications to special incentives such as coupons, loyalty points and bonuses. The future of the hospitality Industry is being shaped accurately with the introduction and the boom it has with regards to Internet of Things (IoT). The Internet of Things has a vital effect as it is the interconnection of everyday physical devices such as mobile devices. The connection between the hotel and the IoT is that this is a factor that gives rise to the "smart hotel concept"(Kankava et.al, 2019). However as fascinating applying IoT on a Sri Lanka based five-star accommodation the preliminary factor to be considered is to introduce the technological factors which needs to be adapted first with respect to the funding. More technological improvements equal higher funding.

As per Solomon James, Vice President of IDS Network Group, the Hospitality industry in Colombo is said to be showing critical improvements if technology is implemented. This may include the following factors:

- Having control over processes
- The alignment of Business objectives
- Reduction of staff requirement
- Defining strategic hotel business priorities
- Guest experience will be much improved
- Delivery of services will be faster
- Guests become brand loyal
- Saving costs
- Maintaining market leadership

1.9 The Hospitality Industry going Green

As James (2011) mentions that tourists are becoming more gadget savvy with time and this would create the opportunity for hotels to improve certain amenities in the hotel technology wise. And from guest management to employee monitoring, this would reduce the use of manpower, which would also enhance operation efficiency, which would provide higher loyalty of customers and retention. Also, this research would revolve around how guests are becoming environment conscious. Many hotels today are turning to energy efficient lighting, heating, organic food, paper-based amenities. Most hotels in Colombo including Mount Lavinia hotels celebrate Earth hour on 19th March annually by switching off lights in the public areas, guest rooms and restaurants. Guests would enjoy a candle light dinner at this time. Also, many beneficial campaigns such as planting of trees in nearby schools is a method followed by many hotels in Colombo to promote an Eco-friendly nature (Mount Lavinia hotel, n.d) All Sri Lanka based five-star hotels maintain the procedures to save electricity and water as means of becoming eco-friendly. However, facility wise these hotels are in the need to improve in an eco-friendly manner because understanding many tourists demand Sustainable Hospitality as it is one of the latest trends. Technology wise the hotel is improving immensely whereas the Sustainable hospitality in the hotel would delight tourists greatly understanding that Sri Lanka is a tropical nation. Some important projects were introduced in previous years such “Greening Sri Lankan hotels” organized by the Ceylon chamber of Commerce of Sri Lanka which their main aim was to enhance the environmental performance of the Hotels in Sri Lanka and to increase their market acceptance which by promoting them to the market as low carbon footprint hotels where improvements will be made on water, energy, waste management systems and minimalizing operational costs (Ceylon Chamber of Commerce, 2008). None of the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo maintain technology developments whilst being Eco-friendly. As they are urban hotels in the heart of Colombo maintaining the green strategy has not being successful comparing with many outstation five-star Sri Lanka based hotels. Because with the improvement of technology in a hotels the guests would certainly prefer to have paper based amenities in their hotel room that would in return give rise to customer satisfaction. As the hotels chosen for this research are bringing much heritage culture to Sri Lanka as few of the oldest hotels in the world bringing out the eco friendliness in their hotel sustains the ancient aspect more than the modern hotels or the international hotel chains in Sri Lanka.

1.10 Importance of Technology on the Hospitality Industry

Understanding that most hotels depend on promotions and discount offers currently, even the Sri Lankan based five-star hotels give much preference on earning revenue via special promotions on special days celebrated in Sri Lanka and worldwide. Special room offers for couples on Valentines day, Mother's day and Father's day is much common offers provided in these hotels. As closely understood Millennials are mostly tech savvy who are closely related with technology trends and to increase their interest on promotions and factors such as Search Engine optimizations is the initial step that a hotel should develop. If tourists travel to Sri Lanka on their holidays which they would reserve their hotel accommodation, if these tourists are visiting the hotel on these specific important days, the tourists would be quite aware about the special promotions beforehand whereas the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels lack this important strategy. Most promotions are not advertised via online however main target would be the local tourists. Most prominent business maintain mobile apps for their customers to freely get in touch with them. This will be a distinct feature for customers to browse what is available and reserve what the customers prefer in an app away. Necessarily in the hotel point of view this should not only be reserving a hotel room but many other features such as reserving a table for dinner or even a delivery online with respect to their food menu. Notifications can allow the customers to be alerted on any special promotion that the hotel is offering at the moment.

As per the research it widely focuses on a specific segment of the hospitality sector of Sri Lanka. A per the various findings put forward above it is quite clear that there is a gap between the Sri Lankan based hotels in Colombo and the development that these particular hotels immensely require. Therefore, with different factors mentioned above the improvement that it requires at first will be minimal and with time further improvements can be made to these hotels understanding the previous results. Because the main aim of this research lies on making processes easy for the hotel employees and in return achieving customer satisfaction. As per Sawyers (2017), hotel employees have long hours of work where they work according to shifts full 24 hours. And the workload is quite bottomless in a busy hotel. Understanding different seasons such as Christmas hotels tend to get much busier and the employees have much work to be completed. And to deal with frustrated and angry customers is a part of the job. Meeting their

requirement at the best is a part of this employee which can be much exhausting and sometimes these hotel employees require further assistance.

1.11 Research Questions and Objectives

1.10.1 Objectives and aims

1. To identify the different technological improvements that the Colombo based five - star hotels need to undergo
2. To determine the different departments of the hotels where the technological improvements need to made immensely.
3. To improve the functioning of the hotels made easier and better
4. To develop a plan for these hotels to invest on new technological improvements.
5. To describe as to how the guests and Hotel employees are satisfied with the new improvements

1.10.2 Research Questions

1. What are the different technological improvements can a Sri Lanka based Colombo five-star hotel adapt?
2. What leading five-star hotels in Sri Lanka that best suits for this improvement?
3. How will the technological improvements on different departments, improve their respective functions?
4. How do these Technological improvements assist to improve the customer satisfaction?
5. How can customer satisfaction be measured in the hotel itself?
6. How will these Technological improvements be an assist to the employees in the hotel?
7. How can employee satisfaction be measured?
8. How would these hotels need to invest in order to improve the technology?
9. How long would it take for Colombo based five-star hotels to invest on the following technological improvements?

The research will be a guide to many developing five-star hotels in Sri Lanka which seek to improve themselves in terms of facilities and Amenities. The facilities and Amenities are those which require technological developments. The main issue existing is that the hotel management is not focusing much attention on diversification or change. Considering the financial plan upon the technological improvements, initial steps need to be undertaken to introduce technological improvements on the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo. With time, later expanding technology depending on the financial plans in the hotel can be critical. The initial steps could take time however the best results intended. As described above, customer satisfaction is key which can be achieved with employee satisfaction. And towards employee satisfaction technological improvements play a vital role and these improvements immensely creates and increases customer satisfaction.

Chapter II – Literature Review

2.1 Factors in the growth of Tourism in Sri Lanka

The tourism in Sri Lanka started to first develop on a commercial scale in 1966. The country was then labelled as ‘Paradise on Earth’ by the tourists and the locals alike. Sri Lanka is different to many other countries due to its spectacular indigenous resources. Rich cultural heritage with different Buddhist festivals, high quality scenic landscapes, ancient monuments, safe beaches, significant wildlife lands and endowed with beautiful designated nature reserves which are some of the island’s main attractions. The government of Sri Lanka saw tourism as a very vital component in the diversification of the economy and which could be a good development strategy. During mid-1960’s and mid 1970’s heavy investment was organized to be used on tourism where many major hotels were constructed, roads and airline facilities were uplifted. In the late 1970’s, as there was a stress on market led policies and private investment, still the government paid much attention towards the development of tourism. For example, the government established their own Sri Lankan national carrier as Air Lanka back in 1979. Also, the government made regular inspections on the tariffs that has to be charged form the tourists. The expansion in tourism grew accommodation wise in Sri Lanka from 770 rooms throughout Sri Lanka in 1966 to 4,600 rooms in 1976 to 9,680 room in 1991 (O’Hare et.al, 1993).

It is understood that the possible contribution of the tourism industry was heavily influenced by international economic and political stability. Threats from terrorists and civil unrest too affected the destination in various occasions. However, there was a widespread view between the tourism analysts the tourists from other nations were much concerned about their personal safety and coming into conclusions that this industry could only survive under peaceful conditions underway. Taking Sri Lanka for instance a major downturn occurred to tourism when the country was affected by war and civil unrest. Tourist arrivals in Sri Lanka gradually declined to the lowest levels of 182,620 in 1987 which as a result of the ethnic conflict in the North of Sri Lanka which commenced in 1983 and the following youth revolution of 1987/1989 in the South of Sri Lanka. But with time the number of tourists arriving at Sri Lanka increased with the progress of the peace dialogue that had been with the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Elam (LTTE) which initially began in 1994.

During this period, many tourist attractions were being destroyed by the LTTE including the first notable tourist spot which was the wreckage of Yaldevi line bound for Jaffna in the Northern district. As per the Tourist Board of Sri Lanka in 2003, between the time frame 1994 – 2002, there was an average of 380,769 tourists' arrivals in Sri Lanka annually. The peace Process that was undergoing at that moment which led to more tourist arrivals and this led the opportunity for hotels to develop further as there was a downturn in Hotel Occupancies by 30 percent in the mid 1980's (Bandara et.al, 2004).

Another factor which affected tourism in Sri Lanka was on 26th December 2004 where the impact was unprecedented. The death toll was calculated to the amount of 30,957 and 5,644 missing. The coastal belt of the areas of Northern, Eastern, Southern and Western provinces were impacted immensely. However, an estimate of 105 large and medium scale hotels in these affected areas were partially damaged and 8 hotels were completely damaged. With respect to rooms, approximately 3,500 of the 13,000 rooms in the large and medium scale hotels were not operating till late February 2005. However, the damages were covered to a certain extent due to various insurance cover schemes by hotel owners as time went past. On the other hand, 2004 was considered a record year with tourist arrivals topping 566,000. An expectation was that the tourist arrivals would reach 600,000 in 2005 where there would be 150,000 arrivals during the initial three month of the year 2005. Because at least 40% of the foreign guest nights are usually spent in the coastal beach hotels mainly in the Eastern and Southern parts of Sri Lanka (Jayasuriya et.al, 2006). The future Tourists arrivals to Sri Lanka had a massive impact where the tsunami has damaged many tourism constructions which was visible and tangible which also caused damage to the tourism image of the country which is invisible and intangible. The latter damage was caused by mainly due to two means which one would be the physical damage and the perception that individuals had that the entire beaches in Sri Lanka and tourism was destroyed by the tsunami which indirectly led to a sense of insecurity. The negative tourism image was as of the perception had among the European tourists. In order to overcome the damage caused by the disaster the government implemented the recovery process in two phases as the 'immediate relief' and the 'rapid recovery' phases. The immediate relief phase mainly focused on the provision of reassuring measures for the tourists who are victims. The rapid recovery phase was focusing on the short-term recovery process and a long-term rehabilitation with a reconstruction

process which is aimed at gaining the interest of the tourists, the affected tourist communities being reestablished and the tourist infrastructure being developed.

As per the above figure, it could be identified that the tourist arrivals were gradually increasing from the year 2009 afterwards. The reason behind this boom was the end of nearly three decades of the brutal war by the LTTE in May 2009. The number of international tourist arrivals to Sri Lanka massively increased that broke all the previous tourist arrivals records considering monthly and annually. After this post war development in Tourism the Government of Sri Lanka launched a Tourism Development Strategy (TDS) which was initially planned for a five-year period from 2011 – 2016 where numerous targets were set by the local government to welcome foreign tourists into the country. The prime target of the government was to boom the economic

development after a major loss. Different marketing strategies by the government led the Tourism of Sri Lanka to be branded as “Sri Lanka – the wonder of Asia”.

<i>Peace Episodes and development effort of Tourism</i>	Periods of upward trends	The growth periodically (annual)
<i>Political, democracy and peace stability with a tourism master plan for 10 years</i>	1966 - 1982	22%
<i>Second wave of economic reforms including the Peace talk in 1989/90</i>	1989 - 1992	23%
<i>Constitutional changes discussed as a solution to the war</i>	1997 - 1999	13%
<i>The fire agreement being ceased and peace talk IV</i>	2002 - 2004	19%
<i>Boom after post war tourism</i>	2009 - 2017	26%

<i>Episodes of war and Violence</i>	Periods of downward trends	The growth periodically (annual)
<i>Eelam war I – ethnic riots taking place in 1983 and the escalation of the civil war in the Eastern and Northern provinces</i>	1983 - 1986	-15%
<i>Eelam war III – The collapse of the peace talks</i>	1994 - 1996	-13%
<i>LTTE attacking the economic nerve centers in Colombo city</i>	2000 - 2001	-12%
<i>Eelam war IV and the end of the war – the commencement of a full-scale war and the ending of the war in 2009</i>	2005 - 2008	-06%

Table 01: Tourism growth during the peace – war episodes

Source: derived from Sri Lanka Tourist Board data for 1970 - 2013

As shown above, table 1 depicts the average annual growth rates of the international tourists arriving in Sri Lanka during the different peace contracts. There are different upward trends shown which was a result of different tourism promotional campaigns. The second part of table

1 depicts the periodical growth rates of the tourists' arrivals during the political unrest and violence in the country that clearly shows a downward trend.

On 21st April 2019, Sri Lanka suffered another loss on Tourism, where there were bomb blasts on well reputed five-star accommodations in Colombo including churches. The Easter attack were suicide bombings carried out by extremists which eventually resulted in over 250 people being killed and this includes foreigners and at least 500 being injured. Prior to the terrorist attack, authorities have made an estimate that Sri Lanka would hit a massive target of 2.5 million tourist arrivals in 2019 where as only 2.3 million tourists visited Sri Lanka in 2018. Tourist arrival in Sri Lanka is much greater in the end months of October where it recorded a decline of 22.5% compared to previous years and a decline of 9.5% for November. However, seven months after the Easter Terror attacks Lonely Planet recognized Sri Lanka as the number one travel destination in 2019, but still continued to suffer a decline in tourism. In order to overcome this major loss, many hotels started operating with various discount schemes on different online and credit card offers that extended to 50 percent. According to Srilal Miththapala, a tourism specialist in Sri Lanka mentioned that with the Easter attack being occurred in April and everything having returned to normalcy, foreign tourists would still be unsure to visit the country.

However, with the conclusion of the terror attacks in 2019, it created a major issue for the hotel industry resulting in many senior professionals in the hospitality sector leaving either the hotel industry or the country because of the declining salaries. With less income being generated by the local hotels, the staff of the hotels started receiving low service charges and tips where most employees began searching for stable careers and futures (Mushtaq, 2019).

The Tourism industry of Sri Lanka was again affected in 2020, when the Covid-19 pandemic took over. The industry was facing many challenges as this was a vital issue for the Tourism and Hospitality industry. As per United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the pandemic has affected many tourist destinations around the world including Sri Lanka being one of the top tourist destinations. Many hoteliers in Sri Lanka have lost their occupations due to this Pandemic and now are seeking opportunities in foreign countries or would be switching to different industries. A study was conducted on the industry as to how it impacted on the

employees of the hotels by the National Resource Development Council of Sri Lanka in 2020 and results showed that many people lost their jobs due to this deadly pandemic. The results were proven to show that 36% were low skilled workers and another 36% were semi-skilled employees who have lost their jobs. And 28% of the middle and junior level management were terminated. Therefore, understanding the negative impacts caused by the pandemic on the hospitality industry the loss of valuable employees and experts in the industry was a vital blow to the nation. With less Hospitality jobs available in the market 58% of the experts have emphasized the need to organize reskilling programs for the employees who are without their jobs in the industry to regain their knowledge lost so it would assist them to understand their jobs back again when the vacancies open in the Hospitality industry once the pandemic situation reduces.

Recommendations that were put forward by Hospitality experts to overcome this issue were as follows:

- Rather than targeting low spending tourists much attention has to be directed towards high spending tourists.
- An important message has to be delivered that the image of Safe Sri Lanka through media coverage, international marketing and promotional activities.
- Sri Lanka being a country well known for indigenous medicinal treatments and Ayurvedic medicines such as ginger, garlic, turmeric, veniwel geta and foreigners who are stuck in Sri Lanka have used these medicines and were quite happy with it uses. At the time Sri Lanka was doing very well fighting COVID -19. Word of Mouth causing many countries to use these treatment methods can allow Sri Lanka to develop such Ayurvedic medical packages and export to foreign countries.
- This would be the correct time where Sri Lanka can focus on Eco-Tourism as this lies far away from the Urban parts of the country more towards the rural areas.
- It will be very important to utilize the youth in the labor market and organizing re-skilling programs which can be conducted toward the tourist guides and the small and medium sized enterprises (SME) that are directly engaged in the tourism industry.

2.2 Major challenges faced by the Hospitality sector of Sri Lanka

The tourism industry has been the main factor to bring higher returns and boost the economy of the country since the conclusion of the three decades of the internal conflict in 2009. Since then, Sri Lanka has been a destination where the travelers are much interested in the sightseeing opportunities, the attractive beaches and authentic food dishes. These factors bring more enhancement towards the tourists' arrivals where with time Sri Lanka gained one of the prestigious name to be a well-known tourist destination. However, being a nation, which offers their tourists with many natural and cultural tourism and hospitality resources, important factors such as inadequate human resources and in certain cases unprofessional service are considered as key challenges in the Sri Lankan Hotel industry. Therefore, making it essential to obtain different global trends into account and utilize them to make the service providers of the hotels more professional and also improve the service quality.

Some of the main issues which are linked with the hospitality industry in Sri Lanka are identified as low pay and low wage jobs, temporary and seasonal jobs, poor awareness of tourism and hospitality job opportunities, massive labor turnover and negative social attitudes on the hospitality employment. Understanding the above factors from a tourist's perspective, some other major issues would be the repeated complaints regarding certain matters of the hotel such as an unpleasant arrival to the hotel, leach of proper attitudes to understand the customer needs and certain requirements, lack of proper communication and good interactive skills, delayed check-in and food service and delivery and mostly the unwillingness of the management to assist guests at certain situation.

2.3 The Hotel Employee – a vital customer experience factor

The Sri Lanka Institute of Tourism and Hotel Management (SLITHM) is the leading government organization that provides trained qualified hoteliers into the field since 1964. Mostly qualified hoteliers from SLITHM are operating in departments of the hotels such as front office, housekeepers, chefs and stewards. So, it is important to understand the current key Human resource challenges which would be a major assist to improve the quality of service in the Hotel

industry in Sri Lanka, a study was conducted on few employees working for well-known five-star accommodations in Sri Lanka and they very well emphasized that lower payment, temporary jobs, lack of training facilities were the main problems that they faced causing to many employees leaving the organization.

This depicts that the HR that's related to the hospitality industry in Sri Lanka is suffering from much in-depth issues. The dissatisfaction that tourists have on a hotel is greatly depending on the employees of the hotel and the satisfaction and the happiness of the employees play a vital role in this process. Understanding in many issues that the employees have to undergo they tend to switch to different industries or work abroad. From a tourist's point of view the service of the hotel is based upon the perceptions of what is received or even experienced. Considering a guest's behavioral approach this may include many types of consumer actions that would be delivered either in a positive or negative manner. The customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction can reflect directly on the hotel service experience which could either be appreciated or condemned by directing communicating with the hotel itself or sometimes spread the positive or negative word of mouth among other travelers. As per a study conducted by Umasuthan, Park & Ryu in 2017 both the cognitive and the emotional empathy of the hotel employees assist to determine the service experience of the hotel guests. It is very crucial that hotel employees to present themselves with a professional appearance and this considering to be a major factor that could satisfy the hotel guests. Grooming is a key factor that builds the customer confidence. The hotel managers need to be responsible that the attire, appearance and the attitude of the hotel employees are well maintained and up to a exceptional level because this is one aspect that the hotel guest may first-hand experience as they arrive at the hotel. In order to overcome certain issues as such it is vital that the tourism and hospitality HRM practices and upliftment strategies and as per many researchers it was identified that different HRM practices such as incentive plan, labor management participation programs, adequate training and pre-employment tests are considered as positive solutions to experience low labor turnover rates of the employees. With the research conducted on the five-star accommodations in Sri Lanka it was found that a practical HRM practice system will assist to influence the hotel industry's external, internal and also the global strengths (Umasuthan et.al, 2018).

2.4 An assist to hotel staff via Technology Introduction

2.4.1 Guest service

The main motive of hoteliers is to provide the best and highest level of service to their guests. But however, to make this much possible hotels provide their guests to achieve the best service with a click of a button. This paves the way to the hotel guests to witness effortless, personalized experiences, and the convenience of technology to make their stay a much positive experience. To date the best example of hotel technology is the Hotel PMS which records the guest information and also their preferences so that it would personalize their experience at the point of entry to the hotel.

This is where the room reservations department records the necessary preferences of the guest to the PMS system at the point of reservation, and through the system other acting departments such as Front office, Housekeeping and Food & Beverage acts upon the necessary requests made by the guest.

Currently the world-renowned hotel Marriot has developed an app as Marriot Bonvoy app which allows guests to check in freely and even send requests to the relevant department for different services via the app. The guests have the opportunity to send real time text messages to the front office if any questions or requests are there prior to their stay, during or even after their stay. This is considered as a crucial opportunity for Marriot to cater fully to the needs and wants of their guests and provide the personalized best experience for them.

2.4.2 Hotel and Employment Management

Adapting technology especially on hotel and Employee Management can assist in everyday operations and make it much more efficient from a hotel point of view. For example, the housekeeping processes in a hotel is mainly managed through the PMS system. This is a helpful tool of technology that allows the housekeeping staff the manage daily room statuses and track maintenance requirements through the computer. The system allows to assign hourly, daily and weekly priorities to the housekeeping staff and this allows to track room updates in real-time which would directly avoid delays for guests who are checking in.

Also, PMS system assists the front office department to maintain single guest profiles. In the past most hotels spent much time manually sorting records. But with the PMS system's Profile Match and Merge feature it helps the staff to identify duplicate in a very short time – which would save time and this improves the ability to deliver the guests with great experiences.

2.4.3 Reporting and Analysis

From the guest experiences to hotel operations, smart hotel technology offers a variety of cost saving and profit generating opportunities to the hotel. The reputation of the hotel mainly relies on the ability to collect, interpret and also respond to the information of the guest and their feedback. The Rate shopper tool is one of the most popular technology developments that most luxury hotel accommodations adopt in order to receive daily reports and it outlines the competitor rates, demand forecasts and Online Travel Agency rankings. Also, Smart thermostats are introduced which can sense fluctuations in occupancy and it responds accordingly that can help save on energy costs, also this tracks the historical temperature settings that assists to determine which room temperatures that most previous guests preferred (Major, 2019).

2.5 Ongoing concepts on Technology in the Hotel Industry

According to Mioic, Korona and Matesic (2012) have examined that the tourism demands the readiness and willingness to develop technological developments in hotels. As per a research conducted by the authors, it was identified that majority of the guests did not prefer the technological implementations ongoing in hotels and that the respondents were willing to see major changes in the near future and smart hotel concept would be implemented rapider. Another study was conducted by Neuhofer (2015) where the purpose was to examine the effect of implementation of smart hotel concept and how this would create personal experiences in the hotel. Because it is quite obvious in order to compete with competitors a change is essential. Also, the study has shown that Information and Communication Technology plays a vital role in the hotel Industry to create consumer experience. Another software similar to PMS is the Happy Guest Relationship Management (HGRM), a platform which provides and assist the hotel staff

with centralized solutions that brings together all the necessary information internal and external and could easily assign check in, check out times, special requests which would be visible for all the departments. As per the author, smart technology immensely assists the management of a dynamic service. By a smart hotel concept, this will not take over the personal human confrontation. Smart hotel concept technology is mainly focused on improving the human resource by equipping the employees and the hotel environment with technological improvements to increase service and the guests experience (Neuhofer, 2015).

A research was conducted by Jaremen et.al (2016) on the smart hotel concept and also identified its attributes. As the research showed, smart hotel concept is can be defined as a practical business model which utilizes Information Technology into the hotel industry which in return increases efficiency and also provide exceptional quality services towards their guests. The research also argues the fact that with respect to hotels, the word 'Smart' is much linked with smart technologies more than a smart organization. The attributes which were found out by the researchers were the broadband internet, the implementation of smart technologies such as apps on smart devices and methodical guest reservation systems. The authors also identified three main conditions that the technological developments in a hotel must meet prior to been implemented. Firstly, the technology improvements need to be safe for the staff and mostly the hotel guests. At second these technology improvements have to have proper functioning communication and thirdly these improvements must be integrated and has to be suitable for the systems that the hotel usually operates with. Another research was conducted on a five-star accommodation in Poland where the hotel managers mentioned many benefits which were identified after adopting technology developments in the hotel such as easy check-in and check-out, lower operating cost, hotel functioning with few staff members, fast delivery of services towards the guests, a low risk of mistakes occurring, east internal communication and more importantly upgrade the room standard. The research showed the implementation of smart hotel concept does have a positive impact on the image of the hotel and making the hotel much different from the competitors (Jaremen et.al, 2016).

Another research was conducted which was aimed to investigate how successful smart hotel concept is successful on a five-star accommodation to understand the possible gaps. In depth

interviews were conducted with hotel managers, investors and technology suppliers. Each stakeholder had different thoughts on smart hotel which mostly depended on the task or the role it played in the organization. Different stakeholders brought forward thoughts to smart hotel concept as service development, effective procedures or even in-room digitalization. The research later was identified that stakeholders were only concerned on the financial benefits rather than improving the customer experience, increase the guest stay experience and create a positive image on the organization. The research showed that there is a major gap between the definition of the theoretical concept of smart hotel and a practice that the hotel has to follow in the future. It is important for hotel staff or other stakeholders to understand that the concept of smart hotels is of more a complex product which would require all parties to be incorporating on many aspects to achieve one final goal (Leung, 2019).

2.6 Smart Hotels

Smart Hotels are also called as Intelligent hotels. Because prior studies have shown different components as to the reason, they have smart hotels which can be implemented on smart tourism or the smart hotels (Gretzel et.al, 2015). According to Leung (2019) the smart hotel concept can be inspected in three different dimensions as customer centric which focusses on in room and in hotel characteristics. Secondly there is employee centric which technology is an assist to increase operation efficiency and lastly manager centric where it saves the cost and increase profit for the organization. A smart organization is knowledge driven, the team is internet based and also dynamically adjust to the different organization plans and the methods adopted by the organization. Most organizations in the world currently are adapting to smart technology and it is largely linked with the smart hotel concept which widely represents a technologically methodical system of hospitality services arrangement. As per Leonidis et al. (2013) a smart hotel room *“provides a ubiquitous attentive environment that constantly monitors the activity and location of people and objects within it and uses this information to control technology in anticipation of the guests’ needs”* (Leonidis et al, 2013 p. 242). Few examples that may relate to these appearances are the systems which control the air conditioner, television, lights and signs for ‘do not disturb’ or ‘clean my room’. Understanding the importance of saving energy, a popular improvement on a hotel room is to set up systems such as sensors to save energy by

automatic lights dimming when no guests are in the room. More advanced features on a room widens to using a guest's smartphone or computer via a hotel app to activate and control some features such as adjusting room temperature, unlocking the room door with a scan via the smartphone.

According to Jaramen et al. (2016) various examples on technology were put forward which hotels currently adapt in various parts of the world. Hong Kong's Upper House guests receive an Ipod Touch at the time of Check in which includes games, music and information and facilities on the hotel and this gadget is tracked and secured by the hotel with antitheft facilities not allowing the guest to take it when departing the hotel for any reason. The Hotel Novotel Munchen Messe's guests are welcomed as they arrive at the hotel with real or a virtual receptionist in the front desk and at each important guest points there are touchscreen devices attached to the wall containing various information for the guests to scan through. Another example would be the Hotel in Poznan , Blow Up Hall the guests receive an iPhone to enter into their room instead of physical keys or cards (Jaramen et al, 2016).

2.7 Internet of Things and ICT

As per Mann (2015) Internet of Things (IoT) is considered as a network to many physical objects or 'things' that are embedded with software, sensors, electronics and network connectivity which enables these particular objects to derive and exchange data (Mann, 2015). IoT is basically a process where it connects devices with an on-off switch to the Internet causing the result of a major connected network. Internet of Things can refer to any electronic device or a machine such as a television, smartwatch, coffee maker or a smartphone (Pizam, 2017). However, it is vital to understand that as per certain studies conducted the Hospitality industry operates slower than most industries when IoT technology is applied. As it was the introduction of IoT on the hotel businesses the progress was operating with time. Apart from hotels, the tourist attractions are benefited where the IoT assist these places on safety and security, energy use, locking systems and to track any unusual activity caused by the visitors.

Information Communication Systems (ICTs) were considered as a vital component and had an effective input on tourism in most parts of the world. In the 1970s Computer Reservation Systems (CRSs) were established which assisted many hotels and the tourist destinations causing them to position themselves on the market further than other competitors (UNWTO, 2001). The adaptation of ICT has been evolved to many different spheres of technological developments. In terms of hotels ICT activities has been divided into two large groups as follows:

- Front office which includes the reservations, food and beverage, housekeeping and customer relationship.
- Back office which focusses on Human resources, Accounting, purchasing and revenues & expenses.

As per Ruiz-Molina et al (2010), ICT was divided in terms of Amenities as in – house ICT which includes the hotel operation system, in – room technologies and business integrated processes. And ICT that is used for external use such as electronic marketing and sales solutions, customer relationships managements and ICT solutions that is associated with the guests and including the communication with the suppliers and other related stakeholders. Beckendorff et al. (2019) has put forward some of the most popular ICT activities in the accommodation sector which are of four groups. The first group focusses on the office applications related to the hotel operations such as room reservation systems, guest check-in / check-out, housekeeping management and in-house guest information. Back-office applications such as purchasing, inventory management is considered as the second group. Guest related interface applications such as guest operating devices in the room such as television, radio, air conditioner, electric locker is considered the third group. The last group is considered as the ICT applications used in restaurants, banquet management and other operations such as menu management, item pricing and cost control. (Beckendorff et.al 2019)

2.7 Responsible Innovations

If a hotel is undergoing a higher efficiency of guests' experiences many researchers tend to believe that it is a result of adopting ICT in the hotel. ICT assists and practices the automation of operations taking place in the hotel, adopting self-service concept and also supporting in reducing the distribution and production costs. Using ICT in the hotel industry can vary to different hotel

categories such as luxury hotels, B&B and budget hotels. And also, ICT may make an impact on different guests such as leisure guests, business guests and families (Jaremen, et al, 2016).

Innovation is a key factor the hospitality and Tourism industry. Understanding that tourists tend to visit the attractions in a particular country that they visit, innovative tourism products may would deliver a greater amount of added value. At this point, destinations and the stakeholders tend to offer valuable experiences towards their customers. This helps the hotels and other destinations to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors. According to Hjalager (2010), has mentioned that there are five different types of innovations:

1. Innovations on the product or service – imposing different changes and improvements on a product or service can be directly noticed by a customer. Therefore if they are beneficial or exclusive for they tourists this will result the tourist using or purchasing that particular product or service.
2. Process Innovation – In a hotel the back-office, the activities conducted requires improved efficiency and productivity. Technology is considered the main factor toward the innovation of these processes.
3. Marketing Innovation – this includes new marketing concepts which may focus on the co-production of the brand and introducing loyalty programs.
4. Managerial Innovation – These focusses on improving the employee satisfaction with organizing new techniques of business processes, personal empowering and compensating the work done perfectly.
5. Institutional Innovation – This is where the organization structure plays a vital role in terms of networks, clusters and partners.

Figure 5: Innovation space model

(compiled by author)

As the Innovation space model shows a hotel focusses on the main two types of Innovations which are the Product and Process Innovations. Product Innovations bring about the new ideas and technology that has to be applied on the hotel facilities and amenities. This will further be expanded on understanding and identifying the suppliers who can provide samples and testing how successful these improvements would be once finalized. As mentioned above the process Innovation would mainly affect the hotel employees directly allowing them to make their day-to-day operations further easy. As per many studies many hotel employees complain the hardships and the stress in which they go through in their jobs where at most occasions they would be multi-tasking. Therefore, to some extend product innovations give rise to process Innovations.

As per the Innovation space model these improvements should be prior understood to be clear and direct in terms of an individual guest or all the guests and the employees as a whole. This is where many hotels follow the trend of providing excellent service and added facilities toward the

guests who have purchased high-end luxury rooms in the hotel especially the suites. The best examples that many hotels under take at the moment is providing butler service on guests who have purchased luxury accommodations. However as per many researches undertaken it will be critical to improve the customer service and freedom to witness technological facilities for all the guests of the hotel as a whole who is not differentiated on the sum of money they have paid to the hotel. It is important to understand that when a hotel develops innovative facilities inside their hotel it must be witnessed and freely available for all guests to use.

The next step on the Innovation space model is to make the innovations to a state of Novelty. The term 'Novelty' specifically means a quality which has to be new, uncommon and original. Therefore, the innovative facility has to be much creative and be different to some aspect from the current technological developments in a hotel. This leading to meeting the demand and the needs of the customers. Any technological innovation that the hotel develops has to be of much use to the hotel guest which could also make their stay more useful.

A more innovative hotel Marketing mix which is called the Seven Sensual Notes of Hospitality has put forward a new vision of the marketing mix in relation to the hotel guest. As per Dzhandzhugazova (2015) the areas are as follows:

- Smell – scents
- Sight – Hotel architecture, paintings
- Taste – Gastronomy and food
- Hearing – Music, Television
- Intuition – peace, security and satisfaction
- Touch – softness, warmth and texture
- Impressions – feelings and experiences

The seven areas mentioned above are those that attracts the attention of the guest. However, Intuition and Impression has direct impact on the guest where perception arising in the mind of the guests can be considered important. Perception then creates a mental image or idea in the mind of the individual which arises the need for satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Figure 6 : The model of information representation in the human brain (compiled by author)

The above model helps to identify that all the pieces of information which reaches the brain of a human is stored in the mind as a specific representation. At a situation of checking into a hotel via online when the guests check in all the facilities and amenities the hotel provides, at to some extend the guest is satisfied with certain technology improved facilities. And as an example, to the above fact, the Marriot Mobile app has three key features they provide to their customers where guests can check in before arrival, room ready notifications are received and they are able to enjoy an enhanced arrival experience. On the other hand, guests can basically skip check in queues and walk to their rooms by just unlocking the room door with an iPhone or Apple Watch. As mentioned above, the app allows the guest to chat with the hotel host up to 24 hours before their arrival to the hotel in case there are special requests that the guest desires to have (Marriot Bonvoy, n.d). Understanding a situation as such as per the above model mentioned, the guest after analyzing data (Marriot hotel app functions) then creates different structures and opinions in their mind based on what is witnessed during the reservation process. As the information is being processed, the guest would then create ideas, judgements, images, concepts and beliefs

which they would tend to believe that if such a process is done through an app which is technologically enhanced and methodical, other hotel benefits, exceptional service and more technology amenities will be provided by the hotel. A perception as such will be created in the mind of an individual (Ogiela, 2017).

According to Lam et al (2007) investigated the relationship that there is between self-efficacy, attitude, the subjective norms and the behavioral intentions that there is towards the hotel employees perception that is there towards the technology adoption. With a research that was conducted on some minor hotels in Hangzhou, China, it showed that attitude, self-efficacy and the subjective norms are positively related to the behavioral intention, perceived IT beliefs also has an immense influence on the intentions through the attitude formation and there are few task technology which is fit to appear and to interact with different perceived IT beliefs that has toward the attitude formation. According to Sarmah et al. (2017) has formed an extensive technology-based service model which assisted to identify the hotel guests innovativeness, the willingness to co-create and also the demand for the involvement and their interaction on the intention to develop new services using app in the smartphones in a collective manner. The findings revealed that the innovativeness in which guests possess and the need to interact with the service staff has a significant involvement on the involvement of the guests. According to Wu and Cheng (2018) by collecting opinions on smart hotel a conceptual model was made in order to synthesis on the dimensions of the technology attachment, dimensions of the relationship quality, the experiential risk with the experiential sharing intention was a critical factor. However, the study comprised of technology affection, technology identity and also the technology bonding which immensely proved to play a vital role in increasing the customers confidence related to smart technology of a particular hotel. Affection, identity and bonding of technology plays a critical role by influencing perceptions on the customer satisfaction, and this satisfaction causing an experiential satisfaction has a much positive influence on experiential trust and this trust and the satisfaction binds together causing the formation of experiential sharing intentions.

The above studies very clearly depict the as to how smart technology is applied on hotels will have an important cause which would directly impact the guest's experience, making it conveniently easy for hotel employees in the long term. Because smart technologies cannot only

rely on the enhancing the management capacity or the operational efficiency but the main aim is to uplift the service quality and the satisfaction. The main benefit is that operational costs will significantly reduce by adopting smart features in the hotel processes.

2.8 State of Art Hospitality services

When considering a digitalized hospitality service platform and in a situation where touch and interaction are crucial factors at an ongoing pandemic, guest facing systems are considered as important between the guest and the hospitality service provider the Hotel.

Guest facing systems	Hospitality services	In-room IoT Sensors
The Client terminal	Housekeeping	Temperature
Kiosk	Room service	Humidity
In-room tablet	Payment services	Ambient light
Cell phone	Loyalty programs	Motion
Remote control	Guided tours	-
-	Keyless Entry, Climate control, Lighting control, Automatic check-in	

Table 3:- State of Art Hospitality services

As per the above table, guest facing systems include mobile services related to hospitality services, point of sale terminals and many hand-held devices conveniently made for the guests to operate and use. However, these systems have to integrated into different three phases which is related to the guest cycle as the pre-sale, point of sale and post-sale phases which will provide a complete digital and technological service experience to the guests. Understanding the Covid-19 impact that it had on Sri Lanka and its affects on many hotels in Colombo, hotel guests would prefer a modern change to the hotels post Covid-19.

The purpose of guest facing systems is mainly introduced to ensure that there is guest satisfaction by allowing guests to control their environment. This is where guest facing systems play a vital role when considering factors such as automatic check-in and check-out services, keyless entry into the room and control in-room functions. Understanding that many hotels in the world such as the Marriot, Hilton worldwide and Starwood hotels have implemented the following facility the mobile brand Telkonet's Ecosmart offers a mobile application that has added features that allows their guests to have control of the IoT in-room facilities or products. The brand was meant to be ecofriendly to promote keyless entry which is connected with a Bluetooth feature linked to a software of the hotel (Telkonet, 2021). Most of the Hotels in Peninsula are developing in-room tablets which is their own line that will assist them to save costs allowing their guests to a variety of services such as room service, transportation arrangements, room services and stream online videos and order television channels.

On the other hand, guest facing systems provide their guests with location-based services that can give rise to guest satisfaction. This is considered as a vital factor because understanding while tourists arrive at a destination for relaxation, they may tend to visit various valuable and beautiful sights around. In 2016 there were more than 30 percent of the hotels in the world that allocated funds and budgets on the location-based technology. With regard to guest facing systems, this would enable guest-based technology that would offer on property and off property guest services which may include digitally guided tours, recommendations on the local events and attractions available and would also include dining and entertainment option suggestions. This is considered as a profitable strategy for the hotel where the guest will be assisted in moving around close proximities, exploring different areas during their stay and this allows the hotels to generate further revenue by preferably encouraging guests towards other sites around the hotel. The best example would be that Fontainebleau hotel of Miami, Florida tailor a schedule or agenda considering the guest's location data. Here, the hotel monitors where the guest arrives from and custom make an itinerary via their system and hence provide it to the guest upon arrival. If the guest agrees or is satisfied with the itinerary, they may choose to move forward with it as they land in a foreign nation which they may not be certain of where to travel or visit around if prior research has not been conducted.

It is important to understand that most services are offered to the guests via complex Back of House (BoH) management systems. The BoH management systems assist the hotel employees in various functions such as customer relationship management, sales and revenue management, housekeeping maintenance software and more importantly the property management software. When there are developments or changes which are made on the guest-facing systems and the IoT units this will create a significant enhancement on the capabilities of the BoH management systems. For example, the IoT facilities inside a guest room such as the thermostats, motion sensors and light sensors can be used in order to control the temperature and the lighting in a hotel room when the room is usually unsold or not occupied with a guest that allows the hotel to save energy on an approximate amount of 20 percent to 45 percent. The best example to support this matter is Starwood Hotels and Resorts adopting 'daylight harvesting' which is considered as a good energy-saving scheme which assists in saving energy and also increase the indoor lighting consistency and this will automatically adjust the energy efficient lighting by understanding via sensors the natural light that is detected coming into the room of the guest.

When guest facing systems are introduced, this allows the hotel to reshape the customer relations dynamic between them and the Hospitality service provider. The guest facing systems are introduced it allows the hotel to closely monitor the guest cycle by basically collecting customer preference data, about certain behaviors and locations. When this data is acquired the hotel and the BoH systems will make use of this data which will assist them in creating custom made guest profiles that will eventually provide personalized service to the customer allowing repeat business in the future. At any case if this refers to a chain hotel, these custom-made guest profiles can be shared with their partner hotels so that if a guest plans on visiting their network in another location or country, this ensures the services offered to the guests are greatly personalized.

Another important factor concerned with the BoH management systems is that this assists in building an online brand value to the specific hotel. The social media platform is key at a situation as such that maintains and develops good customer relations. Which is most uncommonly found in the present day is engaging guests to rate include a rating or a review to the hotel on the hotel's online portal. For example, Sri Lanka based hotels such as Galle Face Hotel and Mount Lavinia hotel currently does not follow a rating system via online nor on paper. The strategy followed is

to verbally communicate with the guest to provide a rating and review on the online reservation site such as Tripadvisor or Booking.com after their stay. The online status of a specific hotel via reviews and star rating directly impacts on the revenue of a company. On the present day approximately 90% of the tourists consider online ratings prior to reserving a hotel for their vacation. However, a negative review can result in a potential loss of a massive number of customers as well. So, it is the duty of the BoH management systems to closely monitor their online systems for any negative reviews or ratings and take necessary actions to mitigate these effects with productive strategies.

A key performance indicator used by many hoteliers would be Revenue Per Available Room (RevPAR). This is used to assess a hotel's ability that allows to fill a hotel's available rooms at an average rate. Consider a hotel's RevPAR increases and it means that that the average room rate or the occupancy rate would increase. RevPAR is considered as an important factor because it assists the hoteliers to measure the overall success and improvement over periods of the hotel (Amadeus Hospitality, 2021). It is important to understand that the BoH management systems assist in improving the revenue per available room of the hotel (RevPAR). And this is occurring by speeding the processes of the housekeeping and maintenance. The benefit of BoH systems is that it can schedule the housekeeping services efficiently with the aid of in-room technologies and guest preference profiles. At present times many hotels tend to close down rooms due to renovation purposes and upliftments. With the BoH management systems this will deliberately assist in reducing the downtime of hotel rooms, improve the use of labour resources and in the meantime, this would increase the guest satisfaction. Research has shown that the use of housekeeping management systems will be important as this reduces the payroll costs by 10 percent to 20 percent. With the aid of BoH management systems this will help to maintain the in-room and on-property smart systems. In the long term these systems will assist in identifying the faults and the failures in bear real-time which will help to facilitate quick maintenance.

2.9 Kano Model

The purpose of the Kano model is to understand the relationship between the fulfillment of customer requirements and the satisfaction of the customer. The Kano model was introduced

with the purpose of achieving customer satisfaction in respect to a specific product or service rendered. The model focusses on the relationship between the achievement of certain characteristics of a service or product and the satisfaction expected from a customer. The Kano model was introduced by Professor Noriaki Kano in the early 1984. Professor Kano has derived the information to create the model from the analysis of a customer and what the individual may wish to have as customer requirements in different kinds which may be a product or service. With the aid of the Kano model, it is possible for researchers to understand the expectations of the customers and also assist the producers of a product or service to consider them at the time of developing new services or products.

Figure 7: Kano Model

(Jou Lin, 2019)

As per the Kano model there are five categories which are related to customer requirements and has rare effect on the customer satisfaction. It is important to understand that different customers have different expectations and how a customer is satisfied will vary according to the product or service. The best example to support this aspect is that taking the factor of Safety in a flight and a hotel room that has a multimedia system. Both of them are very well implemented but it can be the most important factor for the customer rather than the safety of the hotel or the flight. It is important to understand that safety of the hotel is considered as a basic and a minor fulfilment

that does not influence customer satisfaction much however, the multimedia system of the hotel has direct impact and a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

In relation to Technology looking at a Sri Lanka based five-star hotel, the five categories of the Kano model can be linked as follows:

- One-dimensional – At this factor the customer openly expresses their requirement and the suppliers could easily fulfill them. When the requirements are implemented better, there is a very high probability of customer satisfaction. On the other hand, if the implementation is bad, the satisfaction of the customer will be lower. In the current world, this factor is usually considered as performance features. The purpose of this factor is to bring out the highest satisfaction of the guests once features on a product or service are better implemented. When taking the Hotel industry into account, especially the technology aspect, when the hotel offers a pleasant arrival upon the guest where the guest has to undergo hassle free check-in and paperless registration if required this is an example where services which hotels offer is operated with the intension of achieving customer satisfaction.
- Basic – These include the characteristics which are considered by the guests to be self-evident. It is important to understand that increasing the product or service value itself is not enough for an organization. Because if an improvement is made to a hotel in terms of technology it is important even though technology operates and does most activities in the hotel progression, employees need to perform their duties to their highest standards. Convenience is quite important but caring and attentiveness is rendered by hotel employees. According to professor Kano, this factor is considered as the “must-be” as it is the most important factor that is required and should be included and is the price of entry into any field or market. Hotel employees must not be misled with the fact that as features of a hotel are technologically developed their duties and responsibilities should not be degraded.
- Excitement – According to professor Kano, these factors are considered as “Attractive” because this factor is supposed to grab the attention of the guest. Researchers refer to this factor as Enthusiasm because the product or service should include features where guests do not necessarily expect from a product or service. These features will assist the hotel to differentiate themselves from other Hospitality service providers and be inspirational to the customer allowing them to increase the satisfaction. As mentioned prior, human perception allows the

guest to be overwhelmed with the slightest improvement in the performance of a product or service that would lead to overproportioned benefits. Taking Sri Lanka based five-star accommodations into account, neither hotel between Mount Lavinia Hotel and Galle Face Hotel provide Keyless entry to the room however keys are the prime entry. As technology is an emerging trend in the world today hotels as such need to adapt to such changes to gain a competitive advantage.

- Indifferent – These include features which are not much of an importance to the guest. These features do not increase the satisfaction of the guests and also no lower satisfaction during its absence. In terms of a hotel, guests tend to not provide much attention on the wall colors of the rooms, drape designs, floor tiles or the floor setting. However, the guest may tend to seek the features and amenities that they value with the amount paid.
- Reverse – At a situation as such, the guest may tend to dislike the features which usually brings up satisfaction in a guest. An example would be a non tech savvy guest may tend to dislike the technological facilities and amenities the hotel provides even though most guests may find it quite fascinating.

With respect to the Kano model on the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels in Colombo the factors of One dimensional and Excitement are lacking. The purpose of Kano Model on this research is to understand two vital criteria as:

1. The products or service's potential to satisfy the hotel guests
2. The investment that is required to implement features

(Dreesen, 2019)

The four hotels in this research rely deeply on customer satisfaction via service improvements rather than product developments. Considering the importance of technological developments these ancient focused hotels rely on the technology developments which are key in the modern world, in order to facilitate and make the guests convenience and employees duty much easier these hotels have adapted the PMS system as of today. And in-room free Internet facility is considered another added technological feature in these hotels which is becoming a common feature in many hotels currently. These are considered the only and vital improvements which has been made in a hotel of Sri Lanka based till date.

2.10 Technology Amenity Guest Satisfaction

Selecting a product which is based on the need and expectation are considered vital when determining the customer satisfaction. According to Skogland & Siguaw (2004) it was identified that hotel guest satisfaction is considered as an important component in the long term in the hotel business. As per Kandampully and Suhartanto (2000) mentioned that the influence on the hotel image on the loyalty of the customer and their satisfaction towards the service rendered, cleanliness and the price is essential. As per a research conducted by the Cornell University Center for Hospitality Research had conducted a research to determine the preferences of the hotel guests (Verma et al., 2007). The study was conducted using a web-based Technology Readiness Index tool. The purpose of this research was to find which category of guests favored Technology implemented in to hotel operations. To further identify which category of guests the survey was conducted in relation to the categories of young, elderly, highly educated, affluent and frequent travelers. The research was conducted on these groups with respect to certain groups of criteria relating to web-based hotel booking system, In-room internet facilities and convenient check-in and check-out. However, the results showed that mostly the elderly and the highly educated travelers did not mostly prefer a technology based surrounding in their hotel.

A further analysis was conducted by Beldona and Cobanoglu (2007) which included the division of guest-oriented technology into four categories that was based on the importance and satisfaction of the guest related to performance. The first category included features such as express check-in and check-out, remote control television and in-room internet facility which was ranked high on the two dimensions of importance and performance. A second group was introduced with high importance and low performance rankings which included the features such as WIFI facilities, alarm clock, conveniently assessable electric outputs and online reservation systems. This group consisted of people who considered these specific technologies to be important when choosing a hotel of their choice but was ranked performance low during room occupancy. A third group was also formed where it included features such as cable Television, Pay-per-view movies and in-room personal computers. These were rated as low importance level and recorded high performance scores. A fourth group was also developed where the features

included wireless access to the hotel website, business center, videoconferencing facilities a plasma screen television. A hypothesis was developed in this regard as:

H1 – There is a relationship with the hotel technology amenities, overall accommodation facilities and the satisfaction of the guests

As per the above research it was conducted among 3,000 travelers and according to the income earned the research showed the categories varied. The high-income earning groups preferred group three and four. So, the importance put forward by this research was that the income earned by each traveler is a vital factor when selecting a high technological room. Because each hotel sets prices to their rooms according to the facilities that each category provides. In almost every hotel, suites are graded as highly expensive because of the facilities and features they possess. Therefore, the research proved the important of the income in hand prior to reserving a high-tech facilitated room.

Another main purpose of this study was to examine how technology-based amenities had an impact on the hotel guest satisfaction. The survey also identified that the groups who were able to pay higher prices for the accommodations had a positive impact on the overall satisfaction of the and understanding that satisfaction is a direct determinant of future behavior, a positive fact was identified that the type of technology amenity is considered as vital factor in hotel selection and a repeat arrival. The study also identified that that not all technology amenities had a positive impact on the satisfaction equally. As per the study, comfort technologies such as in-built room, control panel for guests, an in-room computer and a flat screen television did not have the likeliest positive impact of the guest. The researchers put forward two important ideas for these results. The purpose of guests visiting a hotel is basically on vacation and with their day's agenda of visiting places and sight-seeing there is a very low chance of them being in the room. Therefore, they would rate these technology amenities as less important as their usage will be less than expected. Another reason would be that the impact of the technology-based amenities could be more closely related with the guest as popular devices that could be found in the guest's home or office. The amenities changed accordingly to the type of traveler. For example, business travelers had a strong impact on facilities such as express check-in/check-out, in-room clock and telephone

and a personal computer. The research proved that the satisfaction guests develop on Technological improvements vary accordingly to their purpose.

2.11 Modern findings

As per a finding conducted by Short (2015) of Software Advice:

- A combined value of 60 percent of the tourist prefer to choose a hotel that provides the guests to check-in and open doors with the aid of a smartphone.
- At an average of 13 percent of users of smartwatches between the ages of 18 – 34, this group prefers to reserve an accommodation with the aid of their smartwatch.
- A moderate amount of 37 percent of the tourists prefer to choose a hotel that has lobby technology that may include check in kiosks and touchscreen facilities.
- A percentage of 41 tourists prefer to choose a hotel which has facial recognition that allows to identify the guests and also enhance the personalization.
- Although a 40 percent of the tourists mentions that the main benefit of hotel technology would be that it reduces travelling costs.

With new technology being developed, smartphones are considered as a key factor in regard to developing the hotel technologically. It is important to link the technological aspect of the accommodation with the smartphone of the tourist for far better convenience. Also other technologies such as smartwatches are being pursued by many hotel brands. A good example to support this fact would be in 2014, when smartwatches were introduced firstly by Apple brand, some hotels were thrilled to introduce facilities where users can access it through their smartphone in emergencies where the smartphone battery is low or at times the mobile is at fault. This would allow the guest to have an extra option in case their smartphone is malfunctioning or on low battery. In 2015, most hotels started to use facial recognition technology in order to identify the demographics of the guest and maximize on personalization. According to a report in 2014, with a survey conducted by Software Advice most travelers had the interest in robotic hotel service. Almost 56 percent of the survey sample had mentioned the keen interest in trying the service especially popular among the younger adults or Generation Y.

As of today, many hotel guests prefer a handful of actions that can be performed with their smartphones. The most common functions are checking in prior to arrival and ordering room service. The latest development that was made via smartphones was the Bluetooth enabled door locks.

As mentioned prior in the research by the author, Hilton and Starwood hotel provide this opportunity to access the gym or the conference rooms apart from the hotel room. Research was conducted with the aid of 241 respondents and the result was as below:

Figure 8: Likelihood to choose Smartphone - enabled Hotel

(Short, 2015)

As per figure 8, 60% of the travelers prefer a smartphone friendly hotel. Lately smartphones have become a major factor in the hospitality field. The best strategy that hotels need to develop is that understanding that almost every tourist makes a reservation to their preferred hotel via a smartphone the best strategy is to develop a personalized hotel app so that guests can access the hotel easily room reservations.the best strategy is to develop a personalized hotel app so that guests can access the hotel easily for room reservations.

Figure 9: Hotel personalized apps

As shown in the above image, developing a specialized hotel app will be step close to interact with the guest. For example, via the mobile apps, hotels can push room upgrade offers and low prices and may promote specials to be served at the bar or restaurant right to the phone of the guest. With special offers on certain days such as Valentines, Father’s Day, Mother’s Day and other special days could be advertised on the app which will be easily assessable to the guest if notification options are enabled. The researcher has reached out to Hilton Worldwide’s Dana Shefsky the director of digital product and innovation of the hotel brand, mentioned that one-third of the guests have used the option of digital check-in with the room selection choice that is available in the Hilton Honors app. A surprising amount of 90 percent of the guests reported to being “satisfied” or “extremely satisfied” with all the features that is there available in the app and these guests would not hesitate to use it again.

Figure 10: Likelihood to choose Smartwatch - Enabled Hotel

(Short, 2015)

None of the hotels in the world have made immense improvements in terms of the smartwatch technology. The Bluetooth functionality in these devices could be used exactly in the process the smartphones re being used in situations such as opening doors or checking in. Research was conducted by Short (2015) with a minimum sample of 93 in the group. The research was to understand if the respondents would reserve a room at a hotel where this function was enabled. However, a number of 63 percent respondents of 93 had rated “more likely” to some degree that reserving a hotel room via a smartwatch is preferable (Short, 2015).

In 2018, Samsung Electronics America and the hotel operations Alice introduced a modern hotel management solution that utilized smart watches in various hotel operations such as staff

communications, quick responsiveness to the guests and also enhance the customer service. This solution was mainly introduced toward the hotel employees rather than the guests where key operations such as housekeeping, maintenance, bellman services and customer requests can be easily handled efficiently across various departments. This product was created by Samsung SDS where the product is combined with a hotel software called ‘Alice’ and the Samsung Gear S3 smartwatch is provided for hotel employees to make operations in the hotels much efficient. The luxury hotel chain Viceroy had bought together, Alice software and Samsung to assist the hotel employees with the implementation of a digital software. At a situation where the guest requests assistance on an issue in the room such as a broken toilet, towel / pillow request, that specific department’s employees will receive a silent vibration or tone alert to the smartwatch on the wrist. Once received the employee would respond or accept the specific task with a tap on the watch. It assists the managers to efficiently track the tasks in real-time until the tasks are being completed (Hertzfeld, 2018).

Figure 11: Likelihood to choose Hotel with Tech-Enabled lobby

(Short, 2015)

Most of the hotels tend to develop lobby technology and at the moment few hotels have already developed lobby technology such as touchscreens which may provide the guests with information such as weather, local attractions to visit and certain news. The process is basically similar to the smartphones to swipe, tap and drag items on the touchscreen. As per a survey above, 63 percent of 339 respondents preferred to have touchscreen kiosks in the lobby of the hotel. With many

technological developments taking place, demand has increased and has given a modern look to the hotel lobbies and its operation.

According to Bob Gobind, president and CEO of Apex Hotel Source, many advanced and developed hotels are looking at installing digital signage in the lobbies that allows to share information with the guests more rapidly. According to Gobind, in order to install such elements a hotel needs to a power source and an internet connection. Apex Hotel Source operates in the process of providing creative ideas to hotel operations that attracts the eye of the guests. Once the basic input as the above is provided, Apex deals with the hotel to understand the content that needs to be displayed in the hotel display screens. As per Apex, currently Best Western Hotels is adopting this method which is quite attracting. Also, the Renaissance New York Midtown in Manhattan, is currently providing a high-tech experience to the guests as walked through the doors. The purpose of this development in this site was to bring some interactive video elements in terms of information to the guests and to entertain the guests as they are waiting to go off to the main lobby as mentioned by Micheal Pandolfi, the principal and design director at Jeffrey Beers International. A distinctive similarity was made on Marriot's International Renaissance brand, a storyline was created for all its hotels to bring out the long history of the Marriot brand. Understanding that the hotel is situation in the city's fashion district New York City, a graphic pattern of fabrics and stitching were projected on to the walls to provide the guests with the immediate sense of the place. And to alert the guests on what is taking place around the location, a digital display was set up in the entrance that provided information on nearby events, restaurants, shopping locations and shows if any (Fox, 2020).

Another important factor that can be developed is that most concierge desks include a personal computer at the lobby. In order to have a much more personal interaction with the guest, it will be a vital factor for the concierge to walk towards the guest with a portable tablet and assist the guest. When referring to Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Hotel Galadari and Kingsbury hotel, maintain a concierge desk and guides the guests towards the desk to provide information. Therefore, a personalized assistance could be provided if the concierge walked towards the guest in order to provide the necessary information.

According to Gene Hopper, strategy and alignment manager at Monscierge which is a leading software company in Oklahoma, has mentioned that at least for the millennials the absence of lobby technology could become a drawback for major hotels. Because as mentioned previously about the task that lies upon the concierge of walking towards the guest for assistant, it would be a vital factor to introduce Kiosks for guests in order to find all the necessary information preferred which could save time in case even the concierge in no present at the desk (Short, 2015)

Figure 12: Likelihood to choose a hotel with facial recognition (Short, 2015)

As per the above when a research was conducted in respect to the preference of having facial recognition option in a hotel out of 339 respondents 41 percent of the respondents are likely to opt to facial recognition facility in a hotel chosen. The facial recognition technology, is mostly a biometric software in which the data is linked with cameras and can identify individuals from afar with respect to the image of the face. So in terms of a hotel when there are repeat arrivals, guests do not specifically have to reserve a room, but if guests have repeat arrivals for a lunch or dinner, the facial recognition option can recognize the guest and a more personalized treatment can be offered to the guest.

Facial recognition allows to automate certain verifications or authorizations along the journey of the customer and simultaneously improve the customer experience. Additionally, the ability to identify large groups of guests and certain specific people can be really advantageous, which would far greater and better than security systems and security personals. With respect to a payment, if the hotel possesses kiosks in the lobby area, if the guest has to make a payment rather than entering a one-time password (OTP) guests have the chance to witness the payment

confirmed via facial recognition and confirm the payment made. In this manner interaction with a hotel employee is not necessary. These Kiosks will be very supportive even for a restaurant where the customers could pay for their meal on their way out. Currently facial recognition is being practiced in two differently located Marriot hotels in China. Here, the guests have the opportunity to bypass the traditional check-in desk and head towards a kiosk. Afterwards the facial recognition technology scans the guest's face, identifies and provides the key card in within a short time period (Revfine, 2021). According to Allen Ganz, digital media solutions for NEC, mentioned that cameras could identify the guests faces as entered in to the hotel, which could alert the general manager and greet the customers in person and by the name. VIP guests could also be recognized via the technology and special access could be granted to special clubs, other areas of the property, or even the bartender could be notified to serve the guest's favorite cocktail as the guest walks in (Short, 2015).

Figure 13: Preference towards face recognition technology by age (Short, 2015)

According to the above graph, the age group 18-24 prefers the new technology being introduced on the hotels. This clearly defines the future of technology in a hotel is a key important development that has to be made. With smartphones being introduced with facial recognition technology, it has proven that this development is a much further development that greatly assists the hotel employees to perform duties with less efforts and hassle-free for the guests.

Figure 14: Top benefits hotel technology can deliver

(Short, 2015)

According to a recent worldwide survey which was conducted by CNN International, depicted that tourists firstly prefer the safety and security factor over price as the factors that influence travel decisions. As per the above pie chart most respondents chose that costs need to be reduced. In order for this, technology will assist in reducing the operational costs of the hotel. As mentioned prior, the smart hotel concepts will assist in using controls to switch off unnecessary lights and air conditioning when there aren't any guests in the rooms that can reduce energy costs. On the other hand many hotels display discounts or free offers on the lobby touchscreens, and having the assistance of using the guest's smartphone or the smartwatch to open the guest rooms can reduce the wastage of energy and the cost of printing physical key cards. Accordingly, the bottom line is that technology could indirectly lower the costs on the guests and could be passed on as lower rates or special rates when making a room reservation (Short, 2015).

2.12 Hotel Information System (HIS)

Hotel Information systems are considered as a collection of information system that merely supports a series of procedures in order to collect, analyze and also store data for present purposes and future use for the hotel business which also includes different computerized systems such as front office systems, back-office systems and lastly the interface systems. By using information technology, HIS has made it possible to efficiently handle and also to distribute necessary information for hotel management and currently this has gained a massive reputation in the industry. However, launching a HIS does not mean that there is a constant continuation of success

but hotel owners continuously seek to find strategies to maximize the efficiency of the system use (Kasavana, 1978).

Technology is formation of information systems. Therefore, HIS is a critical aspect that has to be developed in order to develop a hotel technologically. On the other hand, evaluation of HIS is that developing HIS by adapting information systems, which requires a high initial investment, but low productivity of these systems can cause the in results where the system development to fail and the waste of resources. However when taking the Sri Lanka based five star hotels in Colombo, as these hotels have to develop technology from initial stages, understanding the Information system Success Model that was proposed by DeLone and McLean (1992) from the initial stages will be a critical aspect for any developing five star accommodation. This model was introduced in order to measure the system success. According to this model there are six major components of the information system success which includes, system quality, quality of the information, satisfaction of the user, impact towards the individual and organizational impact. Few changes have been made to the model in 2003 causing the updates D&M IS Model which now comprises of three major quality factors such as system quality, information quality and the service quality and these components assist to influence the intention to use or arise of user satisfaction. System quality usually focusses on the technology and the process aspects and the system characteristics that would lead to efficiency and the reduction of the cost.

The initial stage for the hotels in this research is to develop the necessary Information Systems prior to expanding to further levels. With respect to the hospitality industry, trust has been identified as a critical determinant of the IS usage in the content of online booking purpose. Currently the hotels relating to this research has developed a website for the respective hotels.

Figure 15: IS Success Model

(Petter, 2007)

As per the IS success model technology is developed via the system quality. The PMS system that most hotels adopt at the moment is the best example. When reserving an accommodation, the PMS records all the guest's details. If the same guest arrives to stay in the hotel in another two – three years the same guest details will be available in the PMS system making it convenient to the hotel staff. For example, if the guest had been celebrating their birthday during their previous stay, the records can be found in the PMS system on to what was offered on that day complementary from the hotel if there are new employees in the seat. The system quality and Information quality plays a vital role in this process. The information found in the system is valid throughout the PMS system unless the hotel switches to a new system. Now these hotels understanding the system validity with the information quality that is reliable throughout provides an exceptional service to their guests. The service quality plays a vital role that all customer details are recorded whenever to be utilized. If comments have to be added, if special requests have to added and all these information Is autosaved. The system is user friendly if known how to proceed. With respect to the conveniency of using the system the hotel staff have found it quite stress-free to perform their duties on time. Because each department has the authority to make changes in the remarks section as they wish. So that the other departments are also on the alert for any special requests the guest has requested.

2.13 Hotel Personalized Service

Research on smart technologies in the hospitality sector mostly includes behavioral studies. Researchers have proposed and has examined the factors that affect the hotel guests to use technological devices. According to Kim et al. (2014) have investigated that the concept of customer readiness and its effect on the likelihood of using self-service technologies in a public setting which is a hotel of their choice. However, many studies put forward that attitudes that business stakeholders have towards the smart hotel technologies, the owners of these hotels have different perspectives on adapting smart technology, employees getting adapted to use technology for their duties and also travelers' perceptions on experiencing smart hotel technology is vital.

Apart from understanding perceptions of the guests, another important business strategy with the development of Experience enhancement smart technologies would be to collect the data of the service users personal behavioral data with the intention of further developing and to improving personalized data. Personalization is an important component in the service industry. It is considered as an approach to deliver services that would meet customer expectations, thereby providing customized services in order to match the customers preferences and the needs. It is much necessary to collect the guest's behavioral information which could be used to construct a comprehensive database which could be useful for the analysis of customer choices and that in return would lead to meet customer expectation successfully. On the other hand, guests tend to inherit the preferences which is easily revealed in the service consumption process and it can be much essential for the hospitality businesses to achieve this specific component of personalization in their plan of service design. However in the near future there will be an increase and a variety of Experience Enhanced smart technologies that will be further improved that can be a strategic development of personalized services in the hotel sector (Han, 2021)

Prior to developing technologies which provide a personalized service it is important to understand the need for hotel employees to focus on personalization before engaging in this task via technology. This is a key factor which merely lacks in the hotels chosen for this research. The purpose of personalization is to cultivate the loyal customers and to gain the competitive

advantage over the other hotels. The utmost importance is that prior to introducing technological improvements in a hotel, it is important to train the employees to treat customers with the individual attention component that is essential. Because many hotels and hotel employees would have intentions to introducing technology as to assist on the duties performed and with intentions of relaxing on the job which the technology impresses the guest. This strategy is not very acceptable as employees are however the prime key in building the interpersonal relationship with the guest which technology cannot perform. The employees' interpersonal skills with the technology functions can form a vital improvement in the service quality in all departments of the hotel leaving the guests startled and satisfied. Hotels should not expect repeat arrivals from their guests. Whether the guest arrives at the hotel again or not it is important that by providing the personalized service alongside by impressing the guest with the hotel's technology can leave the guest satisfied causing the result of word of mouth.

It is also important to create a positive image on the hotel. A proper individualized service can definitely make the guest feel truly cared by the hotel also come to realization of the hotel values and the interests of the hotel which can lead to a thoughtful and friendly hotel image that can be deeply rooted in the minds and hearts of the public. With personalization hotels can then improve the economic interest of the hotel. If the hotel personalized their service in order to meet the personalized needs of the consumers there is a high percentage of chance to improve the customer satisfaction and loyalty which would lead to enhancing the awareness of the hotel and this in return would attract loyal customers, repeat customers and would create a positive reputation on the hotel and bring in more profits and occupy a large share in the market (Zhang, 2018). The purpose of bringing in personalization in this research is that apart from developing hotel processes via technology is very important and this even leads to the reduction of the workload of the employees. But many employees may tend to back away and technology take over while the employees will not provide their fullest efforts to their job. So, with personalization component from the employees and when the technology both combines this further improves the customer satisfaction that a hotel looks forward for. With the technological development in hotels, the next generation hotel guests tend to demand frictionless stays, whereas the needs and the requirements will be usually anticipated and will be taken care of by the hotels. Therefore, as a hotel owner or even the staff it will be quite important to fine-tune the digital strategies that

provide customer satisfaction that is more customized or personalized towards the customers. The future of personalization is linked with the hotel technologies that grabs the attention of future tourists are their interest in the hotel grow further.

- It is proposed that Augmented Reality (AR) Virtual Reality (VR), and other wearables will let the users to change into a digital environment with the assistance of images, noise and other physical sensations that most guests prefer. Understanding that AR and VR have been invented long time back but has also gained the attention and the mainstream consumer technology which would enable many hotels to experiment with the digital experiences that these products provide. As proposed by Adobe Digital Insights, “*At least eight of the largest hotels have tested some kind of VR experience*” the purpose of AR and VR towards a hotel is that it could provide virtual tours around the hotel and it could also show the hotels rooms whereas the guest can choose the hotel room they prefer staying at. When AR is taken into place, this could help the hotels to introduce a more effective and more immersive elements into the hotel whereas wall maps which can be viewed from a smartphone can be used a good tourist information tool and need not to be access hotel staff for information when doubts arise from time to time.
- One of the trending technological developments at the moment is AI chatbots. Most sites now adapt this technology which would assist the guest all 365 days. And language options are available where the guest can type in any language preferred and familiar with. AI chatbots are virtual assistants which assist to create a customized experience towards the guest. From the point of handling the guest via the chats there is a major possibility of a potential booking process. This process is quite convenient from the employee’s point of view as the employee could stay connected to the guest if the guest prefers to chat in a weeks’ time as preferred. Leverage data on the guest can also be compiled about the guests who plan to stay at the hotel. Getting in touch on a personal level via a chat could assist the hotel to understand the likes and dislikes of their guests and provide a memorable experience and a more authentic and a personalized manner. For example, with the information that is collected the hotel can provide family discounts, even provide facilities on business trip and suggest or recommend special dishes in the hotel according to the nationality of the guest. Taking the local picture into context, the hotels based on this research all include a respective website for their guest convenience. However, it could be further developed with AI chatbots to interact with their guest on a personal level to professionally to serve the guest better.

- Cloud based management is also a critical factor as gathering the data of the guest and utilizing them in the correct manner has been a major goal for any hospitality business over the recent years. With the assistance of cloud-based management, where the data could be mined, data can be recorded, data can be interpreted and can be used for sending personalized notifications and offers by understanding the preferences of the guests and the behavior which is essential for enhancing the overall experience of the guest. On the other hand, cloud technology can be much helpful in centralizing the property organization with the use of one platform, and it applies that every aspect of the hotel business can be managed from this process from the point of room reservations. And adopting cloud is a solution for the hotel being more eco-friendly and will be a major advantage for the hotel to provide their guests with an environmental-friendly guest experience. Currently the hotels used in the research practice cloud management to a certain extent however it can be further developed with optioned such as syncing the guest's email address photo once the email has been inputted into the system so that upon arrival the guest could be easily recognized.
- Another option of personalized development would be the Beacon technology which works through Bluetooth option and it is considered to be very effective when sending push notifications or even enabling certain functions when a person enters a specific location. This is one of the outstanding features which is quite helpful to the hotel which allows the guests to spend more time with the hotel just by using in-house facilities with the assistance of personalized communication. Some of the useful features of the Beacon technology is that it notifies the guests of special or complimentary spa services and even the happy hours in the bar (Trivago Business blog, 2019).

As per a research conducted by Dr Chen (2019), a four star rated hotel in Switzerland, Hotel Lugano Dante has developed the hotel's website to an new level as to when the guest reserves a room via the website, a portal called "My Page" drops down for the guests to customize their stay. This portal offers the guest over 150 options which varies from baby cribs, disability access, changing tables, baby bathtubs to even the drinks that has to be included in the mini bar. A main purpose of hoteliers is that to understand the issues of the guest and provide solutions. With respect to the above case, guest may sometimes forget until their arrival at the hotel. But as the portal is accessed at the time of reservation useful objects such as portable chargers, adapters,

presentation clickers and even yoga mats could be requested. Once reserved the hotel will send out a confirmation with all the requested utilities via email for the convenience of the guest (Chen, 2019). This is one of the best successful operations for the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels as the chain hotels in Sri Lanka have not opted this feature yet. International tourists are much concerned on the things being brought and this feature will assist them immensely to have the option of borrowing the hotel equipment' if forgotten.

Another important strategy is that hotel owners need to communicate the importance of collecting guest preference data and train the employees to collect this information. However, this cannot be done by contacting the guest and asking the guest preferences. This plan could be conducted by the employees themselves where the employees could record the items consumed by the guests in the mini bar, the last TV channel watched, the room temperature and the room service orders which was ordered and the employees could understand the guest preferences and the behaviors. As per Dr Chen (2019) most international hotels practice this strategy where a guest comment on this strategy was as below:

“When I checked into a hotel recently, I was pleasantly surprised to find a welcome fruit basket containing dragon fruit which I ate immediately, while leaving the other items untouched. The next day, I found another dragon fruit in the fruit basket, together with two new fruits. The hotel had noticed my consumption pattern and provided more choices to learn my preferences. Bravo!”

(Chen, 2019)

However, an important factor to be considered is that until date the perfect strategy to collect and store customer data is not found. Because once the customization and the data collection are in the process, hotel owners need to evaluate the performance of the employees with respect to the data collection and sharing of necessary information. It is agreed that there is high staff turnover in the hospitality industry and hotels cannot solely rely on the individual employees by memorizing the customer preference data and therefore must rely on technology as a substitute to memorize and act as the hotel's extended memory. But considering some destinations there can be very few repeat customers and this may become a major question or doubt with respect to

the investment of data collection is a successful method. Understanding the lower data storage costs which could in return improve the employees efficiency in the process of collecting data, with time there is a chance that these costs would reduce. However, even though there is low percentage of repeat customers for a hotel, the hotel could still benefit from the process of data analysis and could offer more personal, tailored services that is based on customer data towards new guests who stays at the hotel (Chen, 2019)

2.14 Technology Acceptance Model

According to many studies, have accepted and adopted the Technology acceptance model (TAM) which explains the acceptance of various hospitality and tourism technologies by the tourists. According to Lai (2015), has summarized the acceptance of smart technologies by the guests with the guidance of studies that were published from 2005 to 2012 and has analyzed the TAM extended models which were derived from the online booking systems, tourism websites, hotel websites and even Facebook. It is important to understand that ever since 2012 many studies on smart technologies in acceptance to the hospitality environment from a guest's perspective was conducted with the aid of radio-frequency identification that was adopted in situations such as purchase of airline tickets, social media, self-service kiosks in the hotel and hotel access control systems. In a hospitality environment, employees are usually under more pressure whom has to undergo more pressure in order to accept modern technology with the purpose of achieving the organizational goals. However, it is the choice of the guest whether to use or not use these technologies. This is a sound belief which implies that the tourists using smart technologies is implied according to the beliefs. Therefore, the TAM model is considered to be quite importance when investigating if smart technology adoption behavior of the guests and the guest's perspective on it.

Figure 16: Technology Acceptance Model

(Jaradat, 2014)

The TAM model is considered as an important model which was also developed to test the employee's prime intention to use smart technologies for efficient and productive services. However, this model proved to be very powerful which has represented the antecedents on the intention to adopt modern technologies. The TAM model is adapting the framework from the theory of reasoned action (TRA) for the acceptance of information systems. This theory puts forward the ones actual use of technology which can be directly or indirectly be influenced by an individual's behavioral intentions, attitudes and the perceived use of the technology. An individual's behavior is usually affected by ones behavioral intention and is shaped by another individual's attitude. Studies on the technology acceptance is commonly focusing on the relationships which is among the beliefs, behavioral intentions, action and the attitude. Perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU), intention to use (ITU) and the attitude towards use are considered as the four theoretical components of the TAM. Perceived usefulness is usually referred to the technology users and the beliefs possessed that new technology will improve the performance of a certain task which is conducted. Perceived ease of use refers to the convenience and easiness of utilizing modern technology. Attitude towards use is considered as the emotional and judgmental thoughts developed towards the use of technology. With the last component of intension to use it creates a favorable attitude and interest towards new technology.

The technology acceptance model is considered as one of the most widely accepted models which is used to study the consumer behavior of the individuals in the hotel industry. Over the past few years, the technology acceptance model was used and is considered as a theoretical foundation which is used to examine the new technology developed in the industry and to identify how effective adopting new technology would be indifferent social disciplines with the assistance of different empirical data. As per the Technology acceptance model, and considering a hotel

operation for example, the employees attentive and dedicated work results in the output quality, and this in return would create a positive image on the hotel. These factors arise to the state where hotel owners further develop ideas on increasing performance of the hotel. This is where the with process developments, technology developments will directly be developed (Hou, 2020). Technology adoption in hotels is considered as a complex process at the beginning. This has shown put forward some unique characteristics thus proposing some distinctive approaches when dealing with examining the technology adoption behavior and for example such as organization technology climate and other technology characteristics (Wang, 2007). According to Lam (2007) mentioned that many hotels have widely adopted technologies with the purpose of improving the operation efficiency, improve the service quality and reduce costs. Therefore, rather than introducing technology into a hotel without further experiments, few studies were conducted in order to understand the relationship between the external variables and the Technology acceptance model framework with the purpose of explaining the accepted behavior of the technology in the tourism and hotel industry (Lam et al., 2007).

To understand the usefulness of this model, a hotel's front office system will be used as an example to understand how the TAM will play a vital role. It is important that hotel employees use this system regardless of their personal interests. Because when considering the employees working in a hotel, an individual may find tech-savvy, modern thinking and employees who follow old methods on performing the tasks and duties. As mentioned prior in this research, Hotel information system (HIS) is considered as the most vital and critical tool of technology that is important in the hotel business and mainly assists the front office department in the department operations. The front office system operates every day and this is considered as the system which is used by the front office staff to get in touch with the guests via assessing all the details from the personal details to the details of the stay.

With respect to the TAM and the perceived ease of use and the perceived usefulness, there are few external variables that come into play such as personal features that include innovativeness, IT self-efficacy and the past adoption behavior. System features such as the functionality and the design. There are organizational features which include the support of the top management and appropriate training that has major impacts on the behavior of an individual. According to Davis

et.al (1989) mentioned that these external features of the model can have an effect on the beliefs of the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Many studies were being conducted to prove that external variables such as the personal features, system features and organizational were considered as the determining factors. As the main aim is to understand the front office system which has to be approached from a viewpoint of mandatory acceptance, the perceived value of the front office system is usually playing a very critical role in the positive attitude towards the usage. The main two areas which will be examined will be the information system quality and the perceived value of external variables of the TAM. Now in relation to the front office system and the information system quality, the quality of the information system has to be examined in three main dimensions of information, system and the service quality (Eldon, 1997). When the information quality is being measured, it is a must that it has to be adjusted towards the accuracy, relevancy and the efficiency of the exact product of the information system. Understanding that the information quality is very subjective from a perspective of the user, it is also considered as a part of the satisfaction of the user. The quality of the system does have a significance on the operational efficiency with respect to the function of an information system. In many of the studies which were conducted in previous years the measure of the system quality had a significant impact on the system's technical characteristics that includes dependability, response, solubility (DeLone & McLean, 1992). On the other hand with the correlation there is between the system quality and the presence of the possible errors in the system, the consistency of the user interaction, documentation, response rate, program code quality and the maintenance was included. And also when the service quality can make a huge impact on the overall quality of the information service quality, it is considered to be equivalent to the staff of the department of the information system (Baroudi et al, 1988). As per the studies which were conducted by Palmer (2002), has developed an instrument with the purpose of measuring the quality of the online properties. As mentioned prior in this research with respect to the front office systems, SERVQUAL plays a vital role which plays a vital role in the service quality, and have subsequently emphasized the importance of SERVQUAL very important to set the foundation of the service quality. This aspect was put forward because with respect to websites, because there is definitely not going to have any face-to-face interaction the guest. Another example is where when considering internet shopping, it offers many information with respect to placing orders and delivery. So from the cloth shop's point of view the information is necessary to provide

exceptional service towards the customer which can be done online. As per a research conducted, the users of the front office system was only associated with the duties where proper training, attitude, supply of Information technology and the problem solving techniques by the use of electronic data processing (EDP) which will be very useful for front office users which can be critical.

When referring to the perceived value, perceptions play a vital role. Depending on the guests giving and receiving, there is an overall assessment of a product use shows that there is a valid trade-off between the acts of giving and receiving. However if the service cost is expensive, how good the quality is, there is a chance that the service will be less worth the cost. At a point of such the opinion of the hotel employees will be very critical. When considering studies that involves marketing, either the consumer products or there will be reasons for the purchase are considered as important factors and these may have been found to be very important in the perceived value of the consumers. So in the point of Marketing and quality, the perceived value are considered very much proportional to the cost such as the price and time. Profit is critical with the quality (Woodruff, 1996). As of now there is no considerate study conducted on the model which focusses on user satisfaction in the form of information system where the concept of the costs to the hotel employees and is defined specifically or classified by assessment. But it is also important to understand that the concepts of net benefits, usefulness and the user satisfaction is thoroughly evaluated. From the hotel employees view this is considered as a net benefit (Seddon, 1997). The net benefit is considered as a comprehensive measure of the profits which is expected of the past as well as the future taking from the expected expense., which relates to the definition that is found in Marketing and the quality-based literature and can also concur with the personal effectiveness as for successful factor for the benefit of the information system. Net benefit is considered as a practical application when using information technology. When establishing information system, studying the usage, system usage and all the other resources that are useful including time can be regarded as an expense. In order to measure the benefit, it is important to decide it can be worthwhile for the hotel users. So therefore, it is very important to understand that when relating the TAM model to the front office system, the employees need to understand the quality of the system by proper training, with adequate training

this would rise to the perceived use of use and eventually leave the attainment of perceived usefulness.

Institutional Theory

As put forward in many occasions in the research, hospitality businesses continue to be impacted by the new technology and this include recent changes which have been made towards the big data and the artificial intelligence. And this resulting in making technology adoption systems to be persistent reality faced by the hotel businesses (Yuan et al, 2019). However, the technology adoption that is mostly existing in the market right now considers the decision-making processes of individual decision makers and the organizations which is in isolation from a pure good point of view. Extant hospitality literature focusses on technology acceptance as a complete voluntary process while in reality hotels would be exposed to institutional pressures and could be subject to losing the legitimacy that is held by the hotel in the government bodies, associations in the industry or even the collaborators if certain technologies are not adapted into the business. According to Pourfakhimi et al (2019), argues that the technology adoption in the hospitality business is merely characterized by shallow theorization and has an overreliance on the technology acceptance model (TAM). Identifying the technology usage from an institutional point of view can provide contextualized understanding of the processes and the different perceptions that drive the decision making related to technology in the hospitality industry (Pourfakhimi et.al, 2019).

The institutional theory is an important theory that explain the technology adoption to any industry in the world. The institutional theory attempts to prove that the adoption decisions related to technology with respect to social values and observing the organizations that are related to the social system and is guided by internal and external institutional logics. With respect to the institutional theory assumptions, according to Oliveira and Martins (2010) has argued that institutional perspectives and particularly pertinent in order to understand the firm-level technology adoption. In recent research that is conducted by Sun et al. (2018) has identified a number of institutional factors which drives the organizational adoption of the big data technologies. This kind of a institutional perspective is quite critical in the hospitality industry,

and it is a phenomenon that expands to several industries with many complex structures and much heavy regulations. According to Gyau and Stringer (2011), it suggests that the institutional theory is considered as a tool that should receive the attention for the potential in order to foster a greater understanding of the adoption in technology in the hospitality industry. Not many studies have been conducted with reference to the Institutional theory and the hospitality industry. According to DiMaggio and Powell (1983), has put forward three different kinds of institutional pressures that will affect the technology adoption which includes three factors such as coercive, normative and mimetic. The institutional theory puts forward that organizations in the same institutional environment and it would be more similar due to similar pressures being experienced.

In order to further understand the type of technology that is much relevant to a hotel the decision-making process is considered quite vital. Even the five-star accommodations possess different types such as structure and atmosphere. However, this research without being aligned with the hotel's physical appearance it will be quite critical for hotel owners to consider the decision-making process on identifying the pros and cons of a technology development and a change made on the hotel to be successful or not.

Figure 17 : Decision making process (compiled by Author)

It is a main duty of guests when it comes to choosing a hotel of their choice for vacationing. Certain factors such as location, amenities, price are taken into consideration before reserving an accommodation. Likewise hotel owners also have to take some important decisions prior to developing and introducing technology to the hotel. According to the University of Dartmouth, Decision making is considered as process which is used in making choices with the assistance of gathering information, and then by assessing alternative solutions (Umass Dartmouth, 2021). Considering the below example is related to the Sri Lanka based five-star accommodations in Colombo. With respect to the decision-making process the first step of identifying the problem is where the hotel managers need to understand at pre-level the type of technology that is suitable for these types of hotels. However, without the knowledge on identifying which technology is suitable the first upmost area that could be developed is developing the cloud technology and the hotel website. As for research mentioned above the first obstacle for a hotel as such is to develop the internal system prior the room and lobby technology developments. An analysis of this issue will take place next where the hotel owners would find solutions of developing the Website, in order to develop this system of reserving accommodations for guests' ideas will be seeked from the employees or the E-marketing manager. Various alternatives will be provided such as making the website more creative or provide language options which none of the sites have at the moment. And as mentioned prior in the research the AI chatbot is a very interesting idea which can be adopted in this process. And this itself could be considered as an alternative. The alternative of the AI chatbot could be evaluated by understanding the effectiveness of this strategy by using the AI chatbot of another industry's organization as it has not been introduced in any hotel in Sri Lanka. Also, research could be conducted with the aid of guests checking in to understand the opinion processed towards the AI chatbots where sometimes guests themselves have difficulty to gets doubts cleared via a telephone call with the hotel if the employees are busy

with the duties and tasks. With a positive impact on the choice of AI chatbot in the website of the hotel it will be selected and be implemented on a trial to see the effectiveness. As time moves forward the hotel staff could record each employees personal details even prior to the reservation which will be made via a telephone conversation or an email.

2.15 Environment Friendly practices in hotels

Some of on the ongoing issues and negative impacts caused towards the environment by the hospitality sector is the increased demand of energy supply and the increased burden on solid waste management (Kasim, 2006). With respect to these effects there are certain uncertainties that exist with respect to the long-term implications of such negative impacts on the environment and in respect to those which would cause a global climate change. This is where the “greening” factor plays a vital role and the creation of the carbon neutral accommodation is important in almost all the hotels. Hotels are considered as one of the substantial components in the hospitality sector. Hotel operations are being characterized by with respect to a major number of activities that as a whole exert a significant impact on the global resources available (Kirk, 1995). Certain Hotel operations emit greenhouse gases which are being emitted to the into the air in the form of carbon dioxide and chlorofluorocarbons. Also research has shown that hotels exert the most negative influence towards the environment together with commercial buildings. With an approximate value, an average hotel will exert between 160kg and 200kg of carbon dioxide per square meter of a room area per annum and also another impact would be the water consumption per guest per night would be roughly between 170 to 450 litres in a five-star accommodation. A hotel also produces 1 kilogram of waste per guest per night on average (Han et al, 2010).

On the other hand, many guests have growing concerns as to fact that hotels need to be more eco-friendly. This is because the guests are experiencing an increased awareness of the excessive environment damage and the excessive consumption of goods, energy and water. With the negative impacts that hotels exert on the environment, this would create a major pressure on the government and will cause the eco-friendlier enterprises to improve the green consumptions in hotels. With many issues that is arising due to the environment damage, it promotes the hotels to demonstrate a responsible behavior to become more eco-friendly hotels by practicing the possible

ecologically sound practices such as saving water, energy and reducing the solid waste (Manaktola et al, 2007).

2.15.1 Greening trends in hotels

With respect to the hotel sector, the areas towards the concern mainly relies on how the environment is being polluted through the liquid and the solid waste, the energy consumption being high and the increase release of greenhouse gases towards the atmosphere. Some practices such as recycling of waste, management of waste, the supply of clean air, conservation of energy and water, environment health, educating the staff on the negative impacts on pollution are considered some of the ways in which hotels try to mitigate the negative impacts caused on the environment (Mensah, 2006). Some good practices are being undertaken in the hotel sector in this regard. By practicing such methods, it will help the sector to be more sustainable and also environmentally friendly. According to recent studies, 85% of the tourists consider themselves to be environment conscious which is referred as “green consumers”. Some hotel practices the principles of sustainable development at the moment to grab the attention of their guests. Major steps are being taken by hotels who has also conducted audits related to the environment and then access the environment costs of their activities with respect to the energy consumption, waste, transport, purchasing, health and the local environment (Page, 2009). Environment sustainability is considered as one of the major aspects to be considered with respect to the general sustainability to be practiced. The demands that arise from the government will require the hotels to go green. With reference to the below table, hotels can adapt themselves to becoming more eco-friendly concerning different aspects of improvement.

Green practice	Green house initiative
Proper sustainable management of water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The fixtures used to conserve water to be low -flow in the hotel. • Detecting the leaks and drips in the guests’ rooms and repairing them via diverter valves. • Another good option to follow would be to place a glass jar in the toilet tank which would reduce the amount of water that is used per flush.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rainwater harvesting is also considered as an important strategy where hotels can keep their operations to be waste free for example of using that water flush toilets. • Concerns on the careless use of water resources have led to the towel and linen reuse efforts which was adopted by many of the world's hotels.
Energy conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most green hotels at the moment implement measures to reducing the energy consumption through the operation as much as possible during the daylight. • The adoption of energy saving light bulbs such as compact efflorescent bubs are considered to be energy star-efficient heating, air conditioning and ventilation. • By investing in new renewable energies will cause a difference to the carbon footprint of the hotel. Examples may relate to the renewable energy such as sunlight and wind power. • Occupancy sensors can be used in rooms to sense when and when not the room is occupied that automatically switches off the lights.
Solid waste management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling is considered as one strategy in which hotels can participate in waste management programmes. • Composting at the establishment can be encouraged or the municipal refuse collection can be merged to refuse at the composting depot that assist in processing organic waste for the use in the gardens of the community.
Air Quality management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air filters could be used in the hotels • Hotel vehicles could be shifted to hybrid or electric vehicles

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The passing of decrees which is required in restaurants will assist to instill ventilation and also create smoking sections causing a mitigatory effect.
Environmental purchasing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It will be important for guest rooms, kitchens and the administrative offices to purchase re-cycled eco-friendly packaging such as take out boxes, paper bags, paper straws and items which are considered as recycling and biodegradable packaging. • It is also important that hotels purchase locally-produced food items which are considered as fresh and very indigenous. This would reduce the economic leakages in the hotels and directly this supports the local economy as well. • Green purchasing for hotels is also considered vital as buying biodegradable products such as eating utensils, solutions for cleaning, soaps and shampoos and other necessary items for guest rooms.
Community awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education on the environment is an important factor within the hotel staff and the community as well. • Green information can also be made. This could be done and be made available to the society with sources such as television and radio programmes, newspaper articles, magazine articles and leaflets found in libraries. • Conservations training could be conducted which involves the participation of the local community as well as the hotel employees in activities such as cleaning a beach or a park to financially support an association with the purpose of protecting the environment.
Managing permits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permits could be obtained for certain buildings such as green buildings, which could be considered as an improvement in the health and the productivity of the people who are working for them.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Another important factor would be the legislation factor. When the green management was firstly introduced, the main reasons for a hotel to go green was to focus on complying with the government regulations and then saving money by saving the energy and waste. • There may be laws and different regulations which would include the recycling requirements, codes for buildings, and different incentives such as the tax exemptions and different credits for fixing the renewable sources of energy.
--	--

Table 4:- Greening trends in hotels

(Kruger, 2016)

The leading international chain hotels in the world are currently emphasizing efforts on increasing their sustainability with respect to a strategic plan. An example would be the Intercontinental hotel group has put forward the following report where the hotels policies and the standards are set out to achieve the social and ethical issues. And the hotel focusses on developing towards achieving the and ensuring the growth of the business with aligning towards the standards set by the UN Sustainable development goals. According to Wyndham destinations, a percentage of 96 percent of the Wyndham resorts adopt a combination of many proven conservation strategies that is considered as energy sufficient lighting, motion sensors and default settings for the in-unit HVAC systems in order to achieve on ongoing reductions in the harmful emissions and energy. Marriot hotel chain too focusses on the sustainability strategy which supports the business growth and then reaches towards the environment that assist the hotel to protect the environment. Many researches has shown how sustainability is a critical area for improvement and has addressed different point of views. According to Kapera (2018) has discussed the implementations taking place at the moment where barriers and capabilities are set to develop a sustainable environment in every hotel in Poland. As this is cost saving and being a very efficient strategy, the government of Poland has taken a vital step towards the new implementation. According to Han et al (2018) has made a test towards the understanding the perceptions which is processed by the hotels guests on hotel practices in terms of water conservation and waste reduction management which would indirectly increase the hedonic and the utilitarian values which can be examined as with the influence of such relationships on the

participation of the guest in green practices and loyalty intentions. According to Gil-Saura et al (2011) has mentioned the that by introducing the information and the communication technologies can reduce the energy demands. And as per Raymond et al (2019) had explored the impact that is caused by the sustainable development practices in the hospitality industry with respect to the customer satisfaction in many hotels in the province of Quebec in Canada. However, the results have shown that many guests have preferred the concept of going green and adapting to an eco-friendly environment. According to Alipour(2019) have investigated the perspectives of the employees with respect to the sustainable practices in many five star accommodations on an island in the Mediterranean with the assistance of the Global Sustainable Tourism Council hotel criteria indicators, and it included the indicators of the sustainable development for tourism destinations and this included the European Union's sustainability Framework that is assigned for the Hotels in Mediterranean with respect to the three main pillars of the sustainable development as social, environmental and economic. Some studies have shown the positive relationship between the sustainability in the environment and the tourist experience. According to Lee (2017) research has shown that the green image of a hotel promotes ad guests are more likely to revisit, and also make positive recommendations and are also willing to pay much higher prices. According to Moliner et al (2019) have demonstrated that environmental sustainability has a positive and a direct influence on the experience of the customer with respect to the accommodation. Understanding that the green practices on the hospitality industry is being impacted by three reasons as for the financial benefits, customer requirements and the stakeholder relations. Adopting an eco-friendly environment can benefit hotels to a grand-scale because it is one of the emerging trends in the world. When tourists travel with the purpose of doing eco-tourism, they tend to expect their accommodation to be eco-friendly as well. This practice is very important for all hotels and technology can be well applied with the eco-friendly aspect. As discussed, prior the technology developments such as motion sensors is considered as one of the major improvements that has been made with respect to hotels however an improvement which can be made on the hotels in Sri Lanka. There are studies which has depicted as to how the green house practices will contribute in the process of reducing the operational costs on s hotel are thereby increasing the profits of the hotel by enhancing the satisfaction of the guest and the loyalty, the environment being sustained and then gaining a competitive advantage.

As per Ada Derana (2021), the very first eco-friendly luxury boutiques resort is set to be introduced by Waters Edge hotel in Colombo and it is planned to be a 48-room project. It is said to have a unique design with also some smart features and mainly an eco-friendly sustainable structure, it targets for the local and international tourists setting a hallmark for luxury city hotels around the world. This new resort is set to mark a new scale with modern smart guest experiences and more technological advents such as IoT powered rooms, checking in to be digital and also it will include real time air monitoring which will increase the guest satisfaction alongside with safety and wellness (Ada Derana, 2021). According to Black (2020), there are many eco-friendly hotels in Sri Lanka which are situated outside of Colombo. However, the urbanization of Colombo has caused many city hotels to not develop the strategy of sustainability. As per interviews which were conducted by Wickramasinghe (2016) has identified the current common practices that Colombo hotels are undergoing with the adoption of sustainability. With respect to the energy management practices, hotels are undergoing the use of energy sufficient lighting methods such as solar power, key switches, efficient air conditioners, LED televisions and biomass boilers. There is a contribution with each practice that will assist towards the energy savings on the intensity of adoption. An example would be the savings that arise as a result of percentage of energy efficient bulbs that is used out of the total number of bulbs which is used in particular hotel. So as found out via this interview, key switches are considered to contribute heavily towards the energy savings. There are some water management practices which are being conducted such as dual flush toilets, linen and towel reuse, low flow showers and taps and the main strategy of using treated water for watering the garden and rain water harvesting. There are few instances where water management practices which require the involvement of the guests that can save the amount of water which is consumed. For example, the correct handling of the dual flush toilets and the linen and towel re-use can be undertaken with the involvement of the guest as well. Waste management is also analyzed with respect to two main categories such as the waste water management and the solid waste management. According to the research it was found out that management of waste water and the solid waste is considered to be different from one hotel to another. And secondly the adoption of the waste water management practices were considered to be less common when it is compared with the solid waste management.

With respect to the solid waste management, there are over 65 percent of the hotels waste is collected by the municipal council. However, the research was only considering solid waste management practices. On the other hand, giving out that that waste to the municipal council or the private collectors that has to be dumped at the garbage sites were not taken into consideration with the purpose of analyzing the adoption of a good solid waste management practices. And the sustainable solid waste management practices can be easily assessed with the study that includes the factors of composting, recycling, the 3R Policy and animal feed are considered as important practices to be adopted by the hotels. When referring to the waste water management practices, it was considered in the econometric model as a case in the solid waste management. It is also important to understand that the waste water treatment and the biogas production are considered as two practices which are quite important in the process of waste water management (Wickramasinghe, 2016).

2.15.2 Maintaining an Eco-Friendly environment for Hotels in Colombo with the current Status

As mentioned above creating a green sustainable environment is vital for any hotel business because the modern tourists expect this improvement as it is an emerging trend. The first most important step begins from the hotel employees. It can be crucial to inform the employees to participate in a “green team’ initiative around the area suggesting eco-friendly best practices. This was a practice that was conducted in almost every hotel in Colombo, however the proceedings declined with time but did not continue monthly or annually. By conducting such initiatives this gives a sense of ownership to the employees to develop green strategies and in the long term, employees themselves could provide new ideas to improve the hotel’s sustainability. All the hotels related to this research are offering plastic water bottles as compliments in the hotel rooms with the hotel logo. However, cutting down on the use of plastic water bottles and the use of glass bottles will be very critical. Another beneficial factor would be that hotels could introduce a hotel reward program where guests can use a reusable branded bottle with water bottle filling stations at certain accessible points of the hotel. It is important to make the recycling options quite easy to spot and accessible because while the hotel is become eco-friendly, the satisfaction and the happiness of the guest is key to be achieved. Likewise, a technology improvement linked to this aspect would be filling out the customer information via the hotel

website at the point of reservation. A current process ongoing in the hotels Galle Face Hotel and Mount Lavinia hotel is that even at present customer information is jotted down by the guest as they arrive at the hotel. Also paper is used in taking prints of the guest's passport. These are considered as areas where technology plays a vital role as well as being environmentally friendly. At a point of an interview, most interviewers require a hard copy on paper on the curriculum vitae (CV). This process can also be minimized if a personal computer or a electronic tablet be used to refer to the CV. At the concierge desk, many guests are handed leaflets on certain information and matters required on the sightseeing and other places to visit. However such methods could be minimal as much as possible where documents as such or links could be shared with the guest at the point of reservation of the accommodation. In this manner from the hotel's point of view, the hotel too is becoming eco-responsible as an organization and simultaneously assisting the guest with pre-information. As a method of technology, a successful strategy is that every hotel find strategies to develop remote check-in and check-out via a scan off which would cut down on plastic key cards, reduce the usage of paper unnecessarily where and minimization of the carbon emissions that it causes. All the Hotels in Colombo provide hotel transport via petrol and diesel vehicles which emits harmful emissions to the environment. Understanding this situation hotels need to switch to using Hybrid and electric vehicles. Because the new technology of every vehicle brand is the electric technology. So, from the hotel's point of view many options are available to be eco-friendly in terms of transport. Automate conservation has become a trend and mostly research currently where technology plays a vital role. In has been a major finding that fitting smart showers where showers operate on a pre-set time and does not leave the water running at an occasion where the guest forgets to switch it off. As mentioned prior, the rooms sensors are important to be installed that even dims or switches off the lights automatically by detective natural light levels in the rooms. Thermostats too are important with occupancy sensors that adjusts the heating and AC temperatures. With the use of IoT technology, this allows the guests to connect smartphone apps (hotel website app) so that the guests can change the settings remotely. Hotels can also operate with "green" gift shops with respects to the products sold. Products can be green certified with the assist of ethical clothing companies fair trade accessories and ethical travel gear could be sold in these shops. At the point of check out, every hotel in Colombo offers a paper receipt. However, most organizations have undertaken a new strategy

where an e-receipt is sent to the email of the customer. Likewise, it would be smart strategy for these hotels to adapt this feature as it is also a developed feature of technology.

Apart from strategies set to satisfy the guest in terms of sustainability, it is also important for the hotel owners to conduct audits of equipment to understand that the right amount of energy and power is being used to conduct the hotel operations. The important of this strategy is to identify the current power usage, notice the energy saving opportunities and it will also assist in quantifying the long term and short-term energy savings. The engineering department will have to keep track on the different systems of the hotel. Predictive maintenance is considered as an import element. Hotel owners need to make green decision. For instance, it would be essential to opt for biodegradable, non-toxic products in sustainable packaging. And when purchasing high-end appliances for the hotel it is necessary to purchase energy saving appliances such as ice machines, ovens, freezers and dishwashers. If such decisions are taken for the benefit of the hotel, the hotel would be way ahead in terms of a successful sustainability scheme (Fredericks, 2020).

Major hotel brands have taken steps on developing the future of tourism with respect to sustainability. Marriot International has stated that with the structures and designs bringing out the guest experience, there is sustainability which is embedded in the hotel's business strategy. Therefore, the mother company is developing energy efficient hotels which uses renewable energy sources where possible and finding methods that reduces waste and the carbon emissions. The main aim of the hotel brand is to reduce water use by 15 percent, waste by 45 percent and to use at least 30 percent of renewable by 2025. The hotel industry being a major contributor towards the carbon emissions, many experts put forward that the hotel industry has to lower its emissions by 66 percent in 2030 and by 90 percent by 2050. Hilton Worldwide has taken measure to bring its properties in line with the carbon reductions which is mentioned in the Paris Climate Agreement. The main aim of the hotel chain is to drop the Hilton's global environmental footprint in half by the year 2030 which has proved that over the past few years that the carbon emissions have been low. Currently the Radisson Hotel group is reducing the carbon footprint across the chains by reducing the demand for the energy there is from the carbon dioxide intensive sources and thereby taking measures to make use of the renewable energy sources. Understanding the shortage of food in many parts of the world, and the wastage of food in the hospitality industry

Intercontinental hotel group has partnered with a technology organization Winnow Vision to reduce the hotel food waste by 30 percent over the upcoming years. In the past the hotel group American Hotel and Lodging association has partnered with World Wildlife Fund which created a website as HotelKitchen.org in the year 2017 in order to instruct the hotel industry on methods to reduce the wastage of food. Hotels such as Hilton, Marriott International, Hyatt Hotels and Accor Hotels have also participated in this program. As per the Urban Land Institute in Washington D.C and with respect to a study conducted on “*Sustainability in Hotels: Opportunities and Trends Shaping the Future of Hospitality*” has understood the case on sustainability and in which ways the hotels are striving to follow eco-friendly practices into the operations and constructions. A hotel group called 1 Hotels is a nature inspired luxury hotel which is embedded with sustainability. As mentioned above there are many world renowned luxury hotels which has developed and are developing themselves to become more environmental friendly (Hospitality net, 2020). So, the newest trend lies on improving the and developing hotels technologically and simultaneously achieving the sustainability as well. With most of the information mentioned above, a hotel become sustainable could also mean the hotel improves in the technology aspect with certain improvements made.

2.16 Future of Technology in the Hospitality Industry

When the IoT ecosystem is developing and expanding to new facets every day, the future of technology of the hotels can develop overtime and further modern technology could be introduced in the near future. And this could be further linked to the IoT sensors and devices applied on different service categories. The best example would be Body area Sensors where the smart wearable devices are considered as the best trend of IoT revolution. Technology such as smartphones and smart watches are considered to be used in terms of wearable forms like smart clothing and smart shoes. The purpose of this technology is that the devices then gather important data such as body temperature and the heart rate. Wireless medical sensors operate in ways where technology expands to collecting data of the organs and the systems within the body. And with this modern technology of data gathered via the body sensor networks, the hotel service provider can offer their guests with new services such as the automatic adjustment of in-room temperature based on the body temperature of the guest. This could also adjust the in-room lighting based on

the sleep cycle of the guest. And even provide suitable meal plans with respect to the desired fitness goal of the guest. Understanding this and also meals plan of certain guests, hotels can arrange their menus to fit by preparing low carbohydrate and sugary meal options for guests with diabetics, low cholesterol meal options for guests with heart diseases. Another important strategy would be that the hotel service providers coming up with modern methods to use augmented reality and the beacon technology into the hotel's systems. If such technologies are developed it would assist the guests with new services such as digitally guided tours, provide previews on the types of rooms available, interactive menus in the restaurants with previews of the dishes available and food allergy information too can be provided. The future of the hospitality industry also depends on the several cost saving methods such as attaining green operations in the hotel with the assistance of IoT technology. As mentioned above some of the ongoing energy saving systems include smart lighting and the temperature control systems with the use of low power lighting such as compact florescent bulbs and LED lights. The IoT enabled power outlets and IoT enabled smart devices will alert housekeeping and the maintenance personnel in case a particular outlet will exceed a specific limit for the power consumption over a period of time. Afterwards the service staff of the hotel can track if the guests of the hotel are concerned and mindful of the power consumption or if there is a power leak. The IoT technology can also be adopted to limit the water consumption as well. As mentioned prior certain technology developments can be introduced such as installing smart showers, smart sinks and flow controlled toilets. Also the building of Automation and monitoring can benefit the hotel guests and the hotel immensely. By building automation this can lead to greater operational and efficiency of management in the hotel. A good example would be that in-room monitoring systems can be used to detect if a room is occupied or unoccupied so that housekeeping services could be scheduled. When adapting IoT enabled in-room and on-property guest facing systems this could be used in other public areas such as in elevators and automated doors (Kansakar et al, 2019).

With the ongoing pandemic Covid-19, another future technological improvement which will be made is contactless payment. It is a strategy which is being conducted at the hotels at the moment by contactless payments being made via the hotel website. However if a guest orders any extras such as room service or laundry these charges are not being made prior. Therefore, a strategy where these payments to be made via the hotel website itself or hotel app could be arranged. With

the reference number of the guest it would be convenient for the hotel to track if the guest have made the additional payments upon the guest's check-out. In this way neither the hotel nor the customer will not be dealing with a physical payment card or cash throughout the stay. Most researchers prove that the use of robots is one of the fascinating hotel technologies ever being introduced. Already there are many examples where robots are used in hotels to greet guests upon their arrival but the best example was reported by Zheng (2019) where a robot chef in Studio M Hotel impressed many guests and travelers. The robot is programmed into making a perfect omelette within two minutes into nice golden color. The guests have the option of choosing the ingredients and the rest will be operated by the robot (Zheng, 2019). Apart from this technology development the future relies on adopting robots for housekeeping activities such as floor vacuuming and washing, transportation of luggages and restaurant waiting (Revfine, 2020). Voice controlled services are also considered as an impact caused within the guest room experience. This is where the Air conditioner, Television, lighting can be controlled via voice in the guest rooms. This strategy was adapted first by Intercontinental Hotel group on the brand's hotel in China which is known as AI smart rooms and was developed by Baidu's DuerOS Platform.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The preview of the study's research methods is provided in this chapter. It includes specifics on the report's study protocol, the respondents' backgrounds, and the methods used to choose them. The author explains why the research methodology was chosen for this study. The data collection tool and the methods used to conduct this investigation are each clearly explained. There is additional discussion of the techniques used to analyze the data. This chapter devotes a significant amount of space on how the researcher gathers data to address the research topics. A topic or an issue that has to be addressed often guides how many researchers arrange their study. The researcher then considers the required data and the methods they will employ. The research "onion" used in this paper illustrates the challenges behind the selection of data collecting methods and analysis techniques, meanwhile, places the gathering of data in the center (Orth et al., 2021). In order for people to understand why the study should be considered, the researcher must describe how they arrived at this key core (Saunders et al., 2007). As a result, instead of merely peeling and discarding the onion's outermost layers, researchers ought to comprehend and interpret these components.

Figure 3:- The research Onion

3.2 Research Philosophy

The expression "research philosophy" defines a set of assumptions. A research philosophy is a way of thinking about how knowledge about a phenomenon should be gathered, looked at, and used. There are four different types of research philosophy, according to Mackenzie and Knipe (2006): positivism, realism, interpretivist, and pragmatism.

After reviewing the paper, it has been determined that Positivism is the author's philosophical stance. Conferring to positivists, realism is constant and can be viewed and represented objectively, that is, without interacting with the processes being researched (Goddard and Melville, 2004). They argue that findings should be reproducible and that occurrences should be parted. This frequently entails altering reality by changing only one independent variable in order to find patterns in and establish associates among some of the social world's components. World On the premise of the already seen and explicated facts and their connections, forecasts may be formed. "Positivism has a long and influential history. Modern culture has it so ingrained that assertions of expertise that are not supported by positivist theory are simply rejected as unscientific and hence invalid " (Snyder, 2019), who conducted a survey of 902 IS research publications, discovered that all of the experimental studies used a positivist methodology, which inadvertently supports this viewpoint. Additionally, positivism has had a particularly strong partnership with the natural and physical sciences.

The question whether or not the positivist paradigm is completely appropriate for the social scientists has, even so, generated a great deal of discussion (Kothari, 2004), with many researchers deciding to define for a more pluralism attitude toward the IS methodological approaches (Remenyi and Williams, 1996). Although researcher won't go into greater detail, this argument is relevant to the topic since data sources, which deal with how people and technology connect, are regarded to be part of the social sciences instead of the physical sciences (Gupta and Nitin , 2022). In fact, the positivist paradigm's unsuitability for the field may account for some of the challenges faced in IS research, for example the findings' seeming inconsistency. Similar to how certain variables or elements of reality may have historically been deemed immeasurable within the positivist paradigm, and as a result, have not been studied. The current study has used Technology Acceptance Model, Institutional Theory for presenting the conceptual framework.

And data collection was done according to well-structured questionnaire mainly using primary quantitative data. Hence research philosophy of the study is positivism.

3.3 Approach of research

In general, there are two types of research methodologies: inductive and deductive. While the catalytic method focuses on data collecting and the creation of theories based on the findings of data analysis, scholars employ mitigation technology to construct hypotheses or assumptions on existing theories and to establish research strategies for hypothesis testing. (Saunders, 2009). Deductive approach is selected for this research.

The primary distinction between the two approaches is in how they approach how reality really is. While qualitative theorists "believe in multiple constructed facts that create distinct meanings for various people, and whose explanations rely on the author's eyepiece," quantitative theorists "believe in a universal truth that can be measured reliably and validly utilizing scientific methods." Researchers in qualitative research realize the significance of the interaction among researcher and participant in comprehending the event that may be witnessed, but researchers in quantitative research think that participant separation is crucial.

Finding answers to questions is a rigorous approach to qualitative research. It involves spending a lot of time in the field, often working on complex, time-consuming data analysis processes, inscription long paragraphs, and participating in social and anthropological research that does not have definite guidelines or specific measures.

Last but not least, the fact that hoteliers can choose any method for market research requires that they investigate the need, and that prospective clients need to be determined by their loyal strategies, for which they need to spend money and the specific skills of the marketers - researchers.

3.4 Research Strategy

A strategy is a blueprint for carrying out a certain objective. A research plan will assist the researcher in achieving the research goal and addressing the study's research questions. As a consequence, the decision to use a specific research strategy will be based on one's study's research goal and research questions, as well as one's personal philosophy of what constitutes high-quality research and relevant practical considerations like the availability of different

databases and time limits (Saunders et al., 2017). This study design employs a quantitative research methodology. The information is numerical. The kind of research approach used in this study is survey. A correlation study is a sort of research examination. Due to the fact that academics have used previously published material to identify characteristics that might affect staff and client happiness in hotels.

The kind of research approach used in this study is survey. Surveys provide the researcher the chance to learn about behaviors, conditions, or attitudes during a specific time period by using questionnaires or conducting interviews. Afterwards, using quantitative analytical techniques, existing relationships are deduced from this data (Schell, 1992). A survey is a method of gathering data from or about individuals in order to characterize, contrast, or otherwise explain their expertise, opinions, and behavior (Saunders et al., 2007). Meanwhile it enables the researcher to get quantitative and qualitative data on a variety of research issues, the survey technique is highly popular in the field of business research. In fact, surveys are often used in descriptive and exploratory research to gather information about persons, procedures, or circumstances. In particular, surveys on user decision-making, client satisfaction, and job contentment, the usage of health services, management information systems, and similar topics are often conducted in the business world. These surveys mostly consist of one-time polls. The researcher may track changes over time by keeping track of other ongoing surveys. Usually, the questionnaire items are organized into self-administered surveys that a respondent fills out on their own, whether manually or digitally. Interview and observation methods are other survey tools.

3.5 Time Horizon

In progressive study, time horizons often relate to study intervals or a temporal horizon of different width. Three fundamental time horizons are distinguished by Kosow and Gaßner (2008): short-term, or up to 10 years; moderate, or up to 25 years; and long-term, or more than 25 years. As an alternate temporal horizon, Kosow and Gaßner (2008) additionally identify static views from a point in the future that is often connected with normative tactics. Such a retroactive point is often utilized to build "static" or "end-state" scenarios. The cross section the time range for collecting data, known as the cross sectional time horizon, has already been set. It is known as the "Snapshot" time collection because information is gathered at a specific instant. To solve

a research issue, a research might be conducted in which data are only collected once, sometimes over the course of days, weeks, or months. These investigations are referred to as cross-sectional or one-shot research. The two investigations that follow were designed to gather information that would be useful in determining the answer to a research question. It was sufficient to acquire all the data at once.

3.6 Research Framework

The conceptual framework development is presented as below. The responses individuals provide to verifiable questionnaire items may theoretically be independently checked and have correct and incorrect replies. Instances of topics covered by realistic questionnaire items include how often someone practices, where they perceive themselves to be, and what their necessary habits are. In contrast, attitude inquiries gauge perceptions, emotions, and assessments. In contrast, attitude inquiries gauge perceptions, emotions, and assessments. Also required to mention these questions need to focus on long term, otherwise, it is not effective for the future. Then need to consider and need focus on the relevant customers for collection of the data. Further it is discussed about the method to build the questions using the conceptual framework in below diagram. The questions made are based on these factors which are mentioned below.

Figure 4:- Factors affect to overall hotel conditions

Overall, in this question, the summary is given from this diagram. The entire research process is guided by the conceptual framework. The conceptual framework acts as a "guide" or "propulsion" to direct the researcher in achieving the goals or aim of the study. The author's formulation of the research on how to explain an occurrence is represented by a conceptual framework. Provided the prior knowledge of other investigators' viewpoints and his inferences on the research topic, it lays out the steps that must be taken during the course of the study. The conceptual framework represents the author's knowledge of the connections among the specific variables in the study. As a result, it pinpoints the variables needed for the research study. It serves as the researcher's "map" for carrying out the inquiry. From this conceptual framework is using to decide the overall hotel condition and determine the dependent variable effectivity using the dataset. The dependent variables are effectiveness of the technology product for overall hotel condition, and also determine the technology products and amenities for overall hotel condition. Then analyze the most effective dependent variable for independent variable.

Technology products and amenities are most required in hotel industry we focus not only for local tourist people we need to consider about foreign people because they required good facility for in hotel industry. Improving sustainability via energy efficiency is a concern for many hotels because to a current emphasis on climate change and intense competitiveness in the tourist industry. They are seeking some good facility for their life then need to provide the good condition of technology and amenities for them. The five-star hotels also require good technology and facilities to run the hotel, and if the hotel industry requires them to update with time, otherwise they cannot stay in the industry as competitors. Therefore, with the technology needed to update to achieve the targets.

Then, as a second dependent variable, the researcher considered the hotel industry's technological effectiveness. With technology required to update the entire industry, if guests do not want to stay, hotel management must provide them with the best facilities to live in the hotel, which is the main goal of every hotel owner.

Figure 5:- Conceptual framework of Guest and Employees satisfaction

According to the figure 2 the researcher presented three independent factors that can influence the employee and guest satisfaction, namely Product factors, Channel factor and operations factors. Guest and employee satisfaction is act as the dependent variable of the study. In the above diagram explain the guest employee satisfaction of with above mention three independent variables, so better website is required for achieve the target audience because now a days every person is addicted with the social media, with that need to give the publicity using the social media also required to give the more details about hotels and surrounding locations. Therefore, website is a more required component for the visitors to reach the location and attraction. Apart from having the website will not be sufficient, whereas the quality of the website has to be to a considerable level as this would be the first form of glimpse the guest would have on the hotel.

Hotel managers throughout the globe are under stress to boost profitability while working with constrained resources and in an environment of growing competition. Among the primary ways a hotel's offering may set it apart from its rivals is via its customer service. Academic evidence in tourism and hospitality have often concentrated on a particular facility in another country when addressing management challenges linked to service quality and IT. As a result, Sri Lankan facilities have to be upgraded with this technology. A more thorough knowledge of the

difficulties and existing hotel practices connected to Supply Chain Management (SCM) has been relatively neglected in studies on the hospitality sector.

Tourism is a "social, cultural, and economic phenomena associated to the migration of people to destinations beyond their habitual residency region for personal or professional purposes," according to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Thus, tourism has an impact on aspects of the economy, society, culture, and environment. One of the industries with the biggest economic impacts on various areas is tourism, which has also had some of the fastest development in recent years. The tourism industry, according to the UNWTO, continues to significantly improve the lives of millions of people in 2018 by encouraging both local and global growth, generating jobs, lowering poverty, and shaping the way and tolerance. Because of the effect that tourism has on communities and the environment, as well as its effects on social, cultural, and environmental dimensions, many organizations work to ensure that all people are treated fairly by furthering an international approach to the development, management, and oversight of tourism-related activities.

In terms of energy consumption in the service and commercial building sectors, hotels are among the top five subsectors in addition to their economic effect. The hospitality industry's hotel sector is a significant subsector, and as such, it contributes significantly to total energy consumption and environmental effect in the form of greenhouse gas emissions.

Product sustainability and product convenience and efficiency mainly effect for the guests and employers. Therefore, identify the required different technology improvement that the Colombo five-star hotels need to undergo, then researcher try to identify the new technologies present in the industry. Also, it is required to identify the different technology for need to improve, need to establish and need to identify to enhance the departments. To improve the functioning of the hotel, then it makes the processes simpler and creates a better place to work for the employees. So it is required to gather the data for the employers to understand the level of guest satisfaction. Most Businesses rely on qualitative research to learn more about the actions, objectives, opinions, and motives of visitors and customers since the hospitality sector is so experimental. Businesses may focus on facilities, offerings, and current customers as well as possible new customers. With this approach, it's possible to learn how to craft arguments against rivals' offerings.

3.7 Hypothesis development

A preliminary but testable claim that predicts what researchers anticipate to discover in the empirical data is known as a hypothesis. The conceptual model's underlying theory informs hypothesis, which are often related in character. In keeping with this definition, hypothesis may be summed up as logical connections among two or more variables that are stated as testable propositions. It is anticipated that answers to the issues observed may be discovered by evaluating the hypotheses and verifying the speculated connections (Mourougan and Sethuraman, 2017). According to the research objectives and conceptual framework following hypothesis are developed. According to reaearch, in section four the author will discuss about analysis and results, then further will discuss the effects of the independent variables for dependent variable. And furthermore analyse the questionnaire responses from guests. Based on the review of related literature and study framework, to arrive at the real causes of Guest and Employee satisfaction in this study, the following hypotheses have been tested via two tailed hypothesis tests.

Hypothesis 01

H₀: There is no relationship between the Product Factors and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

H₁: There is a relationship between the Product Factors and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

Hypothesis 02

H₀: There is no relationship between the Channel factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

H₁: There is a relationship between the Channel factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

Hypothesis 03

H₀: There is no relationship between the operational factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

H₁: There is a relationship between the Channel factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel

Hypothesis 04

H₀: There is no any associate between gender and preference of future advanced technological experience

H₁: There is an associate between gender and preference of future advanced technological experience

Hypothesis 05

H₀: There is no any associate between age category and preference of future advanced technological experience

H₁: There is an associate between age category and preference of future advanced technological experience

3.8. Research Data

This dataset presents on data collected by an online survey with a questionnaire using a Likert scale, dichotomous questions, open-ended questions, and demographic questions. These types of questions will be discussed below of this section. Also, in this questionnaire build up with conceptual framework because based on this hypothesis theory build up and analyze the dataset and make the decision based on these theories. The questions adopted in this research are directly linked to the technology that Sri Lanka-based five-star hotels could adopt in the future. The determination of this question is to identify the most effective method from the conceptual framework. A questionnaire is the best way to analyze people's ideas about processes, or thoughts. This list of questions or items identifies the attitudes, experiences, or opinions of the respondents. Significant questions are required to create therefore to receive the answers and insights and thereby the researcher can derive at conclusions. It is very important to design questions accordingly which allows the researcher to get the necessary information. There are also some survey design principles that will help researchers get the information they need from friends or clients.

From the questionnaire, wide range of topics are split into small areas and give meaningful and desirable range of questions. Then these questions provide the meaningful and respectful output of data. When an individual, progress the ideas on one subject they try to divide complex and long questions into several angles using questions, and these cover a different level in research. Also required to be simple and understandable level questions in a questionnaire. Then these rules are required to follow to an acceptable level or succeed in questionnaire for collecting the accurate results from hotel guests

The design of the questionnaire is only one aspect of the survey research, and the survey research also includes the definition of population. When users are interested and required to select suitable sampling method and administrating survey, data required to process and visualize the data using suitable analysis methods and need to interpret it. The most important part of survey research is sampling because the researcher will generalize the results to the population. Collect data from a sample representing the population spectrum for externally valid results. So, these question types are more effective and required to consider before creating the questions because with population and data gathering method then need to think about questions type.

The Likert scale is, when people have new product, service, or technology then it will be analyzed or their opinion or thoughts using from this method. The five main types of Likert style responses they are, strongly agreed, agreed, neutral, disagreed and strongly disagreed. These five types mostly effect for determining the product quality. This is the special category in the questionnaire. Most questionnaires are available with this Likert scale type of questions, because this can easily analyze the users or customers opinion. These types of questions are convenient to analyse and are typical across nearly all trades. With an agreement Likert scale, then the researcher will present guests a series of questions and ask them to answer based on how much they agree or disagree.

Recognizing when to include and how to phrase dichotomous queries can be really helpful in surveys, regardless of the questions' planning or the viewers we are trying to reach, whether it is a customer service survey or customer feedback survey to better understand the satisfaction levels of customers. Considering the quality of data gathering, these dichotomous questions. In general, dichotomous questions may provide questionnaires far more structure and clarity. Indeed, surveys that are purely yes or no are widespread. Nevertheless, there are a lot of factors to take

into account when creating survey questions, not only when using dichotomous questions but also with other question types. As a result, researchers must always strive to find a balance among questions that facilitate data collection and those that safeguard respondent experience. If researchers follow this procedure, it will guarantee that they return with the most insightful and comprehensive data possible, allowing them to make business judgments. Dichotomous questions are an excellent method to get clarification on a number of issues as respondents go through the survey, regardless of the information a researcher is searching for. For instance, these questions might be eliminated if the investigator was conducting a technology-related survey and needed a clear "yes" or "no" from the respondent on if they had prior service experience from hotel industry-related model technology.

These are good survey questions to get more meaningful answers from as people have the opportunity to give accurate feedback. However the questionnaire consists of questions which allows the guests to provide accurate answers relating to Likert scale questions. So two questions on demographics are included in this survey because they are a mix of different forms of questions especially revealing the gender and age. Responders may discuss personal, unrelated things to the study, hence have to be more focused on the study's purpose and highlight the questions' purpose. Then, according to above conceptual framework (figure 3) the questions have to be interrelated with each other to provide the absolute proper information for the researcher to analyse the results to whether it is successful developing Sri Lanka based five-star hotels technologically.

Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catching rooms, this question is in Likert scale type of question, it's mention main five star hotels in Sri Lanka then check the opinion from guests on the above hotels facilities compared with standard hotels in other international chains. The second question is also a sub question of the first question. It's focus is on international five-star hotel facilities compared with the Sri Lankan five-star hotels. This question is also a Likert scale question, so requires a direct answer. The next question focusses on which department is required to develop t technologically. This question is related to the second dependent variable because it

is asking about department facility's effect on the guest and employers' satisfaction in the hotel industry. Further aspects will be discussed in results and conclusion chapter.

Further to understanding the technological aspect of these hotels the author intends to discuss the sustainability factor too. The questionnaire contains few questions which are related to this aspect because eco-friendliness is a trending topic in the current hospitality trade. This question is more effective for the hotel industry because more tourists are concerned about the environment, and their preferences can be identified using this data analysis. Because the environment is a major factor in attraction, much attention has to be directed towards this as well. This question is of the dichotomous type, which means it includes only yes and no options. Questions with respect to guest preference for reservation is vital too. With modern technology, everything changes in a short time, but most people have not adapted towards new technology, so this questionnaire will be important to understand their perspectives.

With the limited technology prevailing in these hotels, the employees are well supportive and effective for the guests because of the limited resource availability. Therefore, many tourists would expect the hotel staff to make changes to the hotel in order to develop the slightest technology at the beginning. Management of hotels needs to give special concern to their amenities or facilities. Most guests are foreign tourists and they can afford more than the local visitors. With this aspect it would be the foreign guests who would leniently consider the technological advancements in detail.

Also, checking the employee's working accuracy and if it needs to improve, the following question will be vital. Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. Then there are also Likert scale questions. When these questions are asked to relate to product convenience and efficiency, then it affects hotel performance and the existence of hotels in foreign tourist fields. Otherwise, visitors do not like to recommend the hotel in the future. Then these services are the most important part of the hotel industry.

When reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed they are. This question is also a Likert scale question. It is to check the product's sustainability. When visitors reserve the room based on technology and facilities, there are slight possibilities that the location of the hotel is given high preference. Most guests look at the facilities as they wish, and because they don't like to live in uncomfortable places,

hotel management is required to provide them as they request. Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use. They want to change the living environment in which they live. They need an attractive place with advanced technology. Then you need to identify the areas that need to be changed and need to improve.

There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel. Therefore, it is required to collect foreign tourist opinions regarding facilities, and areas that requires improvement. With such conditions it is necessary to understand the opinions of guests are realistic and achievable too.

When developing a hotel technologically, there is less need for many employees to be hired. This is a question best suited for employers, because guests do not have an idea about hotel working standards and procedures. Therefore, this question is not suitable for guests or visitors. This question is a Likert scale type question, so it needs to collect the data from employers. This variable affects product convenience and efficiency. When the technology implementation is complete, the maintenance cost is going to increase because this is required to maintain this cost within the budget. Therefore, before introducing new technology, it is required to minimize the cost and analyze the benefits of the new technology. Because every new technology is not given the best accuracy, so before analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of new technology, confirming that this new technology would provide a sense of development to the hotel is vital to understand.

Hotels should require technological developments that are more customer-friendly and not be operated only with permission of employees. Every new technology should be accessed by employees in order to familiarize themselves. So, in case guests have difficulty in operating them, the employees of the hotel could assist them when needed. Therefore, every new replacement requires good familiarity to avoid mistakes and accidents. Therefore, human maintenance is most required to exist for the long term, otherwise these machines and technology would not exist in the long term. Before going to establish the new component, the supervisor needs to give every person the knowledge sharing section or training according to the new machine or new service. Then they can easily adopt to this new technology and become familiarized with the new components.

In the future which advanced technological experience do responders believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction. with technology experience and environment they have good idea about future development and where need to improve and where need to replace with new technology. With the efficiency of work, they have good knowledge about these areas. Therefore, it is required to add with the demand of service with reasonable price, with huge cost it is difficult to cover the costs from guest rates, so hotel management need to add suitable technology with effective and efficient price. Otherwise it would be difficult to present in hotel industry with other competitors. So it is required to consider the business plan, and technology evolution based on these add the changes on the hotel business.

The product factors

The product factors concept builds with these variables. Hotel brand, conditions, product changes, product effectiveness, and sustainability. The hotel brand is the essential variable in five-star hotel concept hotels because, with the brand name, customer brand loyalty is more important in the hotel industry than in other hotels. Tourist guides also recommend hotels to foreign tourists, not considering the hotel's technology, facilities, and customer service. However, the brand name is recommended. Therefore, the new five-star hotels have the disadvantage of the brand name. Technology evolution is an effective indicator in five-star hotels. Technologically advanced hotels have the opportunity to expand their business through promotion or industry highlights. Therefore, these hotels have an excellent chance to promote their business strategy in the industry—product change, with the time period required for a change in every place. For example, the present did not accept the typewriter because it was now available with more advanced equipment than the typewriter. The hotel industry requires advanced technology to deal with the time change. Because technology is changing daily, hotel management needs to be proactive to understand the change. Otherwise, the business will not be able to grow, and customer attraction and product demand will suffer as a result of the lack of updates. As a result, hotels must keep up with the rest of the world. Product effectiveness is automatically increased as technology evolves into a more reliable phase. This change automatically increases customers without any effect. That change needs to be an attractive and valuable change in the time and place; otherwise, that action is not practical. Sustainable hotels use eco-friendly best practices for their operations, management, operations, logistics, goods, and

supplies to lower their environmental effect dramatically. The three main components are minimizing trash, conserving energy, and using less water.

Channel factor strategies

Channel factor strategies are the concept of hotel technology. It works as an independent variable of a futuristic overview. This concept worked with website quality and information quality, payment method, customer relationship, information search intention, and purchase intention like these variables affected for channel factor. The website quality and information-sharing methods are required to be of quality. Otherwise, visitors will not show interest in this hotel, because they are looking for information through websites and social media. Suppose this information is not at standard level. In that case, they do not care about these hotels especially foreign visitors because they need clear information about the hotels with their services and prices. Payment method in the model technology most payments are completed in online, also credit and debit cards also using for this. But foreign visitors are most happy to pay online; they have trust and these guests do not like to use money for security purposes. Therefore, in the hotel industry, service must change according to customer requirements.

Operational factors

Operational factors are views of this research based on this concept have two variables: employee satisfaction and guest satisfaction. These variables have an effect on concept. These variables' intention is technological improvements leading to employee effectiveness leads from employee satisfaction. The customer also satisfied with the effective service. Then guest satisfaction also intention to the technological advancements leading to easy facility usage by hotel guests then this will be a valuable point for customer attraction. This is also a business strategy for customer attraction to hotels. Therefore, with world evaluation, technology development is a key point of this industry. Also, this point describes further in guest satisfaction it is the technological improvements ongoing in a hotel is adequate, most of the three star hotel system does not have sufficient technology development for foreign visitors' attraction with a reasonable price. The guest considers amenities and location primarily price, so they do not want to give money meaninglessly. So, a hotel industry employee is required to be a discreet person.

Futuristic overview

The futuristic overview's main variables are prices, artificially intelligent, and competitive advantage. Prices are going to increase with technology development. But this technological advancement needed to be matched with needs and customer satisfaction since useless, unnecessary technological advancement could not be considered a facility or technological advancement to increase prices. Artificial intelligent technology to perform duties that most employees perform this service need to be efficient and effective service for a visitor; otherwise, this technological improvement is not a valuable service for this. In Sri Lanka, most five-star hotels in the same range provide the same service. Most hotels have the same technology, so it has a competitive advantage. Therefore, guests only consider the location and prices; other benefits are in the same range in Sri Lankan five-star hotels.

3.9. Measurement – Primary data collection

Table 1: Operationalization

Sub Parameters	Question No.	Analysis through questionnaire	Scale of Analyzing
Product Factors	1	Most of the hotel amenities and equipment's require technological developments in this hotel	Likert Scale 1-5
	2	Which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations?	Likert Scale 1-5
	3	Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees	Likert Scale 1-5
	4	Tourists tend to prefer technological developments favoring towards sustainability	Likert Scale 1-5
	5	This hotel can develop further on the concept of Sustainability (being eco-friendly)	Likert Scale 1-5

	6	Do the rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc.	Likert Scale 1-5
Channel Factors	7	As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations	Likert Scale 1-5
	8	The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field	Likert Scale 1-5
	9	Which payment method do you prefer?	Likert Scale 1-5
	10	Payment method should be further developed where transactions are done via a hotel app or website due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic	Likert Scale 1-5
	11	With the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective	Likert Scale 1-5
	12	Employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel	Likert Scale 1-5
	13	Tech Savvy guests and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experiences prior to booking a hotel	Likert Scale 1-5
	14	When reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities are	Likert Scale 1-5
Operational Factors	15	Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catching rooms	Likert Scale 1-5

	16	As a tourist, would you prefer making reservations online via the hotel website?	Likert Scale 1-5
	17	Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. E.g.: developed IT facilities	Likert Scale 1-5
	18	Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use	Likert Scale 1-5
Futuristic Overview	19	Which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel	Likert Scale 1-5
	20	Do most of the international hotels you have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website?	Likert Scale 1-5
	21	Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests' easy access to hotel facilities and benefits	Likert Scale 1-5
	22	There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel	Likert Scale 1-5
	23	In the future hotel prices needs to extensively increase if further technological changes are to be made	Likert Scale 1-5
	24	When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired	Likert Scale 1-5
	25	Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees	Likert Scale 1-5
	26	In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction?	Likert Scale 1-5

Table 5:- Operationalization

3.10 Secondary Data Collection

Data collection in statistics refers to the process of collecting data from all relevant sources in order to resolve the study topic. Evaluating the result of the issue is helpful. One might get to a conclusion about the answer to the pertinent issue using the data collecting techniques. "Data" is the major source of the data collecting techniques. Primary data and secondary data are the two categories into which data may be divided. Data collecting is crucial to any study or business activity since it makes it possible to ascertain a number of crucial aspects of the firm, including performance. Therefore, the act of gathering data is crucial to all streams. The two kinds of data collection techniques Primary Data Collection Techniques and Secondary Data Collection Techniques are separated based on the type of data being collected.

Secondary data is information gathered from sources other than the original user. It indicates that someone has previously analyzed the material and it is already accessible. Books, journals, periodicals, newspapers, and other sources of secondary data are included. It might be either previously released or unreleased data. Publicly accessible data may be found in a number of sources, including:

- Government publications
- Public records
- Historical and statistical documents
- Business documents
- Technical and trade journals

3.11. Data Collection Procedure

Representatives presenting to the 200 guests had circled the intended survey in order to shorten the speech. Information for the survey had been gathered during regular visitor duty hours with permission from the Galadari Hotel, Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel and Kingsbury Hotel management for the respondent's easy reference. The following methods are exclusively used in sociology and fall under the category of qualitative methodology: - Focus groups, a qualitative research method that involves asking a group of individuals about their views, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes regarding a concept, product, service, advertising, idea, or package. Participants are allowed to converse with other participants during questions in an interactive group environment.

3.12. Sampling method

Executives in the hospitality and tourist industries should get acquainted with some of the fundamental terms, ideas, and procedures used in quantitative and qualitative research. The goal is to offer this material in a way that is simple to use and in language that is not technical, and to connect it to sources of further reading and other research websites.

The first stage in choosing the sample is figuring out the population that will be studied. Although it may seem simple and apparent, this is not always the case. For instance, researchers seek to restrict the word "hotel visitors" to people 18 and older when asking them about their recent stays at a hotel. Due to linguistic restrictions, the researcher may only wish to invite visitors who can read and/or speak English. The "respondent qualifications" would be this demographic definition that is more operational. People increase the feasibility of the investigation but also set boundaries for its scope.

It entails a list or set of guidelines for identifying the target demographic. Probability sampling and non-probability sampling are the two categories of sampling techniques. Random selection is used in probability sampling, which enables the use of strong statistical judgments about the whole group. Every member of the population has a possibility of being picked, which is referred to as "probability sampling." Individual units are selected at random from the total group, not consciously, but by some mechanical mechanism, similar to a lottery system. The selection of participants in a non-probability sample is based on non-random criteria, therefore not every participant has an equal chance of being picked. Although it is simpler and less costly to get, this kind of sample has a higher risk of bias. As a consequence, judgments may be more constrained than with probability samples and generalizations about the population may be weaker.

The company has 1200 machine operators in the period of this study. The researcher selected 120 active machine operators in the ABC apparel industry as the target population of the study. Stratified random sampling method is used as the sampling method in this study.

$$\frac{\text{Sample size}}{\text{Population size}} \times \text{Stratum size}$$

A list of random data, which contains preset sets of random numbers, may be found in many statistics manuals. To pick the numbers needed for the sample size, one may start at any location on the table and go in any direction. Nevertheless, technology has provided us with a lot of different options. For example, certain phone systems and statistical software programs, such as SPSS, can generate random numbers.

Non-probability sampling is often used in hospitality and tourism research for quantitative studies despite this important drawback. Non-probability sampling methods are a mainstay of almost all qualitative research approaches.

3.13. Method of Data Analysis

The information gathered by the survey was analysed using SPSS programming and Microsoft Office Excel. Using SPSS software, Pearson's relationship (R esteem), ANOVA, and coefficient (R2 esteem) were used to analyze the link between the ward variable, in visitors, and guest satisfaction in hotel industry, with better web site, Reasonable prices, Product sustainability, and Product convenience and efficiency. These data are having univariate analysis, bivariate analysis, and multivariate research Two variables in the data collection are described and summarized as part of the data analysis process. Bivariate analysis is the term for this. Bivariate analysis, in general, refers to the describing and investigating of correlations between two variables at once. Bivariate statistics will be guided by the assessment of association between variables.

The Statistical Package for the Social Scientists, or SPSS, is one of the most popular, user-friendly, and comprehensive packages. The statistical product and service solutions are now used. BMDP, SYSTAT, and SAS are a few more software programs you could come across that have a similar concept. Any of the package's programme data may be applied with ease after data files have been created and labeled in the manner needed by the package. It is an approachable package. It is the application that is used the most to manage and analyze social science data. It offers tabulation tools and high-quality visuals. You could learn on your own if you were persistent, practiced, and used a solid learning resource.

3.14. Validity of the Questionnaires

The extent to which a research tool measures what it is intended to is referred to as validity. It also refers to how well an empirical measure captures the true significance of the issue being studied. However, if an instrument is unreliable, inconsistent, or incorrect, it cannot measure the desired characteristic.

There are three main categories of validity, according to LoBiondo (2006): content, criterion-related, and construct validity. In this research, the validity of the instrument was evaluated using face-to-face communication, criterion-related, and concept (connecting the notion of human resource managers and the idea of workers) validity.

3.15. Research Limitations

This section focusses on the Limitations which were undergone at the process of the research. The section comprises great techniques for creating appropriate boundaries and see the examples that confirm the idea of creating qualitative research boundaries. Including them in the research can improve the research, as constraints indicate all problems before discovering them, even if indicate weaknesses in future research. Apart from this, when the author points out the limits of the study, it means that the author has studied all the weaknesses of this study and has a deep understanding of the subject. Needless to say, all research has its limits. To be honest with the reader, researcher can make a much better impression than ignoring the restrictions altogether.

There are three main limitations that the researchers have that occurs before the research begins. The first is the design limitation. The design limitation is the limitation that occurs when the project is designed in the mind to achieve the targets. The design limitation limits the access to more research and mythology as the mind is set with the limitations of design. The second is the impact limitation. The impact limitation with the field of study and research, data sets and population regional focus. The impact limitation will happen to the readers of the research and the viewers of the research. The final limitation is data limitation. The data limitation will occur when choosing a data set. The data limitation will affect the research outcome.

Restrictions related to the investigator should also be written and displayed to the reader. Both research and future research need to provide suggestions for relaxing these restrictions. The

research may involve some organizations or individuals, and sometimes may have difficulty accessing these organizations. For this reason, the study needs to be redesigned and rewritten. Researcher need to explain why authors' access to the readers is restricted. Needless to say, all researchers have a deadline when they need to complete their research. Time constraints can adversely affect the research. If this happens, the researcher needs to be aware of it and mention the need for further investigation to resolve the major issue. Some researchers may be biased in their views due to their cultural background or personal views. Further it can affect the research. Apart from this, biased researchers may choose only the results and data that support their main argument.

There are strict rules to limit this section of academic research that need to justify and explain possible weaknesses. Following these basic steps will create a well-structured section.

- Presentations to identify the limits of the research and explain its importance,
- Provide the required depth, explain its nature, ponder to justify the study choices,
- Provide suggestions for overcome the current limitations of the study

Researchers are required to identify the target audience that researcher can recognize potential weaknesses in their work, understand them, and point out effective solutions. That means work does not go beyond the possible failures, but researchers should use them as a good opportunity to overcome new challenges and improve their knowledge. In a typical academic paper, the limits of research may be related to these points.

- Formulating the study's goals, objectives.
- Implementation of data collection method,
- sample size,
- Lack of previous research in the selected field,
- Scope of discussion.

3.16. Research Reliability

First, let's take a look at the same page on the meaning of the term "reliability". Reliability is the extent to which a particular research method or tool can produce consistent results from one test

to the next. In areas like mechanical engineering, it is very easy to conceptualize reliability. For example, if an individual want to know the distance between points on a plane, he or she can use a ruler. The results are relatively reliable if taken several measurements in a row. However, in reality, each measurement taken is not exactly the same as the previous measurement. One of the reasons for this is that the reliability of the measurement depends on the interpretation of the contents of the tool. Is the distance close to $5\text{-}11/16$ inches or $5\text{-}3/4$ inches? Did the individual start the measurement from the inside or outside of the line last time? In this situation, the researcher impose a qualitative interpretation of the tools that are likely to give quantitative results. As a result, reliability (ie consistency) is good, but not perfect.

If a general contractor building a new home or installing a closet, the reliability level of the above measurements ($\pm 1/16$ inch) is probably fine. However, when entered a situation where high reliability is essential, such as calculating the theoretical atomic weight of a kilogram, begin to see where seemingly small deviations can have a significant impact on the overall accuracy of the results. Reliability is as important in the social sciences as it is in the physical sciences. For example, if an individual completes the survey once in January, February, and March, he can call the survey "reliable" if his score doesn't fluctuate. The overall credibility of the survey is expected to decline as it changes from month to month. All research criteria must be consistent throughout the three months. This includes the order of the survey questions, the time the individual took the survey, and the time to think about each question before answering it. Even environmental and contextual factors stand out. If this individual ate breakfast, he scored his survey and even the relative humidity on the day of the test was important. They are all summarized. Social science research can be very difficult to carry out with high reliability.

In reality, scholar cannot control all the details of social science research. Because there are so many variables, their individual and collective effects on the bottom line are at the population level (ie, the world that can potentially interact with the device or system). Of course, this does not prevent us from trying to account for the variables that we expect to be most important. In fact, the main difference in reliability that applies to the physical and social sciences is that the latter must rely almost exclusively on the construction of theoretical models to explain relationships between variables. There is no direct, single, absolute measure of "human cognition." There is only one small substitute. It indirectly teaches an element of cognition (such

as cognitive workload). And through the fusion of these surrogate measures, we insist on cognition as a whole.

The reliability of a study refers to whether the research method can reproduce the same result multiple times. If the research method can produce consistent results, it is probably reliable and not affected by external factors. This valuable information will help researcher to determine if the research method is accurately collecting data that can be used to support research, reviews, and experiments in study area. Researcher must perform the same task multiple times to determine if the investigation method produces reliable results. This usually involves changing some aspects of the survey evaluation while maintaining control of the survey. For example, this may mean using the same test for separate groups of people or using different tests for people in the same group. Both methods maintain control by keeping one item exactly the same and modifying the other to prevent the other from affecting the results of the study.

Types of reliability in research

Researchers can choose from several reliability assessments, depending on the type of research which are doing. The most common ways to check the reliability of the study are:

The first method is testing of reliability is Test-retest reliability. One method of testing and repeating reliability in a study is to give a group of people the same test multiple times over a set period of time. In this evaluation, the survey method and the sample group remain the same, but they change when the method is administered to the group. If the test results are similar each time you give them to the sample group, this indicates that your survey method is likely to be reliable and not affected by external factors such as mood and the day of the week of the survey. Sample group.

The next method is testing of reliability is Reliability in parallel. If researcher use reliability in parallel to evaluate the survey, researcher can perform diverse types of tests on people in the same group to determine whether different survey methods yield the same results. The theory behind this evaluation is that consistent results across research methods ensure that each method seeks the same information from the group and that the group performs in the same way on each trial. This means that the method is likely to be reliable. Otherwise, the participants in the sample group will behave differently and this may change the results.

The next method is testing of reliability is Interrater reliability. In inter-rater reliability testing, several people make evaluations on a sample group and compare the results so that they do not affect factors such as personal bias, mood, or human error of the evaluator. If most of the results from different raters are similar, then the rater collected the same data from the group and the survey method may be reliable and produce useful surveys. This is useful for survey methods, such as observations, interviews, and surveys, where each rater may have different criteria but may have similar findings.

The next method is testing of reliability is Internal integrity reliability. There are two common ways to verify the reliability of internal integrity in an investigation. This usually involves making sure that the internal research method or part of the research method returns the same results. One such technique is halved reliability. Run this test by dividing a survey method, such as a poll or a quiz, in half, giving both halves separately to a sample group, and comparing the results to make sure the method is consistent. Outcome. If the results are consistent, the results of the survey method can be trusted. Other internal integrity tests check the average reliability between elements. This evaluation administers multiple test items on a sample set and calculates the correlation between the results of each method, similar to a parallel-style reliability test. Use this information to calculate the average and use that number to determine if the results are reliable.

3.17. Research Validity

Validity is the range in which the score of a measure represents the variable of interest. But how do researchers make this decision? We have already considered reliability, which is one factor they take into account. If the measures have good test and retest reliability and internal consistency, researchers need to be more confident that the scores represent what they are supposed to represent. However, while the measure is very reliable, it has no effectiveness at all, so more is needed. As an example, imagine someone who believes that the length of his index finger reflects his self-esteem. Therefore, author try to measure the self-esteem by bringing a ruler close to author's index finger. This method is very reliable for testing and retesting, but it is completely unreasonable. The fact that one person's index finger is one centimeter longer than the other does not indicate which one has higher self-esteem.

The validity argument generally divides it into several different "types". However, a good way to interpret these types is that, in addition to reliability, there are other types of tests that must be considered when determining the validity of a measure. Here we consider three basic types: face validity, content validity, and criteria validity. The validity of a survey in a survey is related to the extent to which the survey measures the correct items to be measured. Simply put, validity refers to how well a measuring instrument can measure what it is trying to measure.

Reliability alone is not enough, and countermeasures must be reliable and effective. For example, if individual weight scale is 4 kg wrong (4 kg of his actual weight is highlighted), individual can specify it as reliable because the scale shows the same weight each time you measure a particular item. However, the scale is invalid because the actual weight of the item is not displayed.

In addition, effectiveness can be divided into five types.

Face validity is the most basic type of validity and is not based on a scientific approach and is therefore associated with the highest level of subjectivity. In other words, in this case, the investigator can designate the test as valid because it may appear valid without scientific justification.

The validity of the construct is related to the assessment of the suitability of the measurement tool for measuring the phenomenon under investigation. The application of construct validity can be effectively facilitated by the participation of a panel of "experts" who are familiar with countermeasures and phenomena.

Criteria-related validity includes comparison of test results with results. This particular type of validity correlates the outcome of an evaluation with another metric.

Formative validity refers to assessing the effectiveness of a measurement in terms of providing information that can be used to improve certain aspects of the phenomenon.

The validity of the sampling (similar to the validity of the content) guarantees a large coverage area of the measure within the study area. Since there is no way to cover all the items and elements in the phenomenon, the important items and elements are selected using a particular sampling method pattern, depending on the purpose and purpose of the study.

3.17.1. Research Reliability and Validity

These two terms, reliability and validity, are often used interchangeably when not related to statistics. However, when serious readers of statistics use these terms, they are referring to various features of statistical or experimental methods. Reliability is another term for consistency. If a person takes the same personality test several times and always gets the same results, the test is reliable. The test is useful when measuring the object to be measured. If a personality test results in a very shy person claiming to be really outgoing, the test will not be valid. Reliability and validity are independent of each other. Measurements can be valid but not reliable, or reliable but not valid. Suppose the scale resets ten pounds down. The weight reading is reliable, but it is invalid because you have not read the actual weight.

The reliability and validity of the results depends on creating the right study design, choosing the right methods and samples, and conducting the study carefully and consistently.

The first one of the reliability and validity consideration is Guarantee of effectiveness. This is used when measuring changes in something (psychological traits, skill levels, physical traits, etc.) using scores or ratings, it is important that the results reflect the actual changes as accurately as possible. Validity should be considered early in the investigation when deciding how to collect the data.

The next one of the reliability and validity consideration is select the appropriate measurement method. Make sure your measurement methods and techniques are of high quality and are intended to accurately measure what you want to know. They should be thoroughly investigated and based on existing knowledge.

For an example, to collect data about personality traits, researcher can use standardized questionnaires that are considered reliable and effective. If researcher create his own questionnaire, researcher should carefully and accurately express your question based on established theory or the results of previous studies.

The next one of the reliability and validity consideration is Select the target using the appropriate sampling method. This is when to produce valid generalizable results, clearly define the population researcher are investigating (for example, people of a particular age group, geographic location, or occupation). Make sure researcher have enough participants and that they represent the population.

The next one of the reliability and validity consideration is Reliability guarantee. Reliability must be considered throughout the data collection process. When collecting data using tools or techniques, it is important that the results are accurate, stable, and reproducible.

The next one of the reliability and validity consideration is Apply methods consistently. For that carefully plan researcher method to perform the same procedure for each measurement. This is especially important when multiple researchers are involved.

The next one of the reliability and validity consideration is Standardize study conditions. This is considered when collecting data, try to make the situation as consistent as possible to reduce the impact of external factors that can cause variability in results.

It is appropriate to discuss reliability and validity in the dissertation and in the various sections of the dissertation. By showing that researcher take them into account in planning your study and interpreting the results, your study will be more credible.

3.17.2.Ethical Validity

Ethical considerations in research are a set of principles that guide the design and practice of research. Scientists and researchers must always adhere to certain codes of conduct when collecting data from people.

The goals of human experimentation often include understanding real-world phenomena, investigating effective treatments, investigating behavior, and improving lives in other ways. There are important ethical considerations in deciding what to research and how to conduct that research.

These considerations are

- Protect the rights of research participants
- Increase the validity of your study
- Maintain scientific integrity

Research ethics is important for scientific integrity, human rights and dignity, and cooperation between science and society. These principles ensure that participation in the study is voluntary, informed, and safe for the study subject. Balance the pursuit of important research goals with the use of ethical research methods and procedures. It is always necessary to avoid permanent or undue

damage to participants, whether careless or not. Contrary to research ethics, it also reduces the credibility of the research, as it is difficult for others to trust your data if your method is morally questionable. Even if a research idea has value to society, it does not justify violating the human rights or dignity of research participants.

Voluntary participation means that all research subjects are free to participate without pressure or coercion. All participants can withdraw or leave the study at any time without feeling obligated to continue. Participants do not have to provide a reason for leaving the study. It is important to make it clear to participants that refusal to participate will have no adverse effects or consequences. After all, they are taking the time to help you through the investigation process, so you should respect their decisions without trying to change their minds.

Informed consent is a situation where all potential participants receive and understand all the information, they need to decide whether or not to participate. This includes information about the research benefits, risks, funding, and institutional approval. We usually ask participants to read and provide them with a text asking if they have any questions. If responder agree to participate, he or she can sign or initial the agreement. Note that this may not be sufficient for informed consent, especially when working with a group of vulnerable people. If researcher collect data from people with low literacy rates, be sure to give your consent form verbally before agreeing to participate. Participants with extremely limited English proficiency should always translate their learning materials or work with an interpreter to ensure all information is available in their native language. Surveys of children often require the informed permission of parents or guardians to participate. Children cannot give informed consent, but it is best to ask for their consent to participate, depending on their age and maturity.

Anonymity means that we do not know who the participants are and cannot link individual participants to the data. To ensure anonymity, do not collect personally identifiable information such as names, phone numbers, email addresses, IP addresses, physical characteristics, photos, or videos. In many cases, it is not possible to truly anonymize data collection. For example, some personal identification (demographic data or phone numbers) cannot be hidden, so data collected directly or over the phone cannot be considered completely anonymous. Also, if you want to give participants the option to withdraw data at a later stage, you will need to collect some identifying information.

Pseudonymization of data is an alternative way of replacing a participant's identifying information with a pseudonym or false identifier. The data can still be linked to participants, but it is difficult to link because it separates personal information from survey data.

Confidentiality means knowing who the participants are but removing all identifying information from the report. All participants have the right to privacy and must protect their personal data while it is stored or used. Even if you cannot collect data anonymously, it should be as confidential as possible.

The method of communicating research results can cause ethical issues. Good science communication is honest, trustworthy, and trustworthy. It is best that the results are as transparent as possible.

Whenever possible, proactively avoid plagiarism and take steps to investigate fraudulent activity.

Plagiarism means presenting someone else's work as your own. Copying someone else's work without proper credit, which may not be intentional, is the same as stealing. It is an ethical issue in research communication, as it can benefit from harming other researchers. Duplicate is the reissue or resubmission of a portion of your article or report without properly quoting the original work. This is problematic because you can benefit from presenting your ideas as new and original, even if they have been published elsewhere in the past. It can also infringe the copyrights of previous publishers, violate ethical code, and waste time and resources in doing so. In the extreme case of self-theft, the entire dataset or document may be duplicated. These are important ethical violations as they can bias the findings if they are considered the original data.

Research fraud means forgery or falsification of data, manipulation of data analysis, or misrepresentation of results in research reports. It is a form of academic injustice. These actions are intentional and can have profound consequences. Research fraud is not a simple mistake or disagreement about data analysis. Research fraud is a serious ethical issue as it can compromise scientific integrity and institutional credibility. It leads to a waste of money and resources that may have been used for alternative research.

3.17.3. Generalized Validity

Validation generalization refers to the ability to predict the value of the validity factor in a new but similar organizational setting using the validity factor obtained in previous studies in the

organizational setting. The validity factor obtained in the old situation is "generalizable" if the evidence suggests that it can be used to predict the magnitude of the validity factor in the new situation. Perhaps more important is the belief that validation analysis may not be necessary in new situations if the evidence for generalizability of validity is widespread. Conversely, if generalizability evidence of validity is not available, or if existing evidence suggests a lack of generalizability, a 'local' or 'situation-specific' validation analysis is required in the new situation.

3.18. Data Analysis

3.18.1. Data Analysis software

The test's collected data is subjective data that is transformed into quantitative data using the five-point Likert scale method. Employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, which data will be evaluated (SPSS, Version 24). The demographic characteristics and illustrated observations will be the fundamental advancement in the analysis of the data. The consistent quality checks and the relationship between the elements will then be calculated. The recurrence research will be finished to evaluate the developed hypothesis.

3.18.2. Reliability Statistical Analysis

An indicator of internal consistency, or how closely linked a collection of items are to one another, is reliability analysis. It is regarded as a gauge of scale dependability. That in research settings, a reliability coefficient of .70 or above is regarded as "acceptable".

3.18.3. Normality Statistical Analysis

An examination of normality should be performed for each variable as a preliminary assessment since the research has sufficiently many answers (N=200). Modeling the replies as regularly distributed random variables is recommended.

3.18.4. Inferential Statistical Analysis

A stratified random sample of the population was used for this study, therefore the researcher had to use this analytical method since it was unable to examine every participant individually. This explains the population and draws conclusions about it. In this investigation, the researchers employed inferential statistics to assess the likelihood that an observed difference between groups is a reliable one or one that may have occurred by chance.

3.18.5. Correlation analysis

A statistical method for determining the strength and direction of a relationship between two variables is correlation analysis. The correlation coefficient spans the range of +1 to -1 depending

on how strong the connection is. A value of 1 indicates a perfect correlation between the two variables. The link between the two variables will deteriorate as the correlation coefficient value approaches zero. The sign of the coefficient denotes the strength of the relationship. A good connection is denoted by a plus sign (+), while a bad connection is shown by a minus sign (-). A statistical method known as hypothesis testing is used to deduce statistical conclusions from experimental data. To test a hypothesis about a sample statistic is to make a presupposition about it. Significant values for each variable are used to test the hypothesis. If the significant number (P value) is less than 0.5, the null hypothesis may be accepted. In the event that the P value exceeds 0.5, the null hypothesis may be disregarded.

3.18.6. Regression Analysis

The strength of a cause and effect link between the variables was evaluated using regression analysis. It aided in determining how strongly a dependent variable correlated with one or more independent variables and statistically supported the research premise.

3.18.6. ANOVA Analysis

To determine if the survey or study findings are meaningful, ANOVA test can be used. In other words, it aids in determining whether the null hypothesis or the alternative hypothesis should be accepted. Simply, employing test groups to compare them and determine whether there is a difference.

3.18.7. Regression coefficient

A statistical indicator of the typical functional connection among two or more variables is the regression coefficient. Regression analysis considers one variable to be dependent and another to be independent. As a consequence, it gauges how much one variable depends on another.

CHAPTER IV

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher had presented and analyzed the data by using a Statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS). In this section it discusses about data analysis, where the researcher collect the data using a survey from foreign guest and employers.

The main target is providing the best service to the guests in five star hotels. The customer is the main key value in the hotel industry, from local guest thoughts the researcher need to give special concern for foreign guests. As this would assist to identify the perceptions and the mindsets in which the foreign tourists may have. Because currently Sri Lanka is undergoing an economic crisis, causing the loss of tourism in the nation. However, understanding the areas for improvement will be essential when tourism begins to boom in the future.

The nominal or categorical variables that come from this technique of data collection provide a list of options without any discernible hierarchy, such as the initial trip question or hair color. A categorical variable's mean has no significance. Using cross-tabulations, frequency tables, and the mode with categorical variables is important at such situations. Using bar charts to visualize this kind of data (or pie charts if an individual wishes to show proportion) can also be essential. The answer options for ordinal variables are assumed to have a certain order. (5 being extremely agreed, 4 being in agreed, etc.) Use frequency tables (perhaps even cumulative frequencies), cross-tabulations, and the median and mean for these variables. Results may be advantageously be shown in bar charts. The author can use many statistics and, if needed, the author can condense them down into ordinal groups if the questionnaire produces some continuous variables (for example, age in years where an individual is aware on each year is the same distance apart from the next and if the researcher knows the actual age, it could be reclassified the data into age groups.)

Mainly checking the hypothesis validity using ANOVA and checking the frequency of each variable using visitors responds are vital. Then visualize the data using bar chart, then this method can be considered possible for interpretation. Correlation results are also important to describe the variable impact using this interpretation most importantly to reach the objective of the research.

Therefore, it is required that the accuracy of the data analysis using SPSS and essential to apply the best analysis method for using this method. Further, develop the linear equation based on the conceptual framework, and identify the most affected variable for the hospitality industry.

4.2. Descriptive statistics

4.2.1. Demographic data analysis

According to given table 2 is frequency of gender-wise, highest frequency given from male foreign visitors because they are likely to share their idea about their experience in the chosen hotels. And also, they need to share their experience on areas that need to increase the quality, in which they are expecting for a peaceful and suitable place of stay with the best facilities. Then the hotels would want to provide the highest quality facilities to match the needs of these guests. And this is the main vision of the hotel staff. With the 200 overall respondents being adopted in filling out the questionnaire, it can be understood that the male group had more concern about the technological aspect moving forward.

Table 2: Frequency Table of Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	59	29.5	29.5	29.5
	Male	141	70.5	70.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 6:- Frequency Table of Gender

When the graph of gender is considered, the highest number of participants for the survey is from the male group and it reaches three quarter of the total percentage of the participants. While the female participants are just above the quarter of the total number of participants. The male participants reaches a total of 141 participants of total 200 participants which gives a percentage of 70.5 %. The male participants are high because most of the male tourists who travel to Sri Lanka for the purpose of conferences and office meetings in the chosen five stars hotels. As all the hotels adopted in this research are rich in revenue obtained via conference and meeting sales. The remaining 29.5 % of the total percentage are females and most of the females are solo travelers while others are bloggers and reviewers of the hotels. The percentages show that most of the males visit the five-star hotels more than the female by nearly three times of the female percentage. As

per the research conducted it was confirmed with many guest responses that the male category had the most arrivals for business due to many corporate offices in the center of Colombo.

Figure 6: Graph of Gender

In table 3, this represents the summary of age group in responders, most responders include in 20-30 age group, this can conclude young travelers are most like to visit five-star hotel category, hotels as they want to get new experience and also experience new culture around the world . It can be understood that the youth are tech-savvy and they require the best high quality places to reside at. When considering the present generation, the most important component they look for would be WIFI than the older generation. According to the table 3 majority of the responders were on 20-30 age category denoted as 62% from total sample. Because they are eager to share their experience and they like to show improvement towards the hotels from their experiences on how the hotel could develop and what they would expect in their next visit. And this age category is quite aware on how technology has improved in the hotels in their home country. This provides a clear view of aligning similar ideas of different tourists and commencing the technological developments of the chosen hotels in this research.

Table 3 - Frequency table of age group

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 - 30 years	124	62.0	62.0	62.0
	20 - 30 years	66	33.0	33.0	95.0
	41- 50 years	10	5.0	5.0	100.0

	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
--	-------	-----	-------	-------	--

Table 7:- Frequency table of age group

The age groups of the visits that five star hotels can be categorized to three age groups as twenties, thirties and forties age groups basically twenties are 20 - 30 and thirties 31 - 40 and forties is 41 - 50. Most participants are from the age group between 20 – 30 which is just over the half of the participants and equals to 62 % of the total participants in the survey which is 124 participants from the 200 participants. The 20 – 30 age group has participants that is greater than twice of the age group of 31 – 40 age group. The 31 – 40 age group has a percentage of 33 % which is 66 participants from the total of 200 participants to the survey. The lowest of the age group is the 41 – 50 group that is 10 participants from the 200 participants. The gap between the highest age group and the lowest group is 32 participants which is also more than 50 % of the participants. The highest participation is nearly equal to the 13 times of the lowest number of participants, which means that the 41 – 50 group is 13 times less than 20 – 30 age group. The gap between the lowest and the middle is 10 participants, and it is nearly equal to 20 % of the participants for the survey to find the hotel digitalization. The age group 31 – 40 group is nearly equal to 5 times of the 41 – 50 age group. The gap between the highest and the middle graph is 23 participants, and it is also nearly equal to the 50 % of the total participation. The 20 – 30 age group is nearly three times of the 31 – 40 age group and this shows the youth have more free time to enjoy the lifestyle than middle aged and elderly people.

The above table provides a clear view, how the young generation is keen and interested in travelling. Most of these tourists enjoy the beaches in Sri Lanka and whilst they have mostly travelled with a purpose of business and leisure. Considering in a normal household which consists

of 2-3 youth in general, some have travelled with their parents. This assisted in the research to obtain a clear overall view on what expectations the youth would expect to see in these hotels.

Figure 7:- Bar chart of age group vs frequency

Table 5 shows the frequency of department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel. According to table 5 is frequency table of responds, it is display as a frequency and percentage of respond values and valid percentage of responds and cumulative percentage value of these responses. The world has been developing technologically over the past few years. However it can be said that technology cannot be adopted towards every single department. Certain departments or places cannot to be applied for new technology facilities because some technological advancements are impossible to apply, or the staff show unhappiness in adapting for the new technology. With these reasons, few departments do not render good service for their guests. Afterwards, hotel guests show dissatisfaction that would result in bad reviews and numerous complaints. Therefore, it is not only useful for accommodation in the hotel industry. They should be concerned with the technological development of both accommodation and employee services as well

Food & Beverage is the main core aspect of these hotel, This is considered as a crucial department which needs to provide extensive service for their guests. As mentioned prior when referring to order taking every waiter would note down the guest's order in a notebook which could be quite

time consuming and of hassle. Most technologically developed hotels use electronic tabs to note down the order which shows professionalism and hassle-free. Therefore, every critical section and time is required to identify, and they want to provide the effective solution for these problems. According to the analysis, most visitors marked as a front office have a poor technology, and it's required to provide the best service, because this is the department which a tourist observes first when entering the hotel, if it provides poor attraction or service this would cause guests dissatisfaction to stay or repeat arrivals. 38.5 percent people respond as Sri Lankan five-star hotel Front office does not have suitable technology and frequency as 77 responders. This analyzes make the change of hotel industry specially effect in Sri Lanka based five star hotels. 39.5 percent of people respond as F&B have poor technology that is denoted as 79 responders. Only 44% of responders mentioned as housekeeping department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel

Table 5: Frequency table in which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Front Office	77	38.5	38.5	38.5
	Food & Beverage	79	39.5	39.5	78.0
	Housekeeping	44	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 8: - Frequency table in which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel

Figure 8;- Bar chart of in which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in hotels

When considering the departments mentioned above, these departments' service and technological advancements are quite visible to the guests. Therefore the respondents were able to provide clear answers on their experience which they had with the five star hotels overall during their stay.

Table 6 and figure 6 represent the Frequency of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past the guest's expectations. According to above table 6 most visitors respond as a front office denoted as 39.5% from total sample size and frequency of responders are 79. Because despite technological improvements the staff's service was said to be exception. From the front office associate towards the bellman there were friendly and supportive gestures where the guests were quite happy and satisfied about in these four hotels. All visitors are looking effective service in food and beverage department that is denoted as 38.5% form total sample and 77 responders. Many guests were satisfied on the dining etiquette of the stewards and their friendly conversations. Also the guests admired the attire of the stewards that matched the atmosphere of these hotels. Unwittingly guests expecting the best service from these departments, simultaneously the hotel needs to take measures to develop the technology aspect to provide exceptional service. Every guest could measure service standards on front office, food and beverage and housekeeping departments, whereas the production and efficiently of technology used in the kitchen department cannot be measured by the guests.

Visitors respond to an effective department as a front office with 39.5 percent of people responding, the second highest number of responses being to food and beverages and 38.5 percent as an effective department. It is the cumulative value that accounts for 78 percent of the total responses from front office and food and beverage department. As per table 5 Front office technology advancements are low level but their service was effective towards their visitors. Only 4% of responders mentioned that Kitchen department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past the guest's expectations as denoted as 8 responders. Even though the quality of the food was upto the expectations, the efficiency of the chefs cannot be measured by the guests which made them rate this department as low. 18% of responders mentioned that Housekeeping department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past the guest's expectations as denoted as 36 responders.

Table 6: Frequency table of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Front Office	79	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Food & Beverage	77	38.5	38.5	78.0
	Housekeeping	36	18.0	18.0	96.0
	Kitchen	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 9:- Frequency table of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations

Figure 9:- Bar chart of which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations

represent the frequency of guest experience of the rooms in these hotels provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc. This question carries significance as the current trend of most hotels are being eco -friendly. Because most of the hotels are pursuing to follow eco-friendly trends, reduce environmental pollution as it is identified that many tourists are searching for eco-friendly getaways. As mentioned prior these four hotels are yet developing to become eco-friendly completely but few measures being taken for improvement. Also, hotel owners are required to have some knowledge about the green process, and eco-friendly theme ideas, then required to give the training towards the employees on how to promote an eco-

friendly environment in their respective hotels. This question is on product factors. Its main variable is sustainability and its indicator is certain technology developments being eco-friendly. Then visitors feedback are given as a yes, because in Sri Lanka five star hotels the main concept is develop the eco-friendly system in every department with the purpose of saving the environment. Because many tourists prefer eco-tourism and this is regarded as a major concern for many tourists who are visiting Sri Lanka. The most important criteria identified in these hotels would be the use of disposable bags in packaging and carrying items. Using polythene bags is minimal to a certain level. 81 percent of people respond as a yes for this question. Because they highly regard eco-friendly concept in these hotels. The older generation who are familiar with eco-friendliness as they may be used to normal concept, then they responded as a ‘no’. The reason behind this was that the concept of eco-friendliness in hotels emerged recently where the younger generations were quite aware and mindful about. So most respondents of 20-30 age group have the knowledge on eco-friendly concept. Few people having in other age category, most probably above 50 age range people do not have a clear knowledge about what is eco-friendliness and its effect for this hotel. Majority of responders mentioned that particular hotels rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc. that is denoted as 84% from the total sample, and 168 responders. Only 32 responders (16%) guest responded that hotel do not provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc. The lower responders as ‘No’ were basically tourists who were travelling for one or two nights where the amenities were not merely identified.

Table 7: Frequency table of Do the rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	168	84.0	84.0	84.0
	No	32	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 10:- Frequency table of Do the rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc.

In table 8 is a frequency table of visitors, would they prefer making a reservation online via the hotel website, all the responders make as a ‘yes’, because they want to reserve their rooms before arriving at the respective hotel so that just in case their flight got delayed or arrive at midnight these guests have a place to stay. This is a hassle-free method and guests prefer not to make long

distance calls for making reservations. Even though there are some historic hotels, the adoption of their own website has made it convenient for tourists to make reservations from any part of the world. This is the advantage of this online reservation. Therefore, all visitors prefer to reserve their hotel accommodation via online. 100 percent of the respondents acknowledge with this question because they prefer a quick process at check-in without any hassle. This question is in channel factors strategy category. Because good quality websites are essential parts to share the valuable and valid information regarding the place, amenities offered and more importantly the prices. This quality resource makes the key lead factor for purchase intention of the customers. So it is important to share correct information to the guests with quality content. Understanding the quality of the hotels websites and the validity all the 200 respondents regarded their respective hotels to have updated websites which assisted the guests immensely to reserve their accommodation online.

Table 8: Frequency table of as a tourist, would you prefer making reservations online via the hotel website?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	200	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 11:- Frequency table of as a tourist, would you prefer making reservations online via the hotel website?

Table 9 presents the experience of guests of the hotel international hotels have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website, these hotels are most popular and high rated hotels in Sri Lanka. Then these hotels facility details are available on their social media pages and website. And many guests add reviews mentioning the quality of the hotel that would assist other guests prior to making a reservation. Although, 83 percent people answered as a ‘yes’ for this question, because they have a good idea about the website of the hotel. Then its variable is information search intention category where guests perform a large degree of information survey before reserving online. 17 percent of people respond as a ‘No’ which provides a count of 34 number of people. Therefore, this question highly affected for visitors’ attraction, and customer intention towards hotels. However what is identified from the respondents who ticked ‘No’ is that they may not have travelled regularly or may have reserved budget hotels in their prior stays.

Table 9: Do most of the international hotels you have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	166	83.0	83.0	83.0
	No	34	17.0	17.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 12:- Do most of the international hotels you have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website?

The frequency in Table 10 contains the payment method they prefer which is cash, online or physical debit/credit card transaction. From these methods most respondents prefer physical debit/credit card transaction which is 47, as a number 94 people out of 200 people then its nearly covers half population from this survey. Secondly, they like pay cash as a percentage 32 percent from this population. This question is in channel factor strategy category in payment method variable. Because when considering the types of guests considering the age groups, the younger generations tend to use physical debit/credit cards more than the older generation. This is in fact a perception that is endowed in many guests that the secured payment method is to make it at the hotel premises. Therefore, it can be noticed that the majority of the guests make cash or card payments at the hotel itself. And it can be identified that many guests would make the reservation online and thereafter make the accommodation payment at the time of checkout. Only 21% of responders mentioned that their preference would be online transaction as payment method that is denoted as 42 responders. These types of guests are quite familiar with the online transactions due to repeat arrivals to the hotel or other repeat purchases.

Table 10: Guest and employee preference for payment method

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Cash	64	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Physical debit/credit card	94	47.0	47.0	79.0
	transaction Online	42	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 13:- Guest and employee preference for payment method

Figure 10:- Guest and employee preference for payment method

Table 11 frequency table of in the future where advanced technological experience where the guest believes there will be a major positive impact on customer satisfaction. it mentions on the main technology advancements in the hotel industry which are advanced PMS system, Kiosk machines, robot technology and smart rooms. Advanced PMS system is an accurate system for employers and customers, to provide the satisfying service which can reduce the work tasks using this system. Hotel property management system main tasks are encompassing the activities in different departments via the system rather than verbally. Also administrative and daily operation tasks are been divided among the staff which would help to provide reliability, and quality service from time to time. This system allows management of the back and front office operations, handling reservations and channel management. Also, this system provides the report for management level, and it assists the heads of departments to take decisions relating to the hotel.

In hotel industry, different hotels are more competitive among each other in terms of revenue and facilities. Based on this these hotels can create a unique atmosphere by using kiosk machines, it provides a customer satisfaction offering inspiring solutions like mobile hotel, that is provided on kiosk machine. Using this machine, guests could avoid the long queues in the front office, The kiosk is seamlessly connected to the property's hosting cloud to provide a more efficient, connected, and modern hotel experience. Robot technology can be further advanced in the hotel industry but would provide the best service to customers within the limited time period. However certain tasks may not be performed via robot technology such as thinking and manual duties. But

this strategy would be an evolution for this industry. So, as a massive turnaround in the hotel industry the researcher tends to obtain the perception from guests on this regard, then minor improvement could be undertaken with time. The use of robot technology would be an upgrade on the speed of service, cost-effectiveness and precision. However, robot technology can be only introduced for duties such as providing directions and information to the guests and luggage delivery. Also, many human errors can be avoided using this technology. However, robot maintenance cost can rise with investment cost. Therefore, when introducing robot technology it has to serve the hotel long term. Only 4% of responders prefer for future facilities in robot technology in the study. The reason would be that guests understand that robot technology is only limited to certain tasks and cannot perform extra as they are computerized. And it could be a disadvantage, when these machines are required to operate with guests, these technologies need to identify the customer major requests, and when these requests are beyond what the robot technology can perform the guests would be dissatisfied. So it is required to consider before adding the technology for this industry, also need to balance every duties of the staff with the requirements of the staff. Smart rooms are also providing more benefit than other technology, as it increases the convenience level of the guests. Then it improves the standard level of these traditional hotels.

This question concept is in futuristic overview category, then the main variable is in artificial intelligent category because it is beneficial for both parties the guests and the hotel employees. 103 people respond as a smart room service which is the most effective and required technology for hotel industry, so guests believe that the hotel's traditional atmosphere could be further developed when the rooms are further developed technologically. This number as a percentage of total represent 52 percent people respond as a smart room is accurate service in the hotel industry. Secondly highest count of responses as an advanced PMS, it is also one of the best and suited system for hotel industry denoted as 32% of responders from total sample and frequency of responders are 64, and this strategy is beneficial mainly for the employees. This allows the employees with increased efficiency in tasks allowing the guests to be satisfied with the hotel processes.

Table 11: Preference for In the future, advanced technological experience, do you believe, will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Smart rooms	104	52.0	52.0	52.0
	Advanced PMS system	64	32.0	32.0	84.0
	Robot technology	8	4.0	4.0	88.0
	Kiosk machines	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 14:- Preference for In the future, advanced technological experience, do you believe, will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction?

4.2.2. Descriptive data analysis for variables

Product factors (PF)

Table 12 present the agreement for statement of “As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations”. More foreign tourists who are looking for five star hotels facilities and technology advancement for their accommodation is dependent with the age group and gender. Many tourists do not especially consider such factors especially the older generation or tourists who travel with a specific purpose rather than leisure. The tourists who are frequent travellers, there are high possibilities that they would expect most hotels are up to their expectation despite not going through the hotel amenities through the website. This question’s main idea is from guests looking at five star hotel accommodation based on country-based technological advancement. When many foreign guests have experience staying at five-star hotels, and most visitors respond as the perception lies as all the hotels are possessing equal facilities. At certain situations would expect service and quality to be the same. Only 47.5 percent of the population has high percentage as an agreed percentage in this analysis. 95 people respond as an agreed in this study major age group 20-30 as this would be the tech-savvy group. In a second highest respond count would be on strongly agreed category as a percentage 34.5 percent. Therefore, the highest frequency, which covers the most strongly agreed-upon and agreed-upon categories, covers 82 percent as a percentage.

Table 12: As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations (PF1)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	35	17.5	17.5	18.0
	4	95	47.5	47.5	65.5
	5	69	34.5	34.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 15:- As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations (PF1)

In five star hotel sector required technological development in hotel amenities and equipment's. Because hotels required to give attractive and effective service for foreign visitors and the frequency of the statement agreement is presented in table 13. Smart guest experience is the best tool for guests who have visited because this technology predicts the data based on previous experience of guest and personalizing the different services. It then offers accommodation benefits for the needs of guests. Also, smart energy management is the effective and best product for hotel industry. This is via solar power systems which is also eco-friendly. Because it is vital that every hotels develop gradually to suit the needs of the guests technologically. As mentioned prior many guests adore these chosen hotels for their heritage culture and the management will have to consider strategies to develop these hotels one step further by developing them technologically.

According to the question, most people respond with a consensus response, which is 58 percent of the population agrees with the agreed category. 30 percent of the population strongly agreed. Therefore, the cumulative percentage is 88 percent in both categories, which is the highest percentage of the population responding positively to this question. Therefore, many five-star hotels need high-tech facilities for foreign visitors. Hoteliers should therefore decide on a plan to develop those facilities, and a suitable and quality proposal is needed to restructure the hotel industry.

Table 13: Frequency table of Most of the hotel amenities and equipment's require technological developments in this hotel (PF2)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	4	2.0	2.0	2.0
	2	3	1.5	1.5	3.5
	3	19	9.5	9.5	13.0
	4	115	57.5	57.5	70.5
	5	59	29.5	29.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 16:- Frequency table of Most of the hotel amenities and equipment's require technological developments in this hotel (PF2)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

In frequency table 14 describes if this hotel can develop further on the concept of sustainability. In Sri Lankan hotels, they have already maintained the concept of the sustainability, but some foreign visitors, may have the idea about advanced technology with sustainability with their experience and knowledge. So most of the respondents added the strongly agreed with this question. Being eco-friendly is to reduce the usage of plastic and polythene mainly. Actually they are widely used across Sri Lanka and in many hotels for guests to carry items. And introducing plastic straws for beverages has become quite common to be more sustainable. On the other hand complementary water bottles are now introduced in glass bottles. This way there is a huge guarantee that these hotels are gradually becoming sustainable.

The highest respond count having on strongly agreed category, as a count 98 people. As a percentage of this value 49 percent of people respond and second highest respond value having on agreed category. 36 percent of people respond for this category. As a total percentage of in total agreed category 85 percent of total respond in 200 people. As a neutral respond 30 people from total respond, and one person having in strongly disagreed category, based on these respond visitors expected accurate workers in hotel industry with technology advancement.

Table 14: Frequency table of this hotel can develop further on the concept of Sustainability (being eco-friendly) (PF3)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	30	15.0	15.0	15.5
	4	71	35.5	35.5	51.0
	5	98	49.0	49.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 17:- Frequency table of this hotel can develop further on the concept of Sustainability (being eco-friendly) (PF3)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

In table 15 frequency table question is when reserving a hotel room, all tourist people only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities. According to this question, a guest prior to reserving their hotel rooms consider the hotel facilities, advanced technology, and they also consider the location before they are going to reserve their rooms. However the four hotels possess the advantage of being located in the heart of Colombo and close to the beaches. It is also vital that the amenities which are promised to the guest are offered so that the guests value them for the prices paid. Otherwise, the guests would feel dissatisfied with the hotel's false advertising which these hotels clearly do not want to create a negative image for themselves. Hoteliers required to have good strategy plan for their hotel. Guests require peace, environment friendly, safety with modern facilities which hotel managers consider essential for the guests to choose these particular hotels.

This question is in channel factors concept, its main variable is information search intention, where the guests consider if the hotel amenities and services are matching the prices offered. Before the guests are about to make a reservation, the guests would collect information what they required for reserving the hotel rooms in Sri Lanka. With this question 200 foreign visitors selected and check their idea of this question. 90 percent of people agree with these questions in strongly agreed and agreed both category, high responds having on agreed category and second highest category is having on strongly agreed category. 20 people responded as neutral, then this responds not effected for survey. Overall, people required good facilities and advanced technology.

Table 15: Frequency table of when reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities are (PF4)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
--	-----------	---------	---------------	--------------------

Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	20	10.0	10.0	10.5
	4	91	45.5	45.5	56.0
	5	88	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 18:- Frequency table of when reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities are (PF4)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Below table 16 is frequency table presented if the guest would find the technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user friendly and convenient to use, this question is related to guests, because some hotels have advanced technology but it's not user-friendly technology, which requires some assistance from the hotel staff to operate them. Therefore, this question is most usable and accurate question for guests to obtain an honest opinion about the hotel technology they have used until now. It is important to understand that with the technology advancement, the equipments could be used by all gender groups mentioned without any hassle. Because that is the main idea and intention which these hotels need to take into consideration.

This question is in product factor concept, main variables are product effectiveness and product changes, technology changes required with development that need to be an effective and efficient change for improvement. Moreover, this question feedback from responses having on agreed categories, 88 percent of people given as an agreed for this question, clearly separate strongly agreed category 111 people, as a percentage 55.5 percent respond on this category and 65 people in agreed category, as a percentage 32.5 percent people responds having on this category. It is vital to understand that age groups matter when considering the operation of technological amenities. The younger generation shows more interest in these technological advancements than the older generation.

Table 16: Frequency table of Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use (PF5)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5

	2	10	5.0	5.0	5.5
	3	13	6.5	6.5	12.0
	4	65	32.5	32.5	44.5
	5	111	55.5	55.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 19:- Frequency table of Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use (PF5)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 17 is a frequency table of there is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel. Understanding that these hotels share a historical culture, it is vital that technological advancements do not obstruct the uniqueness of these hotels. However understanding that these hotels are lacking technology within it can be noticed that the guests have agreed their importance for these four hotels. And with table 17 it can be implied that the level of technology used in these hotels are minimal and with the guests responds to the questionnaire, these advancements could be further enhanced.

Table 17: Frequency table of There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel (PF6)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	44	22.0	22.0	22.5
	4	62	31.0	31.0	53.5
	5	93	46.5	46.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 20:- Frequency table of There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can be done towards a country-based hotel (PF6)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Channel factors strategies (CF)

Table 18 is frequency table of question 25, this question more emphasizes the website and the advantage the website quality would possess for the guests prior to making a reservation. Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests; easy access to hotel

facilities and benefits. Because foreign guests mainly access the website, before visiting the hotel. if the guest shows interest in the particular hotel, the guest is willing to reserve the accommodation. The websites are quite critical in the reservation process as they include much information that is quite helpful for the guests including hotel images, information and rates.

Therefore, this question is in channel factor strategy concept, with that website quality and information quality variable category and this indicate the purchase decision of the guest. The website needs to be attractive and contain useful information for the guest to explore. As mentioned prior the hotels could further develop chat bots in their websites which could assist the guests to clarify certain information prior to making their reservation. However, these four hotels have exceptional, attractive websites with sufficient information that would allow the guests to obtain a clear idea of the hotel if this would be their very first visit to the hotel. Mainly the reason where 169 guests have agreed on this question is that understanding the hotels websites have similar quality and could be further developed by making them more user friendly. There are some instances where the guests would find difficulty in finding information which they require due to many pages included in their websites.

Table 18: Frequency table of Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests’ easy access to hotel facilities (CF1)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	30	15.0	15.0	15.5
	4	92	46.0	46.0	61.5
	5	77	38.5	38.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 21:- Frequency table of Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests’ easy access to hotel facilities (CF1)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

In frequency table 19 focusses on checking the payment method should be further developed where transactions are required to be via a hotel app or website, because of Covid-19 pandemic , this situation had made more instances where certain people prefer online payments. This causes no interaction with physical cash notes as this was a major concern pertaining to Covid-19. Despite many people paid cash as per table 10, understanding the current consequences they prefer to pay

via online web or app. 49 percent of the people in this table respond in the agree, with 98 out of 200 responding. In strongly agree there are 71 people given from 200 people, as a percentage 36 percent people in total of both highest values, 30 people in neutral category which has a percentage value of 15 percent. From this survey most now agree to pay for their accommodation via online. Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic many guests made transactions using cash. With many industries switching to card and online transactions, the use of cash became quite limited apart from a limited group of people.

Table 19: Frequency table of Payment method should be further developed where transactions are done via a hotel app or website due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic (CF2)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	30	15.0	15.0	15.5
	4	98	49.0	49.0	64.5
	5	71	35.5	35.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 22:- Frequency table of Payment method should be further developed where transactions are done via a hotel app or website due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic (CF2)

Frequency table of 20 question, tech savvy guest and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experience prior to booking a hotel. Currently most people tend to work with new technology. Almost every industry in the world have developed numerous technological advancements from the mobile to the vehicle an individual use. This question is in channel factor category because it is describing the purchase intention of the client variable. Guests are looking for these factors considering these are five star hotels and the prices are quite competitive. Then hoteliers required to identify the customers' major requirement, and according to these considerations need to make the background, and also need to form an attractive place to stay with suitable technological advancements. In this question, guests survey frequency table with respect to strongly agreed 43 percent people visitors respond in this question. As a count 85 people respond for this question. Agreed respond given by 42 percent respondents. As a number 84 people responded for this question. The most guests as a percentage from this survey are 85 percent of

people respond they are looking for modern and unique levels of technology when making a reservation. As discussed, prior mostly the younger generation expects the hotel to be providing such developments. Tourists prefer to be amazed with the different technology adopted by the hotel. Preferably in their next visit to a hotel the guest would expect a further enhancement towards the technology of the hotel compared to their previous visit.

Table 20: Frequency table of Tech Savvy guests and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experiences prior to booking a hotel (CF3)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	2	10	5.0	5.0	5.5
	3	20	10.0	10.0	15.5
	4	84	42.0	42.0	57.5
	5	85	42.5	42.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 23:- Frequency table of Tech Savvy guests and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experiences prior to booking a hotel (CF3)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Operational factors (OF)

Table 21 presents the Frequency table of Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees. Every industry required to update with the world, therefore the hotel industry is also required to update with time. The technological advancement for a hotel reduces the frustration of guests and enhances the efficiency of the hotel and its staff. The technology improvement would also assist employees to complete given tasks without much extra efforts. Therefore, the hotel’s main target is surveying the best accuracy service towards visitors, without any irritation of the guests.

Technology is very effective for performance in the industry, therefore hotel management are required to use good strategies to apply the technology in a positive manner. With respect to the particular question for the majority have responded mentioning strongly agreed as with technology advancements efficiency can be achieved for the hotel employees. Tasks internally and towards

the guests could be completed within a short period of time. So simultaneously the guests would be satisfied resulting in repeat arrivals and positive guest reviews.

According to guests' responses, the highest responses were towards agree of 94 people as a percentage 47 percent out of 200 total respond count. For this question secondly highest respond is on strongly agree as a percentage of total respond 41 percent, as a number 82 peoples' respond as a strongly agree with this question. Cumulative value of percentage in 88 percent. This question is in product factor because its main variables are employee and guest satisfaction, in this question it represents both variables with respect to both guest and employers' satisfaction. This question is one of key elements of this research as the prime motive of introducing technology is to boost the effectiveness of the day to day process since the checking out of a guest.

Table 21: Frequency table of Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees (OF1)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	23	11.5	11.5	12.0
	4	94	47.0	47.0	59.0
	5	82	41.0	41.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 24:- Frequency table of Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees (OF1)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 22 shows the Frequency of Tourists who tend to prefer technological developments favoring towards sustainability. As discussed prior, sustainability links towards the eco-friendliness. So, the importance of sustainability has to be promoted with the hotel itself. The technological advancements made has to be developed with respect to being sustainable. Because if this factor is not focused the hotel is not sustainable. Therefore, there is no actual purpose of the reduction of using plastic and paper if the technological advancements are not sustainable. In order to make it successful it is important that solar power facility is taken into consideration. At the moment many hotels are taking various measures to withdraw using certain materials which should be the primary step before making their technology advanced. In Sri Lanka most of the five star hotels follow green hotel concept. Therefore, sustainability is considered as one of the unique variable in the

hotel industry where the hotel management is required to think in every aspect on this process, before introducing the new technology. The hotel management should also need to consider about every stakeholder such employers, environment agencies and government rules. Because sustainability is the future of most industries. Understanding that the initial steps are being taken such as the minimal use of polythene and plastic chances to look at further sustainable developments are possible. However a time plan is necessary. With that the guests responded for this question with a high percentage given as strongly agreed from 200 people, as a percentage 44 percent people responded, and second highest range is agreed with 73 people agreed and its percentage is 37 percent agreed. In total , agreed and strongly agreed is 81 percent which would be critical to understand that the component of sustainability is quite critical for many tourists.

Table 22: Frequency table of Tourists tend to prefer technological developments favoring towards sustainability (OF2)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	2	3	1.5	1.5	2.0
	3	35	17.5	17.5	19.5
	4	73	36.5	36.5	56.0
	5	88	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 25:- Frequency table of Tourists tend to prefer technological developments favoring towards sustainability (OF2)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 23 is frequency table of employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel, in employee engagement of industry performance which is a most required quality in this industry. Because in usual context, understanding that the job role of employees will be minimal with technology, there will be instances where the commitment levels of employees would decline. Simultaneously the level of dedication that the employees have towards the guests could also decrease. This would be unacceptable as the guests expect good service for the price paid. In a hotel, the staff are required to have pleasant working backgrounds which include friendly colleagues, user friendly systems and up to date information. Or else the staff would be demotivated.

From this survey, most people answered as a strongly agreed as a percentage 49 percent people acknowledge with that. From 200 people, 98 people strongly agreed with these questions. As guests of the hotel they would highly be inclined towards strongly agreed as it is quite obvious even with technological advancements, staff need to perform equally well to provide an exceptional service to the guests. Second highest respond is an agreed 71 people agreed with these questions, so total of percentage value is 84 percent people agreed with this question. Therefore, hoteliers required to be more cautious on these areas and required to have more knowledge to a certain extent. On the other hand, there are 31 guests who were negative on this aspect believing that technology itself would take over most duties of the employees. This leaving the employees with a low self-esteem respective to their job role.

Table 23: Employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel (OF3)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	30	15.0	15.0	15.5
	4	71	35.5	35.5	51.0
	5	98	49.0	49.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 26:- Employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel (OF3)

Table 24 shows the Frequency of When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired. With the technological installation in the hotel the staff can be reduced to a minimum as most of the work can be done using machines. and that leads to the point that the staff that should be hired to work in the hotel is leads to a minimum, which will eventually lead to a halt in hiring new employees. The same number of participants were taken to collect the ideas about whether there is a less requirement to hire employees after the hotel is technologically improved. Nearly 50% of the participants strongly think that there is less requirement of hiring employees after the installation of technological improvements to the hotel. 82.5% or 165 of 200 participants think that it is agreeable with the low requirement of hiring the employees. Only 1 participant out of 200 participants strongly disagree with the statement that there is low requirement of hiring employees. While the total of 35 participants out of 200 disagree with the

statement as a percentage the participants who disagree with the statement is 17.5%. As a percentage 82.5% agree with the statement while 17% is neutral with the same statement and there is 0.5% who totally disagree with the same statement.

Table 24: Frequency table of When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired (OF4)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	34	17.0	17.0	17.5
	4	68	34.0	34.0	51.5
	5	97	48.5	48.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 27:- Frequency table of When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired (OF4)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 25 shows the Frequency of Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees. Most of the technologies that are installed in the companies need specialized assistance to get used to the systems and as the customers do not have that much time to be familiarized with the technologies the system should not be difficult for the customer to operate. The customer always think about the fastest and easiest way, it is proven in the survey as most of the majority agree with the statement. The highest number of participants can be seen agreeing with the statement as it over 50% of the participants. The participants that agree is 112 which is 56% of the participants. The agree amount with agree and strongly agree moves close to 100% as it is 94.5% which is 189 participants out of 200 participants. There is 1 participant out of 200 participants who strongly disagree with this statement as well. There are 10 participants who is neutral in this statement as well which is 05% of the total participants. This shows that the nearly 95% of the customers are looking for technologies that are more user friendly for them, which means that the systems must be simple so that anyone can use the technology for their own requirement. As a percentage 94.5% agree with the statement while 5% is neutral with the same statement and there is 0.5% who totally disagree with the same statement.

The survey shows majority of the people agree with all statements as the customers also need a better experience while in the hotels and the best service for the value they have spent on the hotel. More than three quarter of the participants always agrees with the statements that was surveyed while there was a participant who always strongly disagree with all the statements. And also, the addition of neutral and disagree percentages rarely crosses the quarter of the total participants. The conclusion is that the technological advancement of the hotel is something all customers are looking for while in a hotel of their choice.

Table 25: Frequency table of Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees (OF5)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	10	5.0	5.0	5.5
	4	112	56.0	56.0	61.5
	5	77	38.5	38.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 28:- Frequency table of Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees (OF5)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)

Table 26 shows the Frequency of Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catching rooms. When foreign visitors come to stay in Sri Lanka, they have several options in terms of accommodation. First, in five star hotel chains that include even a numerous International brands. Second, there are smaller properties that have comparable but smaller rooms, but they can offer great service. Lastly, a tourist can go the route of a villa or bungalow where guests typically rent the entire property which could be comprised of one to four bedrooms. This question is suitable for foreign guest because most foreign visitors have an idea about the international five star hotel culture, then they can suggest more idea about relate international five star hotel facilities that need to improve from the guest point of view. Therefore, they are looking for luxury facilities in five star hotels for the prices paid and the perceptions their minds have retsined.

According to the questionnaire responses most visitors responded as agreed, as a percentage 60 percent people respond as an agreed. Secondly respond as a strongly agreed 42 people respond as strongly agreed. Some tourists also have responded neutral and strongly disagreed in these respond which provided a determination that there are some tourists who rarely stay at a five star hotel or would even travel overseas. There are some guests who may be frequent travelers and the difference of these Sri Lanka based five star hotels compared to international hotel chains could have been quite visible. So these guests replied as strongly disagreed. Also, there are possibilities that these guests are not aware on the star categories of the hotels. But high percentage of visitors marked as an agreed and strongly agreed. The cumulative percentage of responses on the strongly agreed and agreed scale covers 81 percent of the total responses, which is the special highlight of this analysis.

Table 26 - Frequency table of Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catching rooms (GS1)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	5.5	5.5	5.5
	3	27	13.5	13.5	19.0
	4	120	60.0	60.0	79.0
	5	42	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 29:- Frequency table of Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catchi

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 27 present the Frequency of with the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective. The researcher's opinion strongly agree with this question because, an employee is required to provide the highest priority to guests who are the main resource individual of this industry. This is in operational factor concept with that guest satisfaction variable. In this variable is in the highest impact of the hotel industry, because then it provides the hotel background with a clear significance to the guests. Therefore, employees need to perform operations accurately and effectively when adopting minimal technology. So it is quite

clear that employees have to input less effort into their job role which would result in them becoming quite effective than expected.

In this survey, 78 percent of people respond as a agree and strongly agreed then they required effective employee in hotel industry, then 154 people are agreed with this question, out of 200 people. Then they are looking for more pleasant workers in hotel industry for survey them. Neutral respond also having in this question, as a count 45 people respond in this category.

Table 27: Frequency table of with the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective (GS2)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	3	45	22.5	22.5	23.0
	4	77	38.5	38.5	61.5
	5	77	38.5	38.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 30:- Frequency table of with the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective (GS2)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Frequency table of 27 give the summary record of people responds, in hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported, with this modern world every industry modernizes with IT facilities, and advanced technology. Considering this, the hotel industry also requires to update thereby allowing hotels to further develop technologically. Employees require a good technology background knowledge to develop the industry, otherwise they cannot operate with modern technology and also, they cannot provide good competition for other hotels lower if the employees are not technologically skillful. Therefore, employees are also required to have a good standard knowledge to work without any hesitation. So in order to consider this matter further, it is important that the hotel managers take necessary measures to provide the skill and knowledge towards the employees through trainings. So when new systems are introduced it will be important to hold three to five day training programs to improve the knowledge of these employees further.

This question is in the operational factor concept. If employee’s satisfaction reduces in terms of working processes with technology, this could lead to less effectiveness in hotel operations. The next important consideration is the guest satisfaction. When the hotel employees are not provided with proper training, there would be certain instances where the guest may have to spend longer time checking in or awaiting upon a request. Considering the responses, 92 people respond as a strongly agreed with this question, as a percentage 46 percent from 200 total respond, second highest respond is an agreed category as a count 79 people respond total percentage of these highest values 86 percent of people responded as an agreed. The employee satisfaction can be made with technological support.

With respect to the 200 responders based on that highest count having on agreed category, as a percentage 46 percent people respond as agreed, second highest category is strongly agreed category where 79 people responded as strongly agreed, and its percentage value is 39.5 percent. Other category respondents are in neutral and strongly agreed category where 31 people responded on these categories. As a percentage 5.5 cumulative percent approximately respond in negative category responds. However, a doubt arises for the guest where they could have less sense on the internal processes of the hotel. And it could be sometimes difficult for them to understand if the employees are genuinely pro-active or was technology assistance to them.

Table 27: Frequency table of Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. E.g.: developed IT facilities (GS3)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	2	10	5.0	5.0	5.5
	3	18	9.0	9.0	14.5
	4	79	39.5	39.5	54.0
	5	92	46.0	46.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 31:- Frequency table of Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. E.g.: developed IT facilities (GS3)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Table 28 shows the Frequency of The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field. Sri Lanka based five star hotels are suitable competitors for technological advancements considering the maturity of the hotel industry. Sri Lanka is one of the best tourist destinations in the world with a tropical climate which all the foreign tourists prefer. Therefore, most foreign visitors plan to spend their holidays in Sri Lanka. Then more hoteliers are hoping to update the technology and they are trying to provide suitable accommodation with up to date facilities that operates without any issues. Being a third world country, many individuals may argue the extent these hotel can go to technologically. However knowing these historic hotels barely adopt technology, certain advancements are still possible. In Sri Lanka, most of the technical evaluations of hotels are in recently developed hotels. New hotels are more technologically advanced than older hotels in Sri Lanka.

According to visitors' feedback people respond as an agreed, because with industry maturity is dependent to technological development. The reason is that a person without hotel knowledge, will not going to look at this as a major point where they are only thinking about hotel location and prices, also they would consider basic requirements. In overall, hotel facilities and technology of products are considered effective for five star hotels. 58 percent people respond as agreed for this question. Because the hotel industry's maturity is an important factor for hotel amenity technology advancement. Because some guest's intentions are far from enjoying the hotel amenities or considering the value for the money spent. Therefore, 77 percent is in cumulative value of agreed and strongly agreed in people responds. Other categories were neutral and disagreed responders are having in a small count. So, that percentage can be considered less necessary with positive frequency count.

Table 28 - Frequency table of The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field (GS4)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	.5	.5	.5
	2	20	10.0	10.0	10.5
	3	25	12.5	12.5	23.0
	4	116	58.0	58.0	81.0
	5	38	19.0	19.0	100.0

	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
--	-------	-----	-------	-------	--

Table 32:- Frequency table of The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field (GS4)

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

Futuristic Overview

Futuristic overview is the main concept of this question with that main variable is in competitive advantage where all five-star hotels should compete equally providing similar benefits and not lacking behind.

The survey was conducted with a participant of 200 participants to determine three statements about the increase of prices of the hotel after introduction of the technological changes, the low or less requirement of hiring of employees after the installation of technological changes and the technological changes should be more customer friendly. So that there will be less employee engagement. Most of the outcomes are based on the personal beliefs and personal experience. The survey shows the personal thoughts of these statements.

The hotel prices will increase with the changes that are going to do with the technological changes but as per the survey that was conducted with the customers the survey was conducted on these 200 participants and all those had different ideas about changing the price of the hotel rates due to the introduction of technological changes. The technological changes are high in price and the hotel management has to spend a lot of money on them. So to overcome these charges as the hotels have been practicing the same work plan and the staff has to be introduced with new technology with seminars and workshops. The majority of people, nearly 50% of the people who participated to the survey strongly agree that with the technological changes to the hotel the price of the hotel should increase. The majority of people think that the price should increase as 75.5% of the people agree with the idea. As the changes to the hotel mean that the company has to install new systems to the hotel and have the hotel more up to date and that will increase the hotel ratings. Furthermore, which will automatically lead to an increase of the prices of the hotel. In this survey 19% or 38 participants are neutral which is more than the percentage of people who disagree with the statement. This also shows that the majority of people have the idea of investments that the hotel is going to perform in order to provide a good experience to the customers, and the guests

themselves also have the idea of getting the best service from the hotel. There is only one individual out of the 200 participants that totally disagree with the statement that the hotel price should be increased with respect to the technological development of the hotel. The percentage of 5.5% also disagree with that statement that shows there are 11 people out of 200 participants that need the best facilities without causing an increase to the existing price ranges. As a percentage 75.5% agree with the statement while 19% is neutral with the same statement and there is 5.5% who totally disagree with the same statement.

Table 21: Frequency table of In the future hotel prices needs to extensively increase if further technological changes are to be made

Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	1	.5	.5	.5
2	10	10	5.0	5.0	5.5
3	38	38	19.0	19.0	24.5
4	64	64	32.0	32.0	56.5
5	87	87	43.5	43.5	100.0
Total	200	200	100.0	100.0	

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

4.3. Reliability analysis

An individual may examine the characteristics of measuring scales and the components that make up the scales using reliability analysis. In addition to providing data on the correlations between the scale's constituent items, the reliability analysis technique creates a variety of regularly used scale reliability measures. Inter-rater reliability estimates may be computed using pairwise correlation coefficients (Weaver et al., 2014). Reliability analysis calculates internal consistency, or how directly connected a collection of variables are to one another. It is evident that it serves as a gauge of scale dependability. It is concerned with precision and credibility, and the measuring instrument influences the extent to which the researcher may learn about the phenomena under study. The stability with which a measuring instrument produces a certain response when the scale being measured has not varied that in a research setting, a reliability coefficient of .70 or greater is regarded as "acceptable." The dependability of the data will be determined using Cronbach's

alpha values (George et al., 2018). The level of dependability of the variable is represented by Alpha Cronbach. An Alpha Cronbach's score greater than 0.6 denotes high reliability and a suitable score, according to Pallant (2001) it is regarded as weak when the Alpha Cronbach's value is less than 0.6. Alpha Cronbach's coefficients of 0.60 to 0.80 are considered to be a conventional yet sufficient range. Despite the fact that Alpha Cronbach's values of 0.8 to 1.00 are regarded as excellent.

The dependability of an instrument is defined as its dependability and consistency. Six likert scale questions obtained a reliability score of 0.824 for the independent variable of product factors. Since the calculated Cronbach alpha is larger than 0.6, it may be used to analyze the internal consistency of the Likert scale items (Table 22).

Table 22: Reliability Statistics for Product factors (PF)

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.818	.824	6

Table 34:- Reliability Statistics for Product factors (PF)

Three Likert scale questions obtained a reliability score of 0.843 for the independent variable of Channel factors strategies. Since the calculated Cronbach alpha is larger than 0.6, it may be used to analyze the internal consistency of the Likert scale items (Table 23).

Table 23: Reliability Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF)

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.839	.843	3

Table 35:- Reliability Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF)

Five Likert scale questions obtained a reliability score of 0.755 for the independent variable of Operational factors (OF). Since the calculated Cronbach alpha is larger than 0.6, it may be used to analyze the internal consistency of the Likert scale items (Table 24).

Table 24: Reliability Statistics for Operational factors (OF)

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.747	.755	5

Table 36:- Reliability Statistics for Operational factors (OF)

Four Likert scale questions obtained a reliability score of 0.824 for the dependent variable of for Guest and Employee satisfaction. Since the calculated Cronbach alpha is larger than 0.6, it may be used to analyze the internal consistency of the Likert scale items (Table 25).

Table 25: Reliability Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.837	.839	4

Table 37:- Reliability Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)

4.4. Validity Analysis of variables

If a statement is to correctly gauge some underlying notion, it must be more than just dependable. As a result, dependability by itself cannot tell users if accurately capturing an underlying reality. Validity in the context of the measurement equation refers to whether or not the true score component is the genuine score of the notion we seek to measure. A tool that is often used in quantitative research is a questionnaire. It is required to examine the validity of the questionnaire in order to establish if it is valid or not. Person Product Movement Correlation was used in SPSS to test the questionnaire's validity. By comparing the results of each item on the questionnaire with the overall score, the validity test for product movement and person movement correlations is completed. The questionnaire items are legitimate, according to a substantial correlation between each item and the overall score. The instrument is considered to be legitimate if the significant value is less than 0.005. When the significant value exceeds 0.05, the instrument is considered to be valid (Morgan et al., 2004).

According to the table 26, validity of Product factors (PF) instrument is acceptable. Since the significant value is 0.000 and that is less than 0.05.

Table 26: Validity Statistics for Product factors (PF)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		323.479	199	1.626		
Within People	Between Items	11.994	5	2.399	8.105	.000
	Residual	294.506	995	.296		
	Total	306.500	1000	.307		

Total	629.979	1199	.525		
Grand Mean = 1.70					

Table 38:- Validity Statistics for Product factors (PF)

According to the table 27, validity of Channel factors strategies (CF) instrument is acceptable. Since the significant value is 0.01 and that is less than 0.05.

Table 27: Validity Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		216.865	199	1.090		
Within People	Between Items	.370	2	.185	1.057	.01
	Residual	69.630	398	.175		
	Total	70.000	400	.175		
Total		286.865	599	.479		
Grand Mean = 1.74						

Table 39:- Validity Statistics for Channel factors strategies (CF)

According to the table 28, validity of Operational factors (OF) instrument is acceptable. Since the significant value is 0.018 and that is less than 0.05.

Table 28: Validity Statistics for Operational factors (OF)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		226.016	199	1.136		
Within People	Between Items	3.456	4	.864	3.004	.018
	Residual	228.944	796	.288		
	Total	232.400	800	.291		
Total		458.416	999	.459		
Grand Mean = 1.67						

Table 40:- Validity Statistics for Operational factors (OF)

According to the table 28, validity of Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS) instrument is acceptable. Since the significant value is 0.000 and that is less than 0.05.

Table 29: Validity Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		336.555	199	1.691		
Within People	Between Items	17.065	3	5.688	20.590	.000

	Residual	164.935	597	.276		
	Total	182.000	600	.303		
Total		518.555	799	.649		
Grand Mean = 1.92						

Table 41:- : Validity Statistics for Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)

4.5. Factor Analysis

4.5.1. Sample Adequacy

The data's suitability for factor analysis is determined using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test. The test evaluates the model's overall sampling efficiency as well as the sampling efficiency for each variable. The value is a representation of how much of the variation among the variables may be a common variance. The sample adequacy is measured by the KMO and must be more than 0.5 in order to go on with an acceptable factor analysis. Consider removing one of the variables from the analysis if any combination of variables has a value that is less than this. In a decent model, the off-diagonal elements should all be extremely small (around 0) (Yong et al., 2013). The survey's KMO value, which is 0.573, is acceptable. Therefore, it may be inferred that a researcher may conclude that there aren't enough variables for factor analysis. This indicates that there is a theoretically sufficient sample size to do the analysis (Table 30).

A further sign of how strongly the variables are related is the Bartlett's test. The correlation matrix's identification as an identity matrix is being tested in this instance. A matrix that has all diagonal members at 1 and all off-diagonal elements at 0 is said to be an identity matrix. The study team wishes to disprove this null hypothesis (Williams et al., 2013). Table 30 demonstrates the significance of the Bartlett's test of sphericity. In other words, its likelihood is less than 0.05. In practicality, the value is 0. Therefore, the null hypothesis may be rejected since the significance level is too low. The correlation matrix is thus not an identity matrix.

Table 30: KMO and Bartlett's Test for the sample data

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.573
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4035.483
	df	153
	Sig.	.000

Table 42:- KMO and Bartlett's Test for the sample data

4.5.2. Communalities

The list of communalities that follows in the result demonstrates how much of the variation in the variables has been explained by the extracted components. For example, almost 70.7 percent of the variation in PF1 and 65.9 percent of the variance in GS2, which measures employee and customer happiness, respectively, are both explained. (Appendix 1 contains the questions generated from the Likert scale.)

Table 31: Communalities of likert scale items

	Initial	Extraction
PF1	1.000	.707
PF2	1.000	.640
PF3	1.000	.823
PF4	1.000	.802
PF5	1.000	.783
PF6	1.000	.830
CF1	1.000	.702
CF2	1.000	.727
CF3	1.000	.785
OF1	1.000	.753
OF2	1.000	.812
OF3	1.000	.826
OF4	1.000	.807
OF5	1.000	.659
GS1	1.000	.778
GS2	1.000	.699
GS3	1.000	.652
GS4	1.000	.826

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 43:- Communalities of likert scale items

4.5.3. Total Variance Explained

The factors that can be extracted from the analysis are all shown in the next item together with their eigenvalues, the percentage of variation that can be attributed to each component, and the total variance of the factor and the preceding factors. Table 32 shows that out of the 18 scale components, the research has found a total of four tables. Notably, the first component explains 50.638 percent of the variation, followed by 9.658 percent, 7.805 percent, and 7.517 percent for the second and third factors. The remainder of the elements are all insignificant.

Table 32: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9.115	50.638	50.638	9.115	50.638	50.638	4.125	22.915	22.915
2	1.738	9.658	60.295	1.738	9.658	60.295	3.662	20.343	43.258
3	1.405	7.805	68.100	1.405	7.805	68.100	3.530	19.611	62.868
4	1.353	7.517	75.618	1.353	7.517	75.618	2.295	12.749	75.618
5	.914	5.077	80.694						
6	.836	4.644	85.338						
7	.517	2.874	88.212						
8	.472	2.623	90.835						
9	.462	2.565	93.400						
10	.274	1.525	94.925						
11	.222	1.236	96.160						
12	.214	1.191	97.352						
13	.147	.814	98.166						
14	.138	.769	98.935						
15	.094	.524	99.459						
16	.061	.341	99.801						
17	.029	.164	99.964						
18	.006	.036	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Table 44:- Total Variance Explained

The scree plot is a graph (Figure 8) of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve starts to flatten. It can be seen that the curve begins to flatten between factors 4 and 5. Note also that factor 5 has an eigenvalue of less than 1, so only four factors have been retained.

Figure 11: - Scree plot

4.6. Correlation Analysis of variables

A statistical technique used in studies to find the connection of two variables and evaluate the degree of their linear association is correlation analysis. The magnitude of change in one variable as a result of the change in the other is determined using correlation analysis, to simply describe it. A high correlation indicates a strong connection between the variables, whilst a low correlation indicates a poor correlation between the two variables (Gogtay et al., 2017). Researchers examine quantitative data gathered via research techniques like questionnaires and live polls using correlation analysis. Researchers look for trends, patterns, important linkages, and relationships between two variables or datasets (Senthilnathan, 2019). When a rise in one variable causes an increase in the other, there is a positive correlation between the two variables. An inverse relationship, indicates that as one variable rises, the other falls. The correlation coefficient is one of the statistical ideas that is most relevant to this kind of investigation. The correlation coefficient, denoted by the symbol r and often a number without units falling between 1 and -1, is the unit of measurement used to determine the strength in the linear connection between both variables in a correlation study.

Table 33 shows the correlations among variables. From this section correlation among dependent variable (guest and employee satisfaction) and independent variables (Product factors, Channel factors, and Operational factors) are described. With a statistical significance level of 0.000 and a Pearson correlation value of +0.813, the relationship among guest and employee satisfaction and the product factors of a certain hotel is statistically significant. Because the Pearson correlation value is greater than +0.5, it is clear that there is a strong positive link between a hotel's product factors and its guest and employee satisfaction ratings. With a statistical significance level of 0.000 and a Pearson correlation value of +0.775, the relationship among guest and employee happiness and the Channel factors of a certain hotel is statistically significant. Because the Pearson correlation value is greater than +0.5, it is clear that there is a strong positive link between a hotel's Channel factors and its guest and employee satisfaction ratings. With a statistical significance level of 0.000 and a Pearson correlation value of +0.789, the relationship among guest and employee satisfaction and the Operational factors of a certain hotel is statistically significant. Because the Pearson correlation value is greater than +0.5, it is clear that there is a strong positive link between a hotel's Operational factors and its guest and employee satisfaction ratings.

Table 33: Correlations of variables

		Product factors	Channel factors	Operational factors	Guest and Employee satisfaction
Product factors	Pearson Correlation	1	.673**	.858**	.813**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200
Channel factors	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1	.784**	.775**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200
Operational factors	Pearson Correlation	.858**	.784**	1	.789**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200	200
Guest and Employee satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.813**	.775**	.789**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	200	200	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 45: Correlations of variables

4.7. Multicollinearity Diagnosis Test

Multicollinearity refers to the linear connections between the independent variables in multiple regression analysis. Co linearity is the relationship between two variables that is almost perfect. Whenever a regression model has a number of variables that are substantially linked not only with the dependent variable but also with one another, this is known as multicollinearity. When there are strong correlations between the variables in a multiple regression model, this is known as multicollinearity. Once a researcher tries to determine how well each component may be used most effectively to predict or understand the response variable in a statistical model, multicollinearity can lead to skewed or misleading findings (Daoud, 2017). In conclusion, multicollinearity might lead to wider confidence intervals and worse probability estimations for the predictors. In other words, results from a multicollinearity model could not be reliable. Due to multicollinearity, putting extra variables to a regression analysis sometimes fails to provide a comprehensive overview of the model. The conclusion of the study is altered by the existence of multicollinearity, which raises the standard errors of each coefficient in the model. Certain of the major research variables become statistically insignificant due to multicollinearity. Regression coefficients become unstable due to multicollinearity's rise in variance, which makes it difficult to understand the coefficients.

4.7.1. Multicollinearity diagnosis by Pearson correlation coefficient

Regression analysis's main goal is to isolate the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable. The statistical stability of the regression coefficient prediction is represented by multicollinearity, which presents significant difficulties for model validation and interpretation. . There is a considerable likelihood of multicollinearity if the Pearson correlation coefficient per each independent variable is greater than 0.9.

There is a considerable danger of multicollinearity if the Pearson correlation coefficient of each independent variable is greater than 0.9. The results of table 34 show that each independent variable's Pearson correlation coefficient is less than 0.9. Consider the value of 0.673 for the Pearson correlation coefficient between Channel factors and Product factors. It falls below 0.9. There is no danger of multicollinearity as a result. Consider the value of 0.858 for the Pearson correlation coefficient between Operational factors and Product factors. It falls below 0.9. There

is no danger of multicollinearity as a result. Consider the value of 0.784 for the Pearson correlation coefficient between Operational factors and Channel factors. It falls below 0.9. There is no danger of multicollinearity as a result.

Table 34: Correlations between independent variables

		Product factors	Channel factors	Operational factors
Product factors	Pearson Correlation	1	.673**	.858**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	200	200	200
Channel factors	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1	.784**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200
Operational factors	Pearson Correlation	.858**	.784**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	200	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 46:- Correlations between independent variables

4.7.2. Multicollinearity diagnosis by VIF value

The confidence interval of predictor coefficients rises and, as a result, the variance of predictor coefficients is inflated when there is correlation across predictors. The VIF is a technique for calculating and measuring the extent of the inflated variance. Typically, the software will determine VIFs as part of the regression analysis, and the results will include a VIF section. If the VIF value is 1 it means the variables are not correlated. If the VIF value is between 1 and 5 the variables are moderately correlated and that is acceptable level. But if VIF value is higher than 5 it means there is a Multicollinearity of the variables.

According to the table, 35 VIF value of Product factors is 3.802 and it is an acceptable level. VIF value of Channel factors is 2.595 and it is acceptable level. VIF value of Operational factors is 4.403 and it is an acceptable level. All the VIF values are less than 5 hence it can be concluded that there is no Multicollinearity of the independent variables.

Table 35: Coefficients

Model	Collinearity Statistics
-------	-------------------------

		Tolerance	VIF
1	Product factors	.263	3.802
	Channel factors	.385	2.595
	Operational factors	.185	4.403
a. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction			

Table 47:- Coefficients

Table 36: Collinearity Diagnostics

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions			
				(Constant)	Product factors	Channel factors	Operational factors
1	1	3.899	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00
	2	.059	8.116	.88	.01	.15	.01
	3	.032	11.040	.09	.30	.62	.02
	4	.009	20.334	.03	.68	.22	.97
a. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction							

Table 48:- Collinearity Diagnostics

4.8. Multiple linear Analysis

The most frequent kind of regression analysis is multiple linear regression. In order to uncover variables that may more accurately predict a result, researchers might add extra parameters to their linear regression study. Multiple linear regression analysis is the name of this analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis may also be used to account for confounding factors. Confounding is reduced in randomized controlled experiments by randomization, although mild confounding may still exist due to slight imbalances in the outcome predictors. Multiple linear regression is used to present data and demonstrate the connection between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables as a predictive study. Matching a single line across a scatter plot is the central objective of multiple linear regression analysis. A line is more precisely fitted through a multidimensional cloud of data points by multiple linear regression. One dependent variable and two independent variables make up the basic form. The dependent variable is also known as the regressor, prognostic variable, prognosis criteria, or endogenous variable at times. The exogenous variables, predictor variables, or regressors are other names for the independent variables. For multiple regression with one addition, all the suppositions for simple regression (with a single independent variable) also hold true. Multicollinearity is a problem that arises when two independent variables have a strong relationship with one another. The analysis and interpretation

are affected, which is problematic. Examine the correlation coefficients for each pair of continuous (scale) variables before looking at potential multicollinearity. To simultaneously evaluate the combined impact of those parameters on the results, researchers can include a combination of numerical and categorical predictors in a multiple regression model, in addition to response variables between categorical predictors or between categorical and continuous prediction.

Table 37 allows for the determination of the study's outliers. Residual minimum and maximum values must not exceed -3.29 or +3.29 in order to assess the sample's outlier. The minimal value for the standard residual is -2.978 and standard. The highest residual value is 2.974. The values in Table 37 of the SPSS results are acceptable. Thus, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the sample contains no outliers.

Table 37: Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.1212	3.3866	1.9175	.56561	200
Residual	-.96127	.96136	.00000	.32076	200
Std. Predicted Value	-1.408	2.597	.000	1.000	200
Std. Residual	-2.974	2.974	.000	.992	200
a. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction					

Table 49:- Residuals Statistics

The data are perfectly regularly distributed, as seen in figure 8. One may thus infer that the plot is linear. The number 9 served as the conclusion.

Figure 12:- Zresid Normal P-P Plot

Figure 13:- Scatterplot of the regression model

Regression model's graph has a normal distribution. The histogram is normally distributed, as seen in figure 10.

Figure 14:- Histogram of regression model

According to the table 37 it can identified there are no any variables removed in the regression model and the method that is used is enter.

Table 38: Variable enter/ removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Operational factors, Channel factors, Product factors	.	Enter
a. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Table 50:- : Variable enter/ removed

The model's executive summary is shown in Table 11. R square values, which have a statistical significance of p 0.5 and a value of 0.757. This indicates that in Sri Lanka's hotel business, independent variables accurately predicted 75.7% of the variances in both guest and employee satisfaction. The independent nature of the observation was shown by the Durbin-Watson statistic, which was 2.039 and had a value between +1 and +3.

Table 51:- Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.870 ^a	.757	.753	.32321	.757	203.144	3	196	.000	2.039
a. Predictors: (Constant), Operational factors, Channel factors, Product factors										
b. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction										

Table 39: Model Summary

The F-ratio in the ANOVA table (Table 40) establishes whether the estimated regression model is a trustworthy fit for the data. The table demonstrates that the dependent variable (Guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel business in Sri Lanka) is statistically substantially predicted by the independent variables (Operational factors, Channel factors, and Product factors), $F(203.144) = 135.161$. To accept the regression model, the significant value of the ANOVA table has to be less than 0.005, and the obtained sig. value is 0.000, which is less than 0.005, and hence the regression model is acceptable.

Table 40: ANOVA table

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.664	3	21.221	203.144	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.475	196	.104		
	Total	84.139	199			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Operational factors, Channel factors, Product factors						
b. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction						

Table 52:- ANOVA table

The model's coefficients are shown in Table 41. The significance value P for the standardized beta values must be less than 0.05. According to the SPSS findings, all of the obtained P values are less than 0.05. That suggests the variables provide a significant and distinctive contribution to the dependent variable's prediction.

Table 41 shows that the Unstandardized Coefficients, B1 for Guest and Employee Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry in Sri Lanka and Product Factors is + 0.644. That means for each one unit increase in product factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.644 units. This means that for each one unit increase in product factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of +0.644 units.

Table 41 shows that the Unstandardized Coefficients, B1 for Guest and Employee Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry in Sri Lanka and Channel Factor is + 0.438. That means for each one unit increase in channel factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.438 units. This means that for each one unit increase in channel factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of +0.438 units.

Table 41 shows that the Unstandardized Coefficients, B1 for Guest and Employee Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry in Sri Lanka and Operational Factors equal + 0.038. That means for each one unit increase in operational factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.038 units. This means that for each one unit increase in operational factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of +0.038 units.

Table 41: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.972E-005	.084		.001	.999
	Product factors	.644	.086	.516	7.508	.000
	Channel factors	.438	.061	.406	7.156	.000
	Operational factors	.038	.112	.028	.344	.031
a. Dependent Variable: Guest and Employee satisfaction						

Table 53:- Coefficients

Regression equation

$$Y = 6.972E - 005 + 0.644X1 + 0.438X2 + 0.038X3$$

Y= Guest and Employee satisfaction

X1= Product factors

X2= Channel factors

X3 Operational factors

The developed regression equation is presented below. Since the significant value of each independent variable is less than 0.05, The alternative hypothesis is accepted. Guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka and product factors are equal to + 0.644, according to the regression equation. That means for each one unit increase in product factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.644 units. This means that for each one unit increase in product factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.644 units. Guest and employee satisfaction in the Sri Lankan hotel industry and channel factors equals + 0.438. That means for each one unit increase in channel factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.438 units. This means that for each one unit increase in channel factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of +0.438 units. Guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka and operational factors is equal to +0.038. That means for each one unit increase in operational factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.038 units. This means that for each one unit increase in operational factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of +0.038 units.

4.9. Cross Tabulation and Chi square Test

Once the variables are nominal, as they often are in scientific practice, one of the most helpful statistics for evaluating hypotheses is the Chi-square test of independence. Contrary to other statistical methods, the Chi-square may offer information on both the significance of any differences observed and the specific categories that contribute to those differences. Therefore, this statistic is among the most helpful tools in the scientist's arsenal of accessible analytic techniques due to the volume and level of information it may supply.

4.9.1. Gender and advanced technological experience that mostly prefer

The Case Processing Summary is essentially a description of the events that were handled when the crosstabs analysis was run, as its name would imply. Table 42 of the research showed 200 valid instances and no missing cases.

Table 42: Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Table 54:- Case Processing Summary

According to table 43, it shows that most female samples prefer smart rooms and they do prefer robot technology as their future technology advancement in hotels. 15 of the females prefer the advanced PMS system as their advanced technological experience, which they believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction. Similarly to the female 62 of the majority of male respondents are preferential for smart rooms and 49 of the responders have advanced technological experience in PMS systems, which they believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Table 43: Cross tabulation

Gender * In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction Cross tabulation							
			In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction				Total
			Smart rooms	Advanced PMS system	Robot technology	Kiosk machines	
Gender	Female	Count	42	15	0	2	59

		Expected Count	30.7	18.9	2.4	7.1	59.0
	Male	Count	62	49	8	22	141
		Expected Count	73.3	45.1	5.6	16.9	141.0
Total		Count	104	64	8	24	200
		Expected Count	104.0	64.0	8.0	24.0	200.0

Table 55:- Cross tabulation

The chi-square statistic may be found just to the right of "Pearson Chi-Square" in the Value column. The chi-square statistic in this table 44 has a value of 15.573. Under the same row, in the "Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)" column, is the p-value (.001). If this number is equal to or less than the specified alpha level, the result is significant (normally .05). The research rejects the null hypothesis, which states that the two variables are independent of one another since, in this instance, the p-value is less than the conventional alpha value. This indicates that there is no relationship at all between gender and the sophisticated technical experience that is most desired.

Table 44: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.573 ^a	3	.001
Likelihood Ratio	18.858	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.839	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 1 cells (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.36.			

Table 56: Chi-Square Tests

Table 45: Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.279	.001
	Cramer's V	.279	.001
N of Valid Cases		200	

Table 57: Symmetric Measures

4.9.2. Age category and advanced technological experience that mostly prefer

Table 46 shows that smart rooms were the most preferred technological advancement. Most 20-30 year old responders' samples are preferred for smart rooms, and they do prefer robot technology

as their future technology advancement in hotels. Advanced PMS systems necessitate advanced technological knowledge. 20-30 years, responders believe, will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction. 35 of the majority of 31–40 year old respondents are preferred for smart rooms, and 16 of the responders prefer advanced PMS systems as their advanced technological experience, which female respondents believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction. 7 of the majority (41-50 years old) respondents prefer smart rooms and they do not prefer either advanced PMS systems or robot technology.

Table 46: Cross tabulation

Age * In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction Cross tabulation							
			In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction				Total
			Smart rooms	Advanced PMS system	Robot technology	Kiosk machines	
Age	20 - 30 years	Count	62	48	0	14	124
		Expected Count	64.5	39.7	5.0	14.9	124.0
	31 – 40 years	Count	35	16	8	7	66
		Expected Count	34.3	21.1	2.6	7.9	66.0
	41- 50 years	Count	7	0	0	3	10
		Expected Count	5.2	3.2	.4	1.2	10.0
Total		Count	104	64	8	24	200
		Expected Count	104.0	64.0	8.0	24.0	200.0

Table 58: Cross tabulation

The chi-square statistic may be found just to the right of "Pearson Chi-Square" in the Value column. The chi-square statistic in this table 47 has a value of 26.019. Under the same row, in the "Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)" column, is the p-value (.001). If this number is equal to or less than the specified alpha level, the result is significant (normally .05). The research rejects the null hypothesis, which states that the two variables are independent of one another since, in this instance, the p-value is less than the conventional alpha value. This indicates that there is no relationship at all between age and the sophisticated technical experience that is most desired.

Table 47: Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	26.019 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	29.862	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.467	1	.494
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .40.			

Table 59: Chi-Square Tests

Table 48: Symmetric Measures

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.361	.000
	Cramer's V	.255	.000
N of Valid Cases		200	

Table 60: Symmetric Measures

According to table 45, the correlation between gender and advanced technological experience that most prefer is 0.279 and the correlation between age and advanced technological experience that most prefer is 0.0.361. Since both relationships are accepted, the alternative hypothesis is It shows there is an associated variable. But between age and advanced technological experience, it is mostly preferred to have a higher Phi value (table 48). Hence, hotel management needs to focus on mostly age-related nominal variables.

The latter part of the questionnaire consists of some open-ended questions. Some significant responses are described as below. Most of the responders have mentioned that due to the COVID-19 situation, the tourism industry has fallen apart, but due to technological features, there is great support for maintaining the tourism industry. Responder 22 mentioned that “*Particularly in COVID 19, information technology has been crucial to the hotel and tourist sectors. Technology has aided in cost-cutting, boosting operational effectiveness, and enhancing services and customer satisfaction. A better reservation, guest service, and communication system will benefit both consumers and companies.*”

When focused on the question of technology enhancement of hotel and employee motivation, most of the responders mentioned that, as technological improvements are made, employee retention and employee satisfaction would arise. However, responders do not agree with the statement "could this also create a loss in employee motivation due to minimal workload". They mention that technology enhancement helps motivate employees due to minimum workload. *"Hotel computer systems provide communication between hotel groups with several sites. The technology also makes it simpler to obtain information and keeps personnel on the same page, greatly improving the experience for hotels' customers. Reservations, housekeeping data, and guest requests may all be accessible on the same system. As a result, this hotel system greatly aids in the effectiveness, efficiency, and accuracy of hotel operations."*

Some of the responders have mentioned that they have already established the technological advancements but need to improve with the worldwide updated level. And they mentioned that they needed more help for cyber security things. *"Since hotel industry employ a large number of people and have accessibility to a wealth of consumer data, the tourism sector is a key target. Malware and phishing assaults are two of the major concerns in this sector, but because of the current dependence on data, businesses are also at risk from human mistake brought on by their own staff. To keep the company secure, this necessitates spending on cybersecurity education and a variety of hardware and software solutions. Therefore, the government must adhere to data protection laws and the most recent policies and regulations"*

One of the most intriguing areas of tourism hotel technology is robotics, which is continually developing. Robots, for instance, have been employed at hotels to serve in concierge-like capacities, assisting to welcome visitors and deliver information. Certain hotels have increased their usage even further by including cleaning and baggage handling tasks. As a result, respondents have given good feedback on the Sri Lankan tourist sector and robots. *"Robots may be used in hotels to help in meal preparation and service. Additionally, pre-screening is done by robots used by travel agencies, which makes client wait times more efficient. Additionally, the hotel may see an increase in local and out-of-town guests thanks to this new technology. The use of robots has actually expanded in reaction to COVID, as has the usage of many other technological advances in the technology sector, particularly since they have the ability to lessen human-to-human interaction"*.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

According to the analysis of the data sample, the author has identified that the front office and the food and beverage department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in these hotels. In the past few years, technology has frequently updated the world. As a result, these updates have affected every industry. Technology evolution is not suitable for every industry or every department in the same industry. Maybe departments or places can't be applied for new technology facilities because certain advancements are difficult to apply, or employees do not like to adapt to new technology. For these reasons, a few departments do not render good service for their clients. After that, hotel guests are looking for effective service from every department. Therefore, it is not only useful for accommodation in the hotel industry. They should be concerned with the technological development of both accommodation and services. And the study has identified that the front office and food and beverage departments are not operating technologically efficient. Since online banking and e-commerce payment platforms are in a technologically effective situation, most guests prefer to pay using a physical debit or credit card. According to the multiple linear regression analysis results, the selected hypothesis is accepted as an alternative hypothesis. They are shown below.

- There is a relationship between the Product Factors and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel
- There is a relationship between the Channel factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel
- There is a relationship between the Channel factors strategies and the Guest and Employee satisfaction in the hotel
- There is an associate between gender and preference of future advanced technological experience
- There is an associate between age category and preference of future advanced technological experience

Hence, it can be concluded that all three independent variables have a significant effect on guest and employee satisfaction. When focusing on the degree of influence of guest and employee satisfaction according to the regression equation of the study, it was identified that product factors have the highest positive impact. That means for each one unit increase in product factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.644 units. The product factor concept builds upon these variables. These are hotel brand conditions, product changes, product effectiveness, and sustainability. The hotel brand is the essential variable in five-star hotel concept hotels, because with the brand name, customer attraction is higher in the hotel industry than in other hotels. When tourist guide people also recommended the hotels to foreign tourists, they did not consider the hotel's technology, facilities, and customer service. The hotel industry required advanced technology to deal with the time change. Because technology is changing every day in the world, hotel management must keep up. Otherwise, the business will be unable to grow, and customer attraction and item demand will suffer as a result of the lack of updates. As a result, hotels must keep up with the rest of the world. Product effectiveness is automatically increased as technology evolves into a more reliable phase. This change automatically increases customers without any effect. That change needs to be an attractive and be a useful change at the right time and place.

Secondly, the most influential factor is the channel factor. Guest and employee satisfaction in the Sri Lankan hotel industry and channel factors equals + 0.438. That means for each one unit increase in channel factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.438 units. Channel factor strategies is the concept of in hotel technology. It works as an independent variable in a futuristic overview. This concept worked with website quality and information quality, payment method, customer relationship, information search intention, and purchase intention as these variables affected the channel factor. The website and information sharing method must be of high quality; otherwise, visitors will disregard this hotel because they are looking for information these days through websites and social media. If this information is not at standard level, they do not care about these hotels, especially foreign visitors, because they need clear information about places with their services and prices. Payment method: In the model technology, most payments are completed online, and credit and debit cards are also used for this. But foreign visitors are most happy to pay online because they have trust and they do not like to

use money for security purposes. Therefore, in the hotel industry, service is required to change according to customer requirements.

The least impacted factor is the operational factor. Guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka and operational factors is equal to +0.038. That means for each one unit increase in operational factors, there is an increase in guest and employee satisfaction in the hotel industry in Sri Lanka of 0.038 units. Intention of operation variables are technological improvements leading to employee effectiveness, which leads to employee satisfaction. Then the customer was also satisfied with the effective service. Then guest satisfaction will also be affected by the technological improvements leading to easy facility usage by the hotel guests. This will be a useful point for customer attraction. This is also a business strategy for customer attraction to hotels. Therefore, technology development is a key point in this industry, with world evaluation. Also, this point describes further in guest satisfaction, the technological improvements ongoing in a hotel are adequate. Most of the three-star hotel systems do not have sufficient technology development for foreign visitors' attractions at a reasonable price.

According to the cross-tabulation chi-square test, researchers discovered that age and gender have an impact on preferred future advanced technological experience. Since both relationships are accepted, the alternative hypothesis is It shows there is an associated variable. But between age and advanced technological experience, it is mostly preferred to have a higher Phi value. Hence, hotel management needs to focus on mostly age-related nominal variables.

5.2. Discussion

The primary purpose of this research is to investigate how to increase the standard of Sri Lanka's five-star hotels to that of worldwide hotel companies. Tourists are familiar with well-known hotel brands such as Hilton, Shangri-La, Intercontinental, and Four Seasons, but this study focuses on technologically upgrading the Colombo-based hotel model. The comparison of Colombo's two largest 5-star hotels will be critical in assessing the variations in money received from visitor visits. According to the research findings, hotel management should be more focused on hotel operation elements while implementing advanced technologies. In addition, hotel management must concentrate on the hotel's channel aspects. The website must be updated on a regular basis, and the dashboard must be user pleasant.

Some of the recommendations for technology enhancement of the hotel are developed as below. The mobile system's flexibility allows it to provide additional advantages. For example, staff employees have immediate access to the business intranet, enabling them to provide visitors with better service. Their capacity to perform effectively and with comprehensive knowledge rises as a result of having accessibility to news reports and real-time modifications. And also, management may optimize their operational procedures using information on employee behavior. The trick is to select technology that will provide managers access to collect and analyze employee data while saving the hotel's team time on repetitive chores by making all the information they need right at their fingertips whenever they need it. Providing out regular updates on VIP visitors or check-ins or having a portable database with papers on security, personnel HR, instruction, employee marketing, and departmental reports are examples of features like communication. These allow personnel to always be educated, keep current with new information, and develop the necessary abilities to carry out their duties effectively and provide outstanding client service. Simply adopting this function may boost customer happiness and retention, as well as productivity—all of which benefit the bottom line. Another crucial element of a hotel stay is the cleanliness of the rooms, and using housekeeping management software may make a huge difference in this area. Tracking housekeeping at a hotel may be difficult since there are so many factors to consider, like first-time check-ins, check-outs, and particular requests from customers, to mention a few.

5.5. Limitations of the study and suggestions for further research

The current study only focused on Sri Lanka's five-star hotels, excluding well-known hotel brands like Hilton, Shangri-La, Intercontinental, and Four Seasons, and the focus of this study is on technologically advancing the Colombo-based hotel model. Since there are several other hotels in Sri Lanka that have a great contribution to the tourism industry, future research needs to cover all levels of hotels in Sri Lanka.

References

- *17 Hotel Technology Trends to watch in 2022*, Intellect Soft, 6th December 2021
- *5 Hotel technologies that can create personalized guest experiences*, Trivago business Blog, 8 July 2019
- Ambepitiya KR and Dharmasiri UR, *The Study of Professional Training to Improve Customer Satisfaction in Small and Medium Scale Hotels in Sri Lanka*, Colombo Business Journal, 01st June 2017
- Baroudi J and Orlikowski J, *A short form measure of user satisfaction and notes on use*, Journal of Management Information, October 1988
- Beldona, S and Cobanoglu C, *Importance – performance Analysis of guest technologies in the lodging Industry*, Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly, October 2007
- Chen M, *Personalization in hotels: stay relevant with customized services*, EHL insights, February 2022
- Cobanoglu C, *Analysis of business travelers' hotel selection and satisfaction*, Oklahoma state University Stillwater, April 2001
- Cobanoglu C, Berezin K, Kasavana M and Erdem M, *The Impact of Technology Amenities on Hotel Guest Overall Satisfaction*, Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism, 14 October 2011
- Daoud, J.I., 2017, December. Multicollinearity and regression analysis. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 949, No. 1, p. 012009). IOP Publishing.
- Davis D, Bagozzi P and Warshaw R, *User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models*, Management Science, April 1989
- De Silva P, *Overdevelopment, shortage of trained employees will affect hospitality industry*. Daily FT, 4th February 2020
- Delone W and McLean E, *Information Systems Success: The Quest for the dependent variable*, Journal of Management Information Systems, March 1992
- Domanski M, *The concept of a smart hotel and its impact on guests' satisfaction, privacy and the perception of the service quality*, Diva Portal, July 2020
- Dreesen A and Elfers J, *Review of the Kano model – practical example tourism industry*, Diva Portal, (n.d)

- Ekanayake B and Ramachandra T, *Challenges in hotel building refurbishment project in Sri Lanka*,
- Fernando S, *Managing the Post-War Tourism development in Sri Lanka*, International Journal of Business and Social Science, November 2016
- Fox J, *Technology changes look, use of hotel lobbies*, Hotel Management, 17 June 2020
- *Galle Face Hotel begins historical restoration project*, Daily FT, 4th September 2013
- George, D. and Mallery, P., 2018. Reliability analysis. In *IBM SPSS Statistics 25 Step by Step* (pp. 249-260). Routledge.
- Gnanapala A, *Factors affecting customer Satisfaction related to the Tourism Hotel Industry in Sri Lanka*, Journal of Tourism and Hospitality management, July 2014
- Goddard, W. and Melville, S. *Research methodology: An introduction*. Juta and Company Ltd. 2004
- Gogtay, N.J. and Thatte, U.M., *Principles of correlation analysis. Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*, 65(3), pp.78-81. 2017.
- Gupta, B.N. and Gupta, N., *Research methodology*. SBPD Publications. 2022.
- Gyau A and Stringer R, *Institutional isomorphism and adoption of E-Marketing in the hospitality industry: a new perspective for research*, Agri-culture and Tourism, April 2011
- Hertzfeld E, *Samsung Alice debut new smartwatch product for hotel industry*, Hotel Management, 19th June 2018
- Hobbs R, *4 use cases of facial recognition in the Hospitality Industry*, Revfine, 13 May 2021
- Hotel Developers (Lanka) PLC, Financial statements, 31 March 2019, Retrieved from: https://cdn.cse.lk/cmt/upload_report_file/542_1560504771644.pdf
- Hotel Technology, *Marriot Bonvoy*, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://www.marriott.com/meeting-event-hotels/meetings/mobility-and-tech.mi>
- *Hotel technology: Your property's complete guide to hotel industry systems and products*, SiteMinder, 2022
- Hou H and Wu H, *Tourists' knowledge of green building design and their intention of staying in green hotels*, Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research, March 2020

- *How Hotel Technology Can Help You Attract New Guests To Your B&B*, Little Hotelier, 2022
- *International Tourism Leaders' summit & Tourism research conference*, University of Colombo Tourism study program, 2019
- Jayasuriya S, *Roadmap to address hospitality skills shortage*, Sunday Observer, 1st July 2018
- Jayasuriya S, Steele P and Weerakoon D, *Post-Tsunami Recovery: Issues and Challenges in Sri Lanka*, ADB Institute Research paper Series, January 2006
- Kaldeen M and Nawaz S, *Impact of Knowledge Management Capabilities on Performance of Star Hotels in Sri Lanka*, International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, February 2020
- Kansakar P, Munir A and Shabani N, *Technology in the hospitality Industry: prospects and challenges*, IEEE consumer Electronics magazine, May 2019
- Kasim A, *The need for business Environmental and social responsibility in the Tourism Industry*, International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration, 25 September 2008
- Kim J, Christodoulidou N and Brewer P, *Impact of individual differences and consumers' readiness on Likelihood of Using Self-service Technologies of Hospitality setting*, Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research, 1 February 2012
- Kim T, Lee J and Law R, *An empirical examination of the acceptance behaviour of hotel front office systems: An extended technology acceptance model*, Tourism Management, June 2008
- Kirk D, *Environment management in hotels*, international journal of contemporary Hospitality Management, 1 November 1995
- Kosow, H. and Gaßner, R., *Methods of future and scenario analysis: overview, assessment, and selection criteria* (Vol. 39, p. 133). DEU. 2008.
- Kothari, C.R., *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International. 2004.
- Lam T, Cho V and Qu H, *A study of hotel employee behavioral intentions towards adaption of information technology*, Hospitality Management, October 2007

- Lee J, Hsu L, Han H and Kim Y, *Understanding how consumers view green hotels: How a green image can influence behavioral intentions*, Journal of sustainable tourism, 6 March 2010
- Mackenzie, N. and Knipe, S. *Research dilemmas: Paradigms, methods and methodology*. Issues in educational research, 16(2), pp.193-205. 2006
- Magnusson, D., *The person approach: Concepts, measurement models, and research strategy*. New directions for child and adolescent development, 2003(101), pp.3-23. 2003.
- Mauricio A, *Perception Model*, Science Direct, January 2012
- Mbasera M, Du Plessis E, Saayman M and Kruger M, *Environmentally-friendly practices in hotels*, Acta Commercii-Independent Research Journal in the Management Sciences, March 2016
- Moliner M, Monferrer D, Estrada M and Rodriguez R, *Environmental sustainability and the Hospitality customer experience: A study in Tourist Accomodation*, Department of Business Administration and Marketing, 25 September 2019
- Moorthy R, *Foreign hotels seek to import labour to fill shortage gap*, Sunday Observer, 22nd January 2017
- Morgan, G.A., Leech, N.L., Gloeckner, G.W. and Barrett, K.C., 2004. *SPSS for introductory statistics: Use and interpretation*. Psychology Press.
- *Mount Lavinia Hotel says soft refurbishment underway before it reopens to public*, Daily Mirror Online, 27th October 2020
- Mourougan, S. and Sethuraman, K., *Hypothesis development and testing*. IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM), 9(5), pp.34-40. 2017.
- Mushtaq M, *Sri Lanka tourism still reeling since Easter attacks*, Asia Pacific, 7 December 2019
- O'Hare G and Barrett H, *The fall and rise of the Sri Lankan tourist industry*, Jstor, 4 October 1993
- Orth, C.D.O. and Maçada, A.C.G. *Corporate fraud and relationships: a systematic literature review in the light of research onion*. Journal of Financial Crime, 28(3), pp.741-764. 2021

- Pallant, J.. *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS*. Routledge. 2020
- Palmer W, *Website usability, design and performance metrics*, Information system research, January 2002
- Pourfakhimi S, Duncan T and Coetzee W, *A critique of the progress of E-tourism technology acceptance research: Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, April 2019
- Proposed Amendment to hotels' classification criteria, Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority, 20th April 2016
- *Rebuilding tourism industry post COVID-19*, Daily FT, 4 May 2021
- Saunders, M. and Lewis, P., *Doing research in business and management*. Pearson. 2017.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P.H.I.L.I.P. and Thornhill, A.D.R.I.A.N. *Research methods. Business Students* 4th edition Pearson Education Limited, England. 2007
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P.H.I.L.I.P. and Thornhill, A.D.R.I.A.N., *Research methods. Business Students* 4th edition Pearson Education Limited, England. 2007.
- Sawyers S, *Why do hotel workers look so fragile and weak?* LinkedIn. 24th November 2017
- Schell, C., *The value of the case study as a research strategy*. Manchester Business School, 2(1), pp.1-15. 1992.
- Seddon B, *A recertification and extension of the DeLone and McLean model of IS Success*, Information Systems Research, 1 September 1997
- Senthilnathan, S., *Usefulness of correlation analysis*. Available at SSRN 3416918. 2019.
- Short T, Guest preferences for technology use in hotels Industry view, Software Advice, 5 February 2015
- Snyder, H. *Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines*. Journal of business research, 104, pp.333-339. 2019.
- Sun S, Cegielski C, Jia L and Hall D, Understanding the factors affecting the organizational adoption of big data, Journal of computer information systems, 7 October 2016
- Taylor M, *Sri Lankan Hotel Industry Faces Opportunities and Challenges (Round Table Discussion)*, Accidental Travel Writer, (n.d)

- The 7th World Construction Symposium 2018: Built Asset Sustainability: Rethinking Design, Construction and Operations, 01st July 2018
- Tim E, *How Technology can impact the success of your hotel?* RoomKeyPMS, 9 July 2019
- Ukwatte JL and Abeysekara N, *The impact of service quality on customer loyalty in the Sri Lankan hotel sector*, Proceedings in Management, Social Sciences and Humanities, 9th International Research Conference-KDU, Sri 2016 Lanka, 2016
- Umasuthan H and Park O, *The challenges faced by hotel service industry in Sri Lanka*, International Journal of Tourism Sciences, May 2018
- *Using Technology to increase guest satisfaction and Loyalty*, Intelity, 20 February 2020
- Varotsis N, *Quality standards in Hospitality Industry: Ionian Region*, Journal of Tourism & Hospitality, 2022
- *Waters Edge unveils Sri Lanka's First Eco-friendly, smart and sustainable boutique resort*, Ada Derana Business, 20 May 2021
- Weaver, B. and Maxwell, H., *Exploratory factor analysis and reliability analysis with missing data: A simple method for SPSS users. The Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 10(2), pp.143-152. 2014.
- Wickramasinghe K, *Adoption of Environmental Management practices in the Hotel industry in Sri Lanka*, Institute of Policy studies of Sri Lanka, December 2016
- Wickramasinghe V and Takano S, *Revival of Tourism in Sri Lanka following the December 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami*, Journal of Natural disaster Science, January 2007
- Wijesiri L, *Developing tourism in Sri Lanka and challenges*. Daily News, 27th February 2010
- Wijesundara W, *An Evaluation of Graduates' Perception on Employment in Tourism and Hospitality Industry*, Tourism, Leisure and Global change, 2015
- Williams, B., Onsmann, A. and Brown, T., *Exploratory factor analysis: A five-step guide for novices*. Australasian journal of paramedicine, 8(3). 2010.
- Woodruff B and Gardial F, *know your customer: new approach to understanding customer value and satisfaction*, Blackwell business, June 1996
- Yong, A.G. and Pearce, S., 2013. *A beginner's guide to factor analysis: Focusing on exploratory factor analysis. Tutorials in quantitative methods for psychology*, 9(2), pp.79-94.

- Yuan Y and Tseng Y, Tourism information technology research trends 1990-2016, Tourism Review, August 2018

Appendices

Questionnaire

Section A

01. Gender

Female

Male

02. Age

20 - 30 years

31 - 40 years

41 - 50 years

Above 50 years

03. Which department of the hotel require the most attention to develop technologically in this hotel

- Front Office
- Food & Beverage
- Housekeeping
- Kitchen

04. Which department of this hotel was operating effectively that was past your expectations?

- Front Office
- Food & Beverage
- Housekeeping
- Kitchen

05. Do the rooms in this hotel provide eco-friendly amenities such as being paperless, avoiding plastic, 100% cotton clothing etc.

- Yes
- No

06. As a tourist, would you prefer making reservations online via the hotel website?

- Yes
 - No
07. Do most of the international hotels you have visited or worked at mention all their technological amenities in the hotel website?
- Yes
 - No
08. Which payment method do you prefer?
- Cash
 - Physical debit/credit card
 - transaction Online
09. In the future which advanced technological experience do you believe will have a major positive impact on customer satisfaction?
- Smart rooms
 - Advanced PMS system
 - Robot technology
 - Kiosk machines

Section C

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? Based on your view, please tick on the relevant number

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Moderate, 4 = Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree

No.	Question	1	2	3	4	5
Product factors (PF)						
PF1	As the International hotel chains, tourists tend to look for technological advancements in country based five-star accommodations					
PF2	Most of the hotel amenities and equipment's require technological developments in this hotel					
PF3	This hotel can develop further on the concept of Sustainability (being eco-friendly)					
PF4	When reserving a hotel room, all tourist types only consider the hotel facilities and how technologically developed these facilities are					
PF5	Guests would find technologically developed facilities in a hotel more user-friendly and convenient to use					
PF6	There is a certain limit to the number of technological improvements which can to be done towards a country-based hotel					
Channel factors strategies CF		1	2	3	4	5

CF1	Hotel website development is the main key factor to be further developed for guests' easy access to hotel facilities and benefits					
CF2	Payment method should be further developed where transactions are done via a hotel app or website due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic					
CF3	Tech Savvy guests and even the modern generation tourists tend to look for new technological experiences prior to booking a hotel					
Operational factors (OF)		1	2	3	4	5
OF1	Technological advancements for a hotel would reduce guest frustration and boost effectiveness of the hotel and their employees					
OF2	Tourists tend to prefer technological developments favouring towards sustainability					
OF3	Employee dedication and efforts should be provided simultaneously as the performance of technology in a hotel					
OF4	When developing a hotel technologically, there is a less need for many employees to be hired					
OF5	Hotels should require technological developments which are more customer friendly and not be only operated on permission of employees.					
Guest and Employee satisfaction (GS)						
GS1	Sri Lankan based five-star hotels such as Galle Face Hotel, Mount Lavinia Hotel, Kingsbury Hotel, Galadari Hotel are maintaining parallel standards compared to international chain hotels in Sri Lanka ex: hotel atmosphere, eye-catching rooms					
GS2	With the limited technology prevailing in this hotel the employees are well supportive and effective					
GS3	. Hotel employees tend to be pro-active when they are technologically supported. Eg: developed IT facilities					
GS4	The Sri Lanka based five-star hotels are suitable contenders for technological developments considering their maturity in the hotel field					
Futuristic Overview		1	2	3	4	5
FO	In the future hotel prices needs to extensively increase if further technological changes are to be made					

29. With the current ongoing pandemic, will technology be a crucial factor for a tourist to consider when making a room reservation or would they look for other factors such as price, locations and ratings/reviews? Please explain

.....
.....
.....

30. As technological improvements are made, employee retention and employee satisfaction would arise. However, could this also create a loss in employee motivation due to minimal workload?

.....
.....
.....

31. Hotels such as Mount Lavinia Hotel and Galle Face Hotel possess historical culture. Would this essence be destroyed if technology is introduced to these hotels? Please explain

.....
.....
.....

32. As a developing nation, what is the first futuristic action that the government should emphasize on prior to developing hotels technologically?

.....
.....
.....

33. The ultimate aim of technology is Programmed Artificial Intelligence (Robots). As most five-star hotels in other nations are expanding to such territories today, would this become a successful strategy in Sri Lanka someday?

.....
.....
.....

34. If such Colombo hotels develop technologically in the near future, should this development be expanded to the Sri Lanka based five-star hotels located away from Colombo and would it be as effective as the hotels in Colombo?

.....
.....
.....

35. Lastly, what is your opinion on country based five-star accommodations matching the standards of international hotel chains to gain a competitive advantage?

.....

.....
.....

Thank you